

The Mojo Revolution:
A Critical Evaluation of Mobile Journalism
Practice and its Impact on Journalistic
Identity

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Submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the
degree of
Doctor of Philosophy.
University of the West of Scotland

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Guidance for Readers

This study contains a written thesis and a video documentary shot on mobile devices. All images presented in the thesis similar to the one below are click-through hyperlinks that will take digital readers to video content gathered and produced during this study.

Further to this, shorter individual case-study by case-study self-contained video clips are available as click-through links in the latter parts of the thesis, if digital readers wish to observe the creative journey while concurrently reading the dissertation. Participant information documentation pertaining to the video content gathering is presented in the appendices.

Click-through link to creative practice output: digital readers can view through clicking on the image below.

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Research Outputs

Publications

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Mahon, J. (2021) 'How the Covid Pandemic Changed Digital Journalism', *The Conversation UK*

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Conferences + Presentations

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University of the West of Scotland, MCS Symposium, 2018, *The Mojo Revolution*

University of Glasgow, Seminar, Department of Sociology, 2019, *A Mojo Revolution*

PubPhd Seminar, Scotland, 2019, *Mobile Journalism News from The Palm of Our Hand*

Association for Journalism Education, Conference Paper, Canterbury, 2018, *MOJO*

Association for Journalism Education, Conference Paper, Paris, 2019, *Untold MOJO Stories*

World Journalism Education, Conference Paper, Paris, 2019, Ignite, *The Mojo Revolution*

Media Education Summit, Conference Paper, Leeds, 2021, *Mojo Empowering Voices*

Broadcasts

East TN PBS, Broadcast in NC, TN, VA and KY, 24th July 2019, *The Mojo Revolution*

PBS Passport, US national distribution, 31st July 2019, *The Mojo Revolution*

Amazon Prime Video, UK and USA availability, November 2019, *The Mojo Revolution*

Film Festivals

Crown Wood International Film Festival, 2019: Winner, Best Mobile Film

L'Age d'Or International Arthouse Film Festival, 2019: Winner, Critics Choice Award

African Smartphone International Festival 2019: Winner, International Documentary

White Unicorn International Film Festival 2019: Winner, Best Mobile Film

Virgin Spring Cinefest, 2019: Winner, Best Mobile Film

MiMo Milano Mobile Film Festival, 2019, Finalist, Mobile Documentary

The International Film and Television Festival, 2020, Winner, Best Mobile Film

Ethical Approval

The following thesis and doctoral research has received ethical approval between 2017 and 2019 from the then School of Media, Culture & Society at UWS Paisley Campus, for fieldwork gathering in Scotland, USA, India and Switzerland.

Your application 4638: The Mojo Revolution, submission reference 2226,

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of smartphone technology on the practices of broadcast journalists in a select number of newsrooms in different continents. The research comprises two main elements: a mobile video documentary; and a written analysis of mobile journalism with a reflection and discussion on the data collected from each site. The research demonstrates that mobile journalism has proven to be variously a solution, a disruption, a reaction and a tool, influenced by both economic and societal trends that affect newsgathering processes.

The video submission involved 20 days of content gathering and fieldwork from four newsrooms in India, USA, Scotland and Switzerland. The research drew on 30 interviews with news editors, mobile journalists, media academics and TV news producers examining their experiences of transitions to mobile journalism and its subsequent impacts. The documentary output of the study is a fly-on-the-wall observational style piece incorporating talking heads with little on screen interference from myself. This approach allowed the interviewees to dictate the flow of the film and bring the viewer on a journey into the journalist's worlds in their evolving digital newsrooms.

I began the doctoral journey as a product of mobile journalism as well as a supporter of its implementation and have solo shot, edited and produced the piece using the same technology utilized by the journalistic practitioners who are the focus of the submission. This allowed me the academic space to analyse, alter my practice throughout the content gathering stage, and in turn reflect upon this. Based upon the creative journey I have undertaken I have become more critical of Mojo and this study provides evidence of some of the concerns and fears that were previously never recognised or acknowledged from me as a practitioner turned researcher. The equipment used throughout the fieldwork

included iPhone and iPod devices as part of mobile journalism (Mojo) kits. The video submission stands as the creative practice element of the study.

Some of the findings demonstrate a greater risk of alienation for media practitioners, the transformative but disruptive impact of mobile technology on reporters and the knock-on effects this has for journalistic identity. The study showed that while Mojo is proving a cost-effective approach to create, share and broadcast TV and digital news with fewer employees, it is exposing journalists to increased workloads while they become more isolated from newsrooms, under pressure to constantly upskill and reskill or be left behind, as broadcasting becomes more mobile technology dependent.

These findings contrast with previous views held by the researcher who no longer supports full Mojo implementation and the study provides guidance for news organisations and educators on how to adopt a more blended approach to newsgathering, one that is supportive and inclusive rather than letting technology dictate newsroom changes.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 The emergence of mobile journalism

Pavlik (2000) has suggested that technology has been one of the key drivers of change in newsrooms, ‘the way journalists work has always been influenced, constrained and structured by technology’ (p.229). As mobile smartphone use increased between 2007 and 2016 (Swearingen, 2018) the world of journalism also changed, in terms of newsgathering, production and distribution (Lichterman, 2017). Rima Marrouch details a number of important news stories where early smartphone technology was first utilised: the 2003 Iraq War, the Madrid and London bombings in 2004 and 2005 and reporting of the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami (Marrouch, 2014). Nokia and Reuters were early entrants to, and shapers of, mobile journalism as they pioneered the alignment of mobile phone technology and journalism output through a 2007 partnership (Karhunen, 2017).

Marrouch (2014) suggests that the emergence of YouTube and live streaming from 2012 onwards built on this initial shift and helped contribute to what is now commonly known as Mojo, short for mobile journalism. Established media academic Podger (2019) defines Mojo as a process where journalists work autonomously shooting, editing and writing their own multimedia content using mobile devices. For other media academics mobile journalism is not just defined by technological form but the mobility and freedom that the technology facilitates (Duffy, et al, 2020).

Throughout 2011 and 2012 leading French and US media organizations, including the *Wall Street Journal*, equipped many of their reporters with their first iPhone journalism kits (Becquet, 2015). Since this 2012 turning point, the advancement of Mojo has been documented by both industry and academic commentators alike (Sundet, 2012; Burum,

2014, Deuze, 2019; Bui and Moran 2020). This has only intensified and accelerated in more recent years. Swearingen (2018) suggests that society is at a pivotal point in mobile phone usage, with Deloitte Global predicting that 90% of the developed world's population will be users of smartphone technology by 2023 (Deloitte, 2017).

However, the changes evident in smartphone usage in recent years has also affected the media industry, positively and negatively. For example, as smartphone usage became more prevalent in newsgathering and content delivery from 2012 onwards, US newsroom employment declined by 23% (Grieco, 2018). The Pew Institute found that the only job growth occurred in the digital native sector with reporters, videographers, photographers and editors all affected negatively by the effects of technological change and associated adaptations to business practice.

The International Journalist's Network (IJN) has provided a platform for dialogue between academics and Mojo practitioners surrounding the implementation of mobile journalism in newsrooms and they highlighted the financial savings made by TV stations as a key driver for news organisations moving to Mojo (Hernandez, 2018). Earlier IJN research also pointed to the pioneering example of Swiss media outlet, Léman Bleu, who produced 80% of their news content using mobile devices in 2015 (Goujard, 2016).

However, the IJN explained that it was not just broadcast news outlets who were transitioning to Mojo from 2012 onwards, that similar trends were also evident in radio and print news outlets, including in India where the *Hindustan Times* had a Mojo first newsroom workflow implemented by Yusuf Omar (Goujard, 2016). Omar trained 750 English speaking mobile journalists throughout 2016 at *The Times* referring to Mojo as both fast and disruptive but what Indian media organisations needed to adopt (Khan, 2016).

As newsrooms adapt to the effects of a changing technological landscape, several benefits and some drawbacks have been apparent to news organizations, journalists and audiences. For news organizations, budget efficiencies and enhanced live broadcasting alternatives can be the outcomes of investment in Mojo. For example, cost savings in equipment and staffing was cited as a significant reason for Canadian broadcaster CBC and their Calgary news team switching to Mojo in 2016 (Albeanu, 2017). This practice was also evident in the US, where multimedia mobile journalists (MMJs) who shoot, edit, write and broadcast live content for TV and online are becoming the norm in top 50 broadcast markets (Perez and Cremadas 2014). As Perez and Cremadas suggest, 'it appears television managers have embraced MMJs in an attempt to keep their stations profitable during a time of fractured audiences and declining advertising dollars' (p.162).

For journalists, a similar picture emerges. In a 2016 report for staff training at international broadcaster Al Jazeera, the authors refer to the need for journalists who can 'cover almost any story in a timely and safe manner' (Maccise and Marai, 2016, p.1), enabled by mobile technology. The authors identified enhanced Wi-Fi, mobile data developments and versatile smartphone apps as all playing significant roles in the transition of their newsrooms to Mojo. More recent research paints a more positive picture of Mojo as transforming news workflows, affording 'journalists the ability to overcome time and space to reach their audiences' (Bui and Moran 2020, p.153).

However, there are also many critics of Mojo who argue that too much is expected of journalists in a digital media age, 'because the reporter is responsible for so many duties the quality of journalism suffers' (Perez & Cremedas, 2014, p.167). This was the view of 80% of multimedia reporters who responded to a survey conducted in 2014. Other critics of Mojo warn that the dilemma facing journalists is around up-skilling of staff to be competent and confident with emerging technologies, software and digital tools and warn

that caution is needed (Pereira-Farina et al, 2017). The number of journalists in the UK has been increasing since 2018, but only 30% now work in print or magazine outlets due to changing business models influenced by mobile journalism and the internet (Murphy, 2020, p. 3). Papacharissi (2013) et al predicted this trend almost half a decade earlier by highlighting that ‘content formulas and business models that worked as recently as yesterday may not work in a few months’ (p. 598). Deuze (2019) refers to this state that journalism finds itself in as a ‘quagmire’ and explains that the conditions in which journalists now work in are in constant flux (p. 2).

Media scholar Andre Monteiro also suggests that journalists must think ‘mobile first’ based on audience expectations (Knight Institute, 2017). Further 2017 research suggests that with the proliferation of smartphone journalism, audiences are keen to be ‘two-way consumers, participating in media actively’, (Mohammedsalih, 2017, p. 43). The same study points to the dilemma that this creates for media outlets who appreciate having a growing number of content consumers turned content creators, but fear this creates an amateur verses professional conflict which Mohammedsalih (2017) refers to as ‘controversial’ (p. 44). Nelson and Lei (2017) further support the view that audiences are influencing Mojo by stating that 72% of news consumers now go to mobile devices and partake in snacking or grazing of more bite-size mobile friendly news segments.

1.2 Mojo and global diffusion

The influence of mobile journalism differs significantly between developed world and developing world economic contexts and for this study, it is important to outline in what ways. For many, access to ICTs (Information communication technology) is seen as a basic human right in technologically advanced nations. However, large populations are deprived of access to high quality internet within some poorer countries, including

women and those living in rural areas in particular (Ling and Horst, 2011). While mobile phones have given many at ‘the bottom of the income pyramid’ in less developed countries new ways to communicate, Ling and Horst, (2011) argue that mobile technology is also used to control and influence poorer people (p. 364). For example, Jamil (2019) cites examples of fake news, disinformation and lack of verification in Ghana and Pakistani digital and broadcast journalism as worrying trends that have emerged with the increase of mobile infrastructure in both nations. Other academics suggest that developments within economically stable regions are seen as having ‘implications for the future of media’ (Wasserman 2014, p. 55) but some of these arguments surrounding print journalism and mobile technology are not as relevant to societies with restricted social media and internet access. Wasserman (2014) suggests that political influences on media organisations are far more important for countries outside Global North regions than that of social trends. Couldry (2019) reinforces this view by suggesting that smartphone and digital media access is helping connect and inform communities, but the vast majority of the technology firms and media organisations are still privately controlled. He cites Mexico as an example and explains that 13 families own 80% of the nation’s radio stations. He contrasts this with Sweden and other Global North nations where public service broadcasting is more prevalent. The influence of private media ownership in more economically deprived nations is also discussed in relation to Indian broadcasting and its impact on political decision-making, elections and nationalism by Udupa (2018). Concluding, Couldry (2019) argues that access to digital media, mobile journalism and ICT can contribute to social progress in developing world nations despite political influence and private ownership but explains that media infrastructure needs to be viewed as important as railways and roads in poorer, less stable countries. India is a relatively advanced Global South nation compared to others in Asia,

Africa and South America but overall, the differences between varying societies impacts how and where audiences can consume mobile journalism and also who influences and engages with digital content creation. Often citizens in less socio-economically advanced countries who are male, with an education and less financially restricted are the only social group who are able to become two-way media consumers (Paul, 2018). Dr Thembi Mutch quoted online after speaking at the 2019 Journalism Festival explained that journalist training is pivotal in helping shape media representation of Africa which in turn gives less developed nations more voices and news coverage from journalists that are not just 'pale, male and stale' (Allen, 2019).

Building on these key areas surrounding the rise of Mojo, its global influence and how it shapes cultural and societal trends informed the following research questions.

1.3 Research aim and objectives

The primary research aim is to explore the impact of smartphone technology on journalism practice between 2017 and 2019 in a number of newsrooms in different countries and continents.

The research sought to address the following four research questions:

1. What is the nature, extent and effect of mobile journalism on news content gathering across four international media outlets?
2. What are the similarities and differences within mobile journalism practice across four international media outlets?
3. What are the primary opportunities and threats posed by Mojo implementation?
4. What impact does Mojo have on journalistic identity?

This study addresses these questions through both the creative practice artefact, a discussion chapter that will draw upon the findings from each study site coupled with creative practice reflections and a comprehensive evaluation of relevant literature. During this study, the definition of what is a Mojo will primarily refer to the views of Podger (2019). Podger (2019) explains both the type and use of technology in her work surrounding Mojo and has authored one of the first mobile journalism handbooks. This differs from the views of Duffy (2020) who expands the Mojo definition to being one that incorporates the feelings of mobility that smartphones enable. Both academics place technological evolution to the fore in their defining of Mojo and Mojo practice and it can be discerned that technological determinism has in turn influenced newsroom decision making with smartphones having bridged a divide between previously passive audiences and more engaged citizen content producers.

1.4 Creative practice and thesis

As Mojo is a relatively recent development in the field of journalism, there is an opportunity to interrogate the practices that have emerged alongside the technologies, including the benefits and drawbacks of Mojo integration in newsrooms in different geographical settings. It also provided an opportunity to undertake a piece of practice-based research that would help address the research aim and objectives effectively, building on my own expertise as a practicing journalist. To that end, I adopted the dual role of videographer and researcher, drawing on ethnographic techniques including participant observation and interviewing to explore the themes and debates emerging from the academic and grey literatures pertaining to Mojo. In order to present these insights in a more nuanced way than in thesis form, I decided to also tell the story of Mojo practice in different parts of the world in the form of a creative artefact through

which the findings could be delivered in a compelling and engaging manner. This approach also built upon my practice-based background in the broadcast journalism sector while allowing me to interrogate my own views and experiences as a prior champion of Mojo.

The mobile video documentary helps present the research findings in a visual and accessible medium with the on-screen interviews guiding the key debates from the study. This practice-based research approach afforded me the opportunity to be embedded in the daily lives of the journalists within the four case study locations. Practice-based research is where ‘claims of contribution to knowledge may be demonstrated by creative outcomes’ (Candy, 2006, p.1). The reason for choosing practice-based over practice-led research stems from my background as one of the first wave of trained mobile journalists in the UK in 2011 and 2012 and the desire to produce what Candy (2006) refers to as an ‘artefact’ along with a complementary written thesis.

1.5 Research Contribution

This study contributes to new understandings within journalism practice, media research and journalism education. Through examining and presenting insights into the opportunities and threats posed by Mojo implementation, this study aimed to better equip and support journalists and news organizations to make ethical and balanced decisions when upskilling and transitioning their reporters and content output. Building on previous waves of ethnographic research into newsroom dynamics, this study demonstrated how and why technological, economic and social factors now influence media organisation decision-making. The expert interviews within this study contribute insights that demonstrate how these transitions in turn affect journalistic identity in the digital age.

Finally, by adopting established practice-based methodological approaches but utilising them to create a mobile journalistic output, this study contributed to knowledge and understanding in the emerging area of mobile research and mobile journalism pedagogy.

1.6 Thesis structure

This thesis comprises a comprehensive literature review (Chapter 2) exploring key debates within the mobile journalism landscape including the influence of smartphone technology on journalistic identity, alienation, privacy concerns for journalists and the platformisation of journalism. Following this, the methodology chapter (Chapter 3) outlines the approaches taken in both the written and creative output of this practice-based study and gives context to the case study selection.

Drawing on the literature, case study interviews and participant observation, the findings chapter (Chapter 4) presents insights from each case study thematically. These findings are then discussed in the analysis chapter (Chapter 5), in relation to the research questions before reflections on the creative practice journey are presented in Chapter 6. The thesis is then concluded in Chapter 7.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Prior to and during this study newsrooms have been experiencing significant change, including the ‘breaking down of barriers between traditional media industries and the telecommunications sector... redefining the way music, film, radio, television, newspapers and books are produced, manufactured, distributed and consumed’ (Burnett and Marshall, 2003, p.1). Murphy (2020, p. 3) describes the last 20 years as ‘extremely turbulent’ for newsrooms, influenced by both the 2008 economic crash and the growth of the internet. A body of research has been generated in recent years in the area of mobile journalism with publications analysing newsroom evolution, drawing on case studies primarily in the US with other significant work published in India, Scandinavia, Holland, the UK and Australia.

This literature review examines studies that have concentrated on the role played by smartphone technology and mobile journalism in the operation of global newsrooms and their effects. The review addresses the study’s research aim and questions while investigating the key debates taking place within the journalism field, including the dilution of news quality through Mojo, the effects of the convergence of consumers and producers, and the platformisation of society. Papacharissi et al, (2013, p. 598) argue that these transformations characterise an ‘era and not just a single generation’.

Decades of technological advance have influenced the operation of newsrooms across the world (Reuters, 2017; Deuze, 2019), starting with the printing press, typewriters, radio and TV, evolving through satellite feeds and culminating with social media reporting and

live streaming. These technological developments have allowed ‘organised gossip’ to influence societies across the globe, affect elections and change the course of history, (Journalism, Fake News and Disinformation, UNESCO, 2018, p.10). However, post-Leveson Britain, Fake News and Wikileaks have left journalism at a crossroads. As Otufodunrin (2017) suggests, when writing in the website version of the Nigerian newspaper, *The Nation*:

Instead of living in denial about our precarious circumstance or dismissing the threat of the new media, there is an urgent need by all to take our destiny in our hands, especially for those of us who don’t know any other thing to do, than journalism (Otufodunrin, 2017).

In structuring this literature review, it is important to understand how journalism has evolved in the digital era and the effect of mobile smartphone technology on journalism practice and identity. Addressing these questions forms the basis of this literature review, which focuses on the emergence of Mojo, altering journalistic roles due to Mojo influence, the platformisation of journalism in the digital age, privacy concerns that arise from Mojo adoption and finally the increased risk of alienation that has become more prevalent as newsrooms have to alter workflows and dynamics.

2.2 The emergence of the mobile journalist

Deuze (2005), when considering what journalism is, and what is expected of it, refers to Russo (1998) and argues that journalists see themselves as part of a profession with a clear ideology rather than simply individual content creators or employees of a publication or broadcasting group. According to Kovach and Rosenstiel (2001), the journalist's occupational ideology has five characteristics or values: immediacy, objectivity, autonomy, public service and ethics. Deuze analyses each of these values in relation to expectations of journalists in the 21st century.

Deuze begins with public service, stating that the public 'vote with their wallets' requiring journalists to hold the powerful to account (Deuze, 2005, p.447). However, Abramson (2020) explains that during the pivotal early years of Mojo adoption, which coincided with the Obama administration from 2009-2017, there have been less opportunities for journalists to hold the powerful to account due to fewer whistle-blowers and data leaks. Abramson cites four organisations who continued to question authority figures and ruling bodies during this digitalisation and Mojo shift in journalism despite facing opposition - BuzzFeed, the *New York Times*, Vice and the *Washington Post* (Abramson, p.10).

Buzzfeed and Vice are primarily new media organisations. Mitchell and Hamm (2014) also argue that journalism in the age of the smartphone has become about bite-size information or 'bits' and feel that with the dilution of multimedia content, journalists must offer something 'less common and less cheap' (p.79). More recently, Perrault and Stanfield (2018) have supported the view that mobile technology is one of the key drivers in creating what they believe is a revolution in content distribution and consumption, with a significant quantity of news produced without charge for social media audiences, often through mobile phones. Harlow and Chadha (2019) highlight that journalism faces

growing identity concerns due to the digitalisation of media, explaining that news organisations are being caught between providing a commodity and a public service. This dilemma faced by both traditional and new media organisations has been exacerbated during the period of this study as mobile technology continued to evolve.

Deuze (2005) also highlights the challenges in achieving objectivity in journalism, with Ryan (2001) suggesting that although it is unattainable it must still be strived for. These views are supported by Durham (1998) when referring to *New York Times* coverage of the crash of TWA Flight 800. He states that journalists use 'objectivity to make sense of the world' but in the case of news coverage 'precision and control could not define the story' (p.107). Sjovaag (2011) refers to how media outlets often follow and support the dominant ideology in societies. She mentions Gitlin's (1980) book *The Whole World Is Watching* in which he explains 'in the sixties, the value of objectivity gets questioned, but it always returns as if by default' (Sjovaag, 2011, p. 268). Gitlin also outlines how 'normally in the course of newsgathering, reporters tend to get pulled into the cognitive world of their sources' (Gitlin, 1980, p. 270). The removal of Mojos from newsroom environments and the expectation of most to work alone exposes them to situations where objectivity can be hard to achieve and the risk of being influenced by sources and interviewees is greater. These concerns are reiterated during the practice output of this study by the experienced assignment manager and editors at the US news outlet, who fear too much focus is being put on technology and not enough on traditional journalistic principles and values.

The digitalisation of journalism has presented both challenges and opportunities in relation to objectivity. For example, Dickinson and Bigi (2009) contend that the role of a journalist is evolutionary. They argue that prior to the prominence of social media and

mobile journalism a ‘trend is being hastened by the introduction of new production technologies’ (p. 509). During their research in 2009 they also analysed the roles of a number of Swiss video journalists (MMJs), who solo shoot, edit, write and produce news content and highlighted that research opportunities are diminished due to newsgathering demands, ‘you are busy shooting – and you’re alone’ (Dickinson and Bigi, 2009, p. 520). Fast forward a decade and social media and live streaming expectations are now added to these multimedia journalist’s workload due to the replacement of video cameras with smartphones (Goggin, 2020). Later work from Deuze (2019) highlights the precariousness of this new emerging journalistic identity, one where reporters are overworked, fearful of job loss and disconnected from each other.

However, Murphy (2020) explains that the digitalisation of journalism leaves reporters better trained, ‘Video, audio, graphics and other creative skills are now required too as standard for journalists’ (p. 6), but with all these expectations there is less time and space to research stories which impacts negatively on objectivity. Journalists are granted less opportunity to verify sources, review, and balance their content as the push to go live and get news out is enabled by having live broadcasting technology in the palm of a reporter’s hand.

Deuze (2005) relates autonomy to censorship citing Weaver’s (1998) view that ‘Journalists are not merely the lackeys of their editors’ (p. 448). However, Dickinson and Bigi (2009) believe this same autonomy for reporters working on their own, gathering and producing news content, leads to workplace alienation and caution that this can also lead to ‘psychological strain’ (p. 520). Rottwilm (2014) has also explored whether autonomy and the ability to self-censor are lacking when freelance journalists do not have a newsroom structure, compared to full time staff journalists. He concludes that journalism

as an ideology shapes both sets of workers regardless, whereby ‘the former are more independent and the latter are more restricted than often assumed’ (Rottwilm, 2014, p.10).

The challenge for journalists to uphold the core values of journalism proposed by Deuze is exacerbated by the trend towards the digitalisation of news media, aided primarily through smartphone adoption (Karhunen, 2017). This can lead to increased demands being placed upon journalists, alienation from newsrooms and challenges around objectivity and self-censorship. Journalists may have a greater range of technical skills, but some fundamental aspects of their professional practice are being challenged and with it their identity. Salzmann, et al (2020) refer to the solidifying of mobile journalism practice between 2017 and 2019 as a ‘jungle of innovation’ and one that is dictated by technological advancements (p.12).

Immediacy as a value of journalism has now become more important than ever before. It ‘lends the work of journalists an aura of instantaneity and immediatism’ (Deuze, 2005, p. 22). A growing desire for breaking news is a feature of multimedia and digital newsrooms. Groot and Meijer (2014, p. 634), drawing on an American TV case study, explain that ‘In 2012 the news organisation introduced a policy of internet first; each item is made available online immediately’. They further detail the crucial steps some Oregon news agencies made in catering to a smartphone audience over that of a traditional print or broadcast approach. Flew (2019) cites a Reuters study that examines demand for social media news between 2012 and 2017, which showed that more than half of all Americans reach for their smartphones instead of waiting for an evening TV bulletin. Moreover, research from Heckman and Wihbey (2019) claim that a desire for access and immediacy in news has led to mobile news consumers making it ‘part of their daily routines’ (p. 318). This transition to digital media enhances immediacy for the consumer but also has some

potentially negative consequences for journalists. Rottwilm (2014, p. 16) refers to this evolution as ‘always on deadline’ journalism and cautions against excessive dictation and incessant audience demands. Heckman and Wihbey (2019) explain that these expectations can put newsrooms under pressure to switch to mobile journalism and upskill staff quickly. Here, they refer to Rogers (2003) and his five-stage diffusion of innovations theory, ‘innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards’ (Heckman and Wihbey, 2019, p. 319). While innovators and early adopters switch to mobile and digital news production and distribution pathways which in turn aid immediacy, others can feel left behind in what Goggin (2020) explains is a 21st century digital media society where breaking news alerts to mobile smartphones has become ‘pervasive, ambient aspects of everyday’ (p. 170).

Deuze (2005) argues that The Code of Bordeaux adopted in 1956 by the international federation of journalists was a turning point for ethical decision making in journalism. He refers to journalists as ‘watchdogs of the state’ and that a ‘sense of being ethical’ (p. 447) is crucial. Some scholars believe these ideas are dated. In a time of data sharing, hacking, coding and internet surveillance, what is expected ethically of journalists is being questioned more and more (Babcock and Freivogel 2015). Sjovaag (2011, p. 22) suggests that professional journalism can be ‘achieved and retained by securing a monopoly on expertise’. This can present ethical dilemmas for the overworked and alienated Mojo. Sjovaag (2011, p. 22) refers to ‘ethical cleansing’ where journalists have to self-police, she quotes Norwegian scholar Odd Raaum who argues that journalists have to self-govern and punish their own for acting unethically in order for journalism to maintain and protect its own integrity (Sjovaag, 2011). However, a growing number of ethical challenges are being presented to journalists who are not only dealing with increasing production workloads but are expected to verify and check sources that could be malinformation,

disinformation and misinformation presented via social media or User Generated Content/UGC (Shu, et al, 2020). Ferreira (2021) differentiates between malinformation and disinformation by explaining that the latter is often the leaking of facts with malicious intent and cites hate speech and hacks as examples. Ferreira (2021) describes misinformation as inaccurate data shared to audiences without the intent to harm while disinformation is false information. Ferreira (2021) refers to disinformation and malinformation as more aligned to the term 'Fake News' which he believes was coined to undermine journalistic integrity.

Shu (2020) also outlines the difficulties that journalists face when analysing multimedia content produced by bots. With journalists operating alone and away from newsrooms and facing new ethical dilemmas, the expectation to self-police grows as the number of colleagues diminishes. This can lead to unverified or illegal content being distributed to a larger audience and discredit both the journalist, their employer and their industry.

Alongside Deuze's (2005) five key values, Peters (2012) argues that journalism in the 21st century is also about space. He explains that modern journalism is about 'understanding where and through what medium audiences consume news' (p. 698). For Peters (2012), the ability to practice journalism in the 21st century matters on three levels: ontologically, epistemologically and phenomenologically. He challenges media professionals to first ask how they view themselves as citizens, how they learn about newsworthy issues and how they view news.

Some academics advance the argument that 'Newspapers dig up the news...others repackage it' (Mitchell & Hamm, 2014, p. 80). The debate surrounding form and distribution is further explored by Westlund (2015) who believes that patterns, people, place and participation are also some of the main driving factors in digitalisation and the

transition to mobile journalism. He argues that patterns of mobile news consumption are key, mentioning a Japanese study by Kitamura (2013) which shows that mobile journalism is complementary to legacy news media. Goggin (2020, p. 2) quotes Nelson's (2020) when explaining that a 'mobile platform is a continuation of what came before'. Other research highlighted by Westlund (2015, p.153) evaluates studies conducted in Portugal by Damásio, Henriques, Teixeira-Botelho, & Dias (2013) which refers to how mobile media consumption remains lower than 'online news in general'. Scandinavian media academics contest the notion that traditional media can remain unaffected by mobile news consumption as demand for journalistic content increases, they cite the examples of some US audiences who turn to their phones during the workday but TV and newspapers when at home (Jensen et al, 2014). These studies were published during the earlier part of the Mojo rise and their findings contrast significantly with more recent research from Flew (2019) and Fortunati and O'Sullivan (2020). The former explains that mobile and social media consumption is now in the majority and traditional media is significantly affected. Fortunati and O'Sullivan (2020) take this view a step further by arguing that:

The mobile has opened a perpetual access to news, extending beyond temporal and spatial boundaries in everyday life. It can do this because the space where it is situated is the human body, in all places and at all times, whether on the move or in sedentary settings (p.166).

It can be claimed that the core principles of journalism are being influenced by emerging mobile and digital trends. These developments are both technologically led but also swayed by audience demands. Vos and Hanitzsch (2017) refer to journalistic identity as a belief system within which journalists aspire to roles they often struggle to carry out.

With a growing number of factors at play in the journalistic vocation due to mobile and digital media advancements, what a journalist is and does is altering. The five values of immediacy, objectivity, autonomy, public service and ethics are each being changed and questioned as mobile and digital technology replace journalists and more traditional workflows. This shift, in such a short time from 2012 onwards, has impacted on journalists and changed the dynamic between previously passive media consumers and broadcasters, which will be discussed further in the next section.

2.3 Journalism in the digital age: altering roles and identities

CNN Pentagon correspondent, Jamie McIntyre, who described the transition from using 12-person crews during the first Iraq War in 1991 to using a MacBook Pro and a satellite internet transmitter to do the same job in 2008, suggested that ‘when you’re a TV reporter and you’re doing everything yourself; it changes the way you tell a story’ (Blankenship, 2016, p. 3). One of these transformations is the more prominent role played by audiences who now have the same equipment in the palm of their hand as professional broadcasters (Hadland, 2017). However, while there is a range of opportunities for audiences and broadcasters to work together in story creation and distribution these same pathways can lead to new challenges that undermine previous workflows, journalistic identity and traditional media roles.

2.3.1 Content consumers: an engaged audience

Audiences are no longer tied to TV and radio bulletins or newspaper print rounds but engage and consume content around the clock through online publications, apps, live streaming and social media. However, Chan-Olmsted, Rim, and Zerba (2012) query why younger audiences are turning away from more traditional media like newspapers, radio

and television and conclude that the main factors influencing this trend were relative content advantage, relative technology advantage and relative cost advantage. News content is related to space (Peters, 2012), but here in a slightly different context.

Chan-Olmsted et al (2012) present digital journalism as infinite, not limited to a broadcast minute cap or column inch restriction. Therefore, the space afforded to storytelling is greater and access is easier for younger more technologically comfortable audiences, 'Since mobile news is often the mobile version of online news, the perceived advantage of unlimited content might also be present for this news platform (Chan-Olmsted et al, 2012, p. 129). Chan-Olmsted et al view mobile and online technology as major contributors to how audiences access news. They refer to audiences being able to view a wider range of multimedia content including, 'archived material, forums, links and streams' (p. 129) in the palm of their hands. This point is echoed by Drula (2014), who refers to a Google study where one third of mobile phone users admitted to happily giving up TV, in order to keep their mobile device. In India, NDTV has created the world's first vertical 'always on', live streaming video news service offering a TV alternative via social media platforms for a younger audience, watched primarily on mobile devices called Hop Live (Sinha, 2018). The service, similar to a constant Instagram Live feed has feature and news segments and is shot throughout India by Mojo crews. Schröder (2014) suggests that platforms play a key role in both presenting the news genre but also in enhancing the audience experience, further discussion on platformisation will be addressed in the forthcoming sections.

When referring to costs, Chan-Olmsted et al (2012) identify both financial and time consumption issues associated with the digitalization of journalism. They suggest that

access to extensive video content for audiences through digital platforms with no charge is a major influencer in how technology affects media. The impact audiences have as content consumers when dictating news-cycles is significant, especially the importance of ‘clicks, comments and shares’ (Tandoc et al, 2014, p. 439). Prior to the emergence of internet and mobile technology into the media space, audience feedback was often dismissed as editors could choose what letters of complaint were published or not. Fuchs (2014), drawing on a critical theory lens, believes economics as well as opportunity is a key factor influencing engagement with information and communication technologies. He argues that ‘people with high income, far-reaching and influential social relationships, good education and high skills are much more likely to have access to ICTs’ (p.16). These content consumers can also pick and choose from a wide range of free mobile-based news material that Heckman and Wihbey (2019) suggest can leave some media corporations with fewer ‘monetization opportunities’ (p. 325). The Reuters Institute report *A Decade of Dependency* explored some of these ICTs and demonstrated how significant audience shifts from 2008 to 2018 have been led by the evolution of smartphone technology, enhanced 4G, internet infrastructure and the rise of social media. These same key factors have also influenced the primary creators of news content, journalists.

2.3.2 Content creators: mojo enabled

Journalists, as creators of content, are significantly impacted by digital and mobile trends (Drula, 2014). Drula explains how smartphone developments have put journalists at the forefront of modern journalism:

Mobile technologies are used as media tools both for consumption and production of news. The mobile environment permits easy and accurate identification of the audience, Web traffic, and the tracking of content usage (p. 50)

Drula refers to convergence and how the instrument used to consume is now also that of creation, impacting on journalism practice. Similarly, Bivens (2008) explains that audiences are also becoming content creators due to having access to similar hardware with good cameras on mobile devices, ‘on some occasions, the flood of UGC linked to a breaking news item has actually reversed the traditional flow of news’ (p. 117).

Technology impacting on journalistic practices is significantly influential in less developed nations as part of mobile laden eco-systems where rural communities can now create their own mobile journalism and access broadcasters they were unable to previously (Jamil, 2019). In South American research, Pereira et al (2013) discuss how the reconfiguration of news processes and technological convergence have altered professional journalistic identities in Brazilian newsrooms. The influence of evolving mobile technology on the media landscape also has its critics. Rottwilm (2014) expresses a concern that mobile audiences will demand too much from mobile journalists whereby:

This new social form of journalism is increasing both the amount and pace of information input, as well as the output of journalistic work, arguably leading to cognitive overload, with journalists less able to filter and analyse their sources and detect and remove biases (p. 16).

Rottwilm (2014) also warns that this always-on deadline journalism which is presented through social media reporting using mobile technology makes it more physically and mentally challenging for reporters who are now more aware of their own competition. He further contends that the convergence of jobs as a photographer, editor, and reporter puts more pressure on journalists to be multi-skilled. Hanitzsch and Vos (2017) discuss how role expectations within journalism are a combination of informal rules, customs and procedures. Deuze (2019) explains that this combination disadvantages young digital and

mobile journalists, as previous workflows which supported them to understand who they are and what they do through occupational socialisation are now ‘crumbling’ and young reporters ‘rarely see a newsroom on the inside’ (p. 3).

Adornato (2018) describes the emergence of multi-skilled mobile journalism as an evolution. Drawing on research from the Knight Foundation and the Pew Research Centre he suggests that news is both mobile and social due to technological influences. He explains that since the unveiling of the iPhone in 2007 and Twitter in 2006 ‘never before in such a short amount of time has new technology had such a dramatic influence on so many facets of communications’ (Adornato, 2018, p. 3). Rottwilm (2014) agrees that smartphone technology is influential but sees mobile journalism as well as the producer-consumer relationship as a challenge. This producer-consumer merger is primarily evidenced in user generated content and the rise of citizen journalism. Hadland (2017, p. 21) refers to how audience created mobile content is often utilized by TV stations to cover ‘crime, violence and conflict’. His research showed that while amateur mobile video reportage was also used to cover some weather stories, it was in international reporting where broadcasters relied heaviest on UGC (Hadland, 2017). This shifting dynamic and Mojo enabled relationship between consumer and producer has created some challenges as well as bringing audiences closer to, and often part of, the story.

2.3.3 The convergence between content creators and content consumers

With smartphone and internet technology enabling consumers to also be content producers, Thurman (2008) evaluates the role that social media plays in the dynamic between journalists and their audiences. He suggests that the initial digital relationship between media consumers and creators has been influenced through emails and social media. He uses the example of audience interaction at the BBC during the beginning of

the 21st century arguing that ‘The speed and volume of correspondence from their growing and increasingly vocal audience meant that the BBC found it impossible to read the 10,000 or more emails they received on a weekly basis’ (Thurman, 2008, p. 147). This early two-way communication between consumers of content and creators of content is now embraced by most digitally focused news organisations via social media platforms and in some cases has further positive knock-on effects. Later work from Thurman (2018) suggests that consumers who are also producers of journalism are better able to migrate and find personalised news content. These are often younger news consumers who are smartphone savvy, but older audiences are excluded leading to a divide ‘leaving behind the less adaptable’ (Thurman 2018, p. 29). However, Holt and Karlsson (2013) suggest that social media interaction between journalists and consumers also has a constructive impact on political participation and therefore can have a more significant role in society. Thurman (2008) cites examples of celebrity deaths as allowing media consumers a platform to voice their feelings and be included in the news process. The *Scotsman* editor cited in Thurman’s article is critical, however, arguing that the great problem with any kind of public involvement is that you have to moderate it and that is very resource-heavy (Thurman, 2008). The consumer-producer role has become more accepted during the Mojo emergence despite the challenges that it creates (Lin and Zhao, 2018). These new digital media consumers who also produce industry-standard content tend to use readily available cost-effective equipment such as mobile smartphones. Paul (2018) discussing examples of these producer-consumers in relation to case studies in Indian media suggests that only those who are well educated, living in urban areas and financially stable can fulfil these roles (Paul, 2018). Erdal et al (2019), when referring to *The Times of India* digital audience, explains that it is these engaged mobile news consumers who are shaping and shifting how news is now produced and presented and refers to the media

outlet as transitioning to video reporting utilising ‘silent mode’ for commuters (p. 172).

This supports the arguments put forward by Fuchs (2014) that there is a social divide when it comes to mobile media consumption and creation, which is more apparent in less developed economies, where those who commute for work and are employed in urban areas are more actively able to contribute and influence media organisations in the mobile age, compared to those who are poorer, living in rural areas and have restricted mobile infrastructure.

While Thurman (2008; 2018) outlines both sides of the argument for the influence of technology on news, Rottwilm (2014) is critical of its role. Chan-Olmsted et al, along with Drula, demonstrate that the needs of audiences are influenced by technological evolution and with that, journalists must move with these trends. Adornato (2018) supports this transition to a media world where multiskilling and technological tools are commonplace. Murphy (2020) adds that a caveat to this multiskilling is a lack of diversity within digital and mobile journalism primarily ‘an occupation chiefly of young, white people from relatively prosperous backgrounds’ (p. 4). This divide created by mobile journalism impacts on content creators, consumers and producers, especially those who are older and poorer leading to marginalization in some Global South societies (Wasserman, 2014; Paul, 2018; Fuchs, 2014).

Spyridou et al (2013) also highlights what happens when news organisations fail to keep up with these digital and mobile trends. In her research on Greek media outlets, she found that both audiences and journalists were alienated from each other. She suggests that Greek broadcasters were slow to respond to this new ‘digital era’ (p. 83) and by doing so isolated their audiences. She points to the debt crisis post-2008 and how socio-political blogs, news websites, UGC and Web 2.0 provided younger audiences with news output

that traditional media had overlooked. Her research also concludes that a lack of technological upskilling within traditional Greek news media was a concern, in that it left these newsrooms behind ICT trends and audience expectations.

Many in the academy both support the influence of technology in media but also warn of its pitfalls (Borchart, 2018). While these scholars and academics demonstrate contrasting views, there is evidence that, fundamentally, the influence of technology and changing audience demands are increasingly defining what newsrooms feel they need to adapt to. Papacharissi et al (2013, p. 604) refers to this as not a point in time where everything changes but instead as a period of ‘constant...ongoing habits’. Without an audience, newsrooms cannot exist whether they are made up of multi-skilled mobile journalists or not. Ease of access will remain paramount for audiences whether it be due to device, cost, platform or medium.

2.4 The mobile journalist and digital disruption

The five journalism values discussed by Deuze and the media space arguments presented by Peters are all affected by the emergence and implementation of mobile journalism. Heckman and Wihbey (2019) refer to this period in newsroom evolution as ‘disruptive’ (p. 236) due to job loss, roles changing and more live broadcasting expectations. More recent research from Deuze reiterates these views and describes journalism as precarious with newsrooms now left ‘full of empty chairs’ (Deuze, 2019, p. 1).

Westlund (2005) suggests that Global North news consumers who are in relationships and employed are more likely to access mobile news and be active players in the mobile and digital journalism emergence. The first part of the literature review explored the changes to journalistic identity due to digital and mobile technology, suggesting that the normality

of using a touchscreen device in public has contributed to greater mobile journalism news content being produced. Chinese academics refer to this as finger-reading (Xu, 2016). In previous work, Westlund (2013) suggests that phones and multimedia have converged since the early 1990s and that subsequently there has been ‘uninterrupted change’ (p. 6). His extensive body of research also questions why this convergence occurred, identifying a number of drivers. He highlights that age, gender and educational level all contribute to how an audience accesses news and therefore influences how journalists create it. For example, he suggests that ‘Swedish research has shown that educated men aged 15-49 are far more inclined to consume mobile phone news frequently than others’ (p. 153). Westlund’s views surrounding place, patterns, people and participation are also alluded to by Indian scholars Kumar and Haneef (2017) who discuss what Indians believe is journalism in the 21st century and suggest that the country is not experiencing a ‘declining print industry’ (p. 1) but is instead seeing it rise along with the digital demands of audiences of all ages. In neighbouring Pakistan, research from Jamil (2019) has shown that the increase in media consumption, creation and engagement fuelled by smartphone adoption in some Global South societies has also provided pathways for unverified citizen journalism with images and video gaining national coverage due to a lack of gatekeepers (p. 56).

Westlund (2015) suggests the medium to access news, which includes mobile devices, is shaping its fate. In contrast, Kumar and Haneef (2017) feel that it leans more towards societal patterns of behaviour. These same emerging and disruptive trends amongst audiences are bringing India rapidly into the digital news sphere. This supports Peter’s (2012) views about space, that audiences focus on the medium and environment in which news comes to them, whether that is via tablet, TV, print or in the palm of their hand.

Multimedia and mobile social media material is being produced by both multimedia journalists and what Bruns (2008) terms producers, these are engaged audiences who reshare, create or augment content rather than just passively consume it. Bird (2011) suggests that since the emergence of Web 2.0 all audiences have the potential to be producers, and younger generations are more active contributors in this active and participatory media cycle (Guerrero-Pico, et al, 2019). However, this new approach creates challenges surrounding workflow dynamics for newsrooms, including concerns about biased and ethical contributions from audiences. For Spyridou et al (2013), the emergence of digital journalism and what journalism will become in the 21st century is driven by technological drivers of change. The proactive, and in some cases, disruptive role smartphones are playing within broadcast newsrooms has created debate and discourse within both the academic and industrial spheres and draws upon some of the key concepts surrounding technological determinism.

Post and Crone contest that there is no firm definition of technological determinism (Post and Crone, 2015, p. 873) but drawing on the work of Bjiker (2010) suggest that technology develops independently, but has both social and economic impacts. The influence technology has had in the media space is significant both for journalists and especially for younger audiences, with social media influential in shaping political and societal changes. This has become apparent in developing world nations, with younger populations in a position to utilise technology to become educated and enlightened. Post and Crone (2015) referred to how smartphone and internet usage empowered young Syrians and Egyptians to protest and speak out for their human rights, which in turn influenced the news media narrative and agenda within those regions and for international media outlets. Green (2002) suggests that technological influence within society is often presented as individual moments of understanding or progress (Green, 2002, p. 2) but

believes time and culture play a prominent role in how technological change alters society. Post and Crone (2015) refer to this when comparing how younger marginalised user generated content creators in conflict zones, utilised technology in innovative ways to amplify messages to international audiences and therefore bypass traditional or government-controlled media which their older or less tech savvy oppressors may not understand. Green (2002) refers to the work of MacKenzie and Wajcman (1999) when explaining that technology is only neutral if people don't know how to use it or don't know it exists, therefore reinforcing the arguments of Post and Crone (2015), whereby once smartphone and social media tools are discovered by engaged or often younger audiences, the technology is no longer neutral and becomes 'implicated in social processes' (Green, 2002, p. 5). However Green (2002) contests that the influence technology can have, is in turn impacted by which groups within societies can access or use the technology which demonstrates that both arguments by Westlund (2015) and Kumar and Haneef (2017) are interlinked and it is not just medium or human behaviour which can bring about change but both together if smartphone technology is available. When discussing access to technology, Green (2002) refers to three main drivers, the armed forces, bureaucracy, commercial power (Green, 2002, p. 9). She believes that technology can not only be created by the elite but also controlled and limited to them, this in turn marginalises who can create, consume and partake in technology and in the case of this study, the media and news cycle. Further to this, the success of technology often benefits those already in the ascendancy (Green, 2002, p. 10) and marginalises poorer communities as well as being exploited for political gain (Green, 2002, p. 11).

Therefore it can be attested that the transition to digital-mediated forms of journalism is influenced by a combination of technology, society, governments, corporations, audience needs and emerging trends. All of these contributing factors are in turn impacted by what

Fuchs (2008) terms the digital divide. He argues that the division between the audience who have internet access and those who do not significantly impacts on news consumption. He also refers to how even when internet access is provided in a society to those without education, they often use it to play games instead of using this same technology to receive new important information which frequently comes from media outlets. This trusting of technology without question is explored by Sage (et al 2011) drawing on the Actor-Theory Network and the work of Latour (1987), wherein the inner workings of smartphones are not queried and ‘we need to know nothing but its input and out’ (Latour, 1987, p. 3). Sage (et al, 2011) describes how technology in turn aligns and later defines social constructs and norms similar to newsroom workflows being altered in Mojo and explains how these new expectations then reaffirm support for the technology and therefore leave it unquestioned, Sage, et al, 2011, p. 348)

More recent work from Fuchs (2020) suggests that the technological acceleration that both Global North and Global South societies are experiencing, which includes faster internet, is also contributing to changing perceptions of ‘time and space’ (p. 257). This wider argument that smartphones are accelerating, altering and disrupting our societies is impacting on the journalism we create and consume. Other academics suggest that these same internet and smartphone technologies are replacing previous social trends, and in turn, a journalist’s role as messenger may become less impactful, ‘it used to be when you communicated with someone, the person you are communicating with was as important as the information they provided but now with the internet the person isn’t important’ explains Dr Lawrence Krauss from Arizona State University interviewed in the Werner Herzog documentary *Lo and Behold, Reveries of the Connected World* (Herzog, 2016). In conclusion, smartphone technology is proving a disruptive influence led by technological evolution, audience demands and societal trends that in turn are pushing journalists to

alter their workflows, their jobs and approach to storytelling with some significant negative ramifications including increased workloads and the altering of journalistic identity.

2.5 Platformisation and mobile journalism

‘Technology is transforming the way journalists work’ (Lees, April 17th, 2017: European Journalism Observatory, blog post,)

Xu (2016, p. 227) argues that mobile journalism is not ‘a gear change but a game change’ in the evolution of the mobile impacted society, listing mobile banking, mobile health, mobile gaming, mobile learning and mobile shopping as all encouraging the shift to consuming mobile news. Other academics believe mobile technology companies have dictated the direction and influence mobile journalism has and is having due to capitalizing on the economic crash of 2008, the rise of the internet, the lack of trust in mainstream media and emerging audience demands (Wu et al, 2019). Aradau, Blanke and Greenway (2019) describe these drivers as leading to economic and infrastructural acceptance and subsequent dominance of platforms within the digital media space. The shifts within digital content consumption from laptops and desktop audiences to smartphone users have in turn altered newsroom workflows leading to faster turnaround of stories and media consumers who are comfortable with ‘brevity’ and ‘disposal’ of ‘fast’ journalism (Salet, 2021, p. 8).

There are shifts not just, in where and how audiences consume news content, but also in the technological choice of the content creators. In some cases, there are no longer human journalists. Heliograf is the *Washington Post’s* journalism bot that writes and creates news content. It published 850 news, sport and politics stories entirely autonomously in

2017 (Schmelzer, 2018). Schmelzer adds that augmented intelligence is also creating weather reports, sports summaries and financial news updates in newsrooms. The *New York Times*, the BBC and Associated Press have also created their own augmented intelligence software. These include NewsWhip, Juicer and Editor. The AI works alongside journalists to enhance searching of key phrases, monitoring what audiences engage with and provide source and fact checking for stories (Schmelzer, 2018). A study from Nelson (2020) has also shown the key role SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) specialists at BuzzFeed and the *New York Times* play in driving certain news content to mobile platforms using algorithms and A/B testing. This trend demonstrates that the job of a journalist is becoming more technology led and influenced.

Fuchs (2010) argues that the content consumed by audiences whether produced by AI, journalists or producers is in turn reproduced and redistributed by a digital consumer audience:

The difference between the audience commodity on traditional mass media and on the internet is that in the latter case the users are also content producers; the fact that the users are more active on the internet than in the reception of television or radio content is due to the decentralized structure of the internet (p. 192).

The decentralisation of the internet and rise of smartphone use has in turn provided opportunity for the platformisation of journalism. Bell and Owen (2017) warn that news organisations continue to push their content to other platforms including Snapchat, Facebook and Twitter without any guarantee of a return. They further argue that the role these platforms play in news distribution is more significant a shift than the move from print to digital. Flew (2019) agrees and believes there was a turning point between the 2000s and 2010s due to app innovation, where social media took precedence over search

engines. Flew cautions against the platformisation of journalism believing it leads to monopolies by technology corporations over mass media distribution. While Murphy (2020, p. 6) refers to Facebook and Google as the ‘world’s lead media companies’, Whitaker (2019) explains that there is a ‘big five’, Google, Amazon, Apple, Facebook and Microsoft, who are the main drivers in changing the media landscape. He further details how of these ‘big five’, YouTube (Google owned) and Facebook are now ‘responsible for more media consumption than any other group’ (Whittaker, 2019, p. 8). Fuchs (2020) cites three of the ‘big five’, Google, Facebook and Apple as receiving only minor punishments for tax evasion and misuse of personal data. This monopoly and control of digital media by technology corporations is influencing how and where audiences get news. Nelson (2020) research has shown that algorithms, harnessing data from smartphones push established headlines out and leave content from other media organisations ‘doomed to obscurity’ (p. 90). Goggin (2020, p. 172) also cites Nelson (2020) who fears this platform monopoly within digital journalism leaves us with a society facing growing ‘inequality’.

Fuchs (2014) believes that this move to maximise digital audiences through mobile platforms is often used for financial gain. He feels these same content consumers, producers, and reproducers create advertising revenues for major media and technology corporations, who are in turn targeted by tailor made mobile media content, creating a cycle where content is created, (in bulk) if AI is involved, distributed to audiences, who then form part of the content distribution chain and share the media across their own mobile and social platforms, and by doing so generate income for technology organisations, who then reuse their consumer’s social media platforms and data and retarget them in a platformised media society. Fuchs (2014) cites Marx when cautioning

that this transition will leave workers and content consumers exploited by the capitalist class. For those involved in the content creation cycle there is also an innate attachment (Latour, 1999), a desire to be activated and reactivated through rolling news and social media content, which creates reliance for audiences and journalists on mobile technology than in turn predetermines what we see, hear and read.

Perrault & Stanfield (2018) explain that mobile journalism also creates fears for older journalists that they have to keep up with new technological and mobile platform evolutions or risk losing their jobs despite management not having to do the same.

Drawing on the work of Bourdieu, they explain this as a tension between journalistic doxa and journalistic habitus (Perrault & Stanfield, 2018). Zuboff (2015) also criticises this exploitation and fears the capitalist elite can suppress both mass media consumers and news producers by merging production with surveillance capitalism allowing our mobile platforms to let Google ‘know more about us than we do about ourselves’ (p. 83). This leads to another issue and key debate within the mobile journalism landscape which is that of privacy and use of our mobile data by media organisations to show us the news they think we want (Nelson, 2020).

2.6 Mobile journalism and privacy concerns

Privacy is cited as one of the primary areas of concern for digital journalists working in 2019 and 2020 as they become more reliant on smartphone technology and emerging hardware, citing geo-location data sharing, social media exposure and over reliance on mobile infrastructure (Bui, Moran 2020; Kay, 2019).

The Digital News Report of 2018, drawing on data from more than a dozen countries across three continents, shows that some news consumers were moving away from

established social media, including from the ‘big five’ (Facebook, Amazon, Apple, Microsoft, Google), mentioning privacy risks when sharing their mobile content (Newman et al, 2018, p. 14). Furthermore, the same study highlights the rise of podcasting, app usage, news alerts and a greater presence of voice-activated technology in homes, such as Amazon Alexa. However, it can be contested that all modern and emerging mobile and smart technology comes with software to maximise future revenue streams by listening, watching and sharing our interests and patterns of behaviour, it is a consumer choice to disable these features or not (Davidow and Malone, 2020).

Pavlik (2013) supports arguments surrounding privacy risks and indicates that journalists operating on location can be more impactful instead of through a screen; they make observations, ask questions and conduct interviews that might yield critical information.

Burum (2014) also touches on this privacy debate in one of the world’s first mobile journalism doctoral studies. He believes that technological change and smartphone-empowered witnesses will not replace the media’s role as ‘watchdogs’. However, he also highlighted that news often happens when the press is not present and due to social media and mobile technology, the press is now ‘present in virtual form’ (Burum, 2014, p. 39).

This virtual form of journalism now includes emerging digital skillsets including data scraping, SEO and AI. With this new technological infusion within media, come greater risks of hacking, data breaches and disinformation which Ferreira (2021) refers to as the inaccurate information intentionally disseminated. Ferreira (2021) explains that disinformation is primarily utilised for political gain and is more prevalent in Global South news markets and cites its success in Brazilian journalism (Ling and Horst 2011; Couldry 2019; Jamil 2019). Dowd (2020, p. 46) refers to this emergence as ‘post-journalism’ where stories are created and shared sometimes without significant journalistic input. Richardson (2020) also raises a key concern regarding journalistic

content and privacy, explaining that citizen-produced video on social media is designed to disappear. She suggests the decision of whether protest coverage happened or not, or when it is removed or deleted, no longer lies with the content creator or news organisation but with big technology corporations.

The future pathway for journalists may be a fusion of mobile technology, more app usage, news alerts, advanced algorithms and augmented intelligence but all come with warnings from the academy. Many cite the lack of regulation and law regarding usage as dominant issues for newsrooms and journalists (Topkins 2017). Bimber (1990), when evaluating technological theory outlines that cultural and social change can follow technology but also culture and society evolve with technology. The deskilling of journalists and their replacement with technology leaves the human aspect of the occupation diminished.

Ornebring (2010, p. 1) suggests that ‘journalists ascribe great power and independent agency to technology’ and explains that while there is deskilling in journalism, there is also up-skilling and reskilling. He also highlights that journalists in the digital age now need to not only reskill, deskill and up-skill but multi-skill simultaneously and this can manifest itself in a changing approach to production, technical, investigative and newsgathering tasks within newsrooms (Ornebring, 2010). These skills pressures are referred to by news managers in all four case studies in the documentary with the more experienced staff at the US outlet concerned by the expectations and demands. The knock-on impacts of these emerging anxieties can in turn alter how journalists see themselves and how they carry out their roles.

2.7 Alienated and disconnected in a mobile newsroom

Through this altering of a journalist's role due to technological influence, reporters who are Mojo focused are spending more time disconnected and away from their news team and newsroom (Deuze, 2019). Dickinson and Bigi (2009, p. 518) describe these solo operating journalists as lone wolves and explain that these reporters tend to 'mythologize their work, invoking the romantic ideal of the journalist as free, autonomous seeker after truth'. With this separation, there are 'fewer checks and balances' made to news content (Dickinson & Bigi, 2009, p. 518) and the quality of journalism can be affected. This detachment is mentioned by Bock (2012) but explored also by Nygren and Gidlund (2012, p. 513), who explain that technology can create 'a system for which each individual functions as an instrument not as a social being'. Nygren and Gidlund (2012) suggest that Marx's views on production can be applied to the information age as people experience 'digital alienation' (p. 514). This occurs when people's digital selves become alienated from the world they live in'. Reporters project a professional self that is available, informed, engaged (Rottwilm, 2014) and connected through social media, broadcast and online channels. Throughout the documentary part of this doctoral submission social media expectations were presented from all four outlets, these include the example of live tweeting shots during court reporting for WDEF News 12 journalists and Facebook live streaming by Léman Bleu reporters. This constant pressure to produce and deliver content presented through the digital self can leave reporters isolated and seen merely as social media handles and cogs in a content distribution machine.

Whittaker (2019) contends that the power dynamic has shifted from content producers to platform distributors including the 'big five'. With technology companies having such a

monopoly on the market, digital journalists fear they are merely contributing free news content that benefits Silicon Valley corporations through advertising revenues (Van Damme, et al 2020; Whittaker, 2019). Consumers, producers and producers of news are fulfilling the industrial roles that Marx warned against and which Green refers to when discussing technological determinism that keep the capitalist elite in control and empowered.

Social media platforms and enhanced smartphone technology are certainly having varying effects on the journalism landscape. These technological changes are also driving change within workflows and creating professional development pressures for mobile journalists (Ornebring, 2010). With this technological driven change, risks to the privacy of content consumers and producers are becoming more apparent as is the alienation of journalists from newsrooms and the altering of their professional identities. The platformisation of our society is normalising 24/7 audience demands, while enriching technological corporations (Van Damme, et al, 2020), with reporters overworked in less stable jobs concerned that they will be replaced by machines or be left behind by younger colleagues. Posetti (2018) captures the extent and effect that technology is having on journalists in the 21st century:

Audience expectations of ‘on-demand’ news, mobile delivery and real-time engagement on social media further increasing pressure on news professionals facing diminishing resources in a never-ending news cycle (p. 59).

Since 2012 and the mobile journalism emergence, smartphone technology has been viewed as a cheaper alternative to traditional broadcasting. Diminishing advertising revenues and growth in social and digital media leave news editors with a choice, to make the move into this chaotic disruptive phase or be left behind.

2.8 Conclusion

This literature review has shown that the journalism landscape is influenced by a number of key factors. These include audience demands, technological influences and medium, as well as patterns of news consumption and location. The principles of immediacy, objectivity, autonomy, public service and ethics discussed by Deuze (2019) as fundamental to journalism continue to have relevance, but are challenged by technological evolution. The influence of mobile technology on journalism practice is significant and upon the core principles of the profession. Extensive research has demonstrated that the rise of mobile journalism has had positive impacts for some Global South media consumers, but with so many media organisations owned by fewer people, risks of bias, political influence and unverified content has created a range of problems and issues exacerbated by Mojo.

There are many benefits from the emergence of mobile journalism including reduced costs for news outlets, more autonomy for journalists, a direct line of communication via social media to content consumers and producers and enhanced live broadcasting options. This is referred to by the news managers in the accompanying PhD documentary who refer to the economic benefits on more than one occasion, and deliberate how Mojo has allowed their American news outlet to monitor broadcast competition. However, the replacement of on-the-ground news teams with solo reporters operating away from newsrooms illustrates that technological advances can also have negative repercussions for media professionals. The expectations of ‘always on deadline’ demands in journalism influenced by narratives of technological determinism are altering societal needs and expectations. Fuchs (2014) cautions against this new system, believing it to be of financial benefit to media corporations (Green, 2002). Regardless of the

technological influence on journalism, journalists fear they cannot be left behind and need to constantly alter their skillsets.

During this study, the term Mojo pertains to a journalist using primarily smartphone technology to gather and distribute news content drawing on the definitions of both Duffy (2020) and Podger (2019). In the forthcoming chapter, the key themes and debates from this literature review are drawn upon to frame a methodological approach to address the research questions and provide further discourse and debate.

Chapter Three: Methodology

Figure 1: Mixed methodological approach

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the broad philosophical underpinnings that informed the design of the study are outlined, including the commitment to an ethnographic approach utilizing qualitative research methods, interviewing and participant observation. The rationale for choosing a practice-based approach is also discussed, drawing on my mobile journalism practitioner background and use of documentary film techniques.

3.2 Practice-based research approach

In the arts and humanities, discussions over the value of practice within the research process have played out over decades. This has led to the emergence of various terminologies to describe the role that practice plays in research. Practice-as-research became more common after it was pioneered by a number of Australian institutions in the 1980s (Candy, 2006), and since then has become a more accepted avenue to contribute to knowledge. Examples of practice-as-research include films, musical recordings and dramatic performances (Skains, 2018). Skains (2018) suggests that undertaking the creative practice leads to answering of the research questions while fostering insights. Candy (2006) argues that for some disciplines, practice-as-research can advance knowledge in that area whether there is a creative artefact or not. There are two other defining paths within practice research - practice-led and practice-based.

Candy (2006, p. 1) argues that ‘practice-based research is an original investigation undertaken in order to gain new knowledge partly by means of practice and the outcomes of that practice’. I chose to adopt a practice-based research approach, drawing on my experience of producing mobile video journalism content. I also felt it was a compelling way to present the key debates, themes and insights generated from this study. Adopting this approach also provided the medium and platform to show the nature of the research field, foreground participant voices and provide context to their approach to newsgathering and mobile content creation. Skains (2018) contends that when undertaking practice-based research, ‘the finalised creative artefact is the basis of the contribution to knowledge’ (Skains 2018, p. 85). Furthermore, she refers to Candy (2006)

when explaining that practice-led research differs, as the research output does not contain a creative practice artefact.

Practice-based and practice-led research are often utilized by researchers working in the arts and humanities as well as communication fields. Practice-led research has a number of critics as well as supporters. Brook (2012) outlines some of the primary reasons why he believes practice-led research is less impactful compared to its practice-based counterpart. He refers to Dewey (1934) who details how practice-led research is akin to someone who takes an interest in painting and then reviews and critiques paintings without ever having painted themselves (Brook, 2012). Brook elaborates on Dewey's point by asking if the work of the practitioner is less appreciated or therefore deemed less impactful based on the views of an observer.

Rust's (2007) review of creative practice-based research in art, design and architecture suggested that 'Many viewed research as embedded and impossible to separate from practice' (p. 15). The same publication found that a number of researchers believed that the 'creative arts cannot be easily compared to other academic disciplines and should be treated differently' (Rust 2007, p. 15). Another view is that practice-based research is favoured in creative and communications faculties due to its legacy to art and use of image as well as text (Buchler and Biggs, 2008).

Leggett (2006) experimented with some practice-based research techniques in the 1970s and 1980s in Sydney, utilizing posters and rudimentary video cameras to demonstrate his artwork and interest in art. His pioneering approach also analysed the role technology has played in his own practice. Leggett explored how the evolution of personal computers

influenced his artwork both from a creative and storage basis. His personal reflections on this practice and how technology altered it, allowed him to branch out from art and focus more in the early 2000s on memory of machines and of humans. Thompson-Bell (2014) produced a creative portfolio including video documentaries of music compositions as part of his practice-based research study. He found that, through creative practice studies, his techniques and style were altered, and he was able to examine and analyze his own practice more comprehensively (Thompson-Bell, 2014). In the context of creating an original piece of journalism, Cross, writing online for the website version of the *Columbia Journalism Review* (2018) explains that ‘The journalist’s mission is to share information, the filmmaker’s mission is to elicit emotion’ (Cross, 2018).

Practice-based doctoral research around the use of mobile journalism has previously been carried out. Ivo Burum undertook mobile journalism doctoral research in Australia between 2011 and 2014. His practice-based output included 2 x 25-minute documentaries showing workshops he led on mobile journalism skills in remote areas of Australia. His research-based practice produced a short handbook on mobile journalism as well as a thesis. Burum’s methodology incorporated qualitative and action research. Similar to this study, Burum drew on insights from a range of contrasting regions including, Australia, China and Denmark (Borum, 2014).

However, Burum’s study did not examine the role of technology in the mobile journalism space. He argues that ‘because the media landscape is rapidly changing, one concern in my research is to maintain currency. This is why my primary focus is on the story element of Mojo rather than on shifting technology’ (p. 77). The lack of research around mobile technology and its impact is a gap in the mobile journalism research landscape, presenting

an opportunity to make a contribution to knowledge in this space. This study differed both in methodological approach, design and output form from that of Burum but the focus on evaluating mobile journalism's influence was common. Burum created two mobile journalism films as creative artefacts but they focused more on the training aspect of mobile journalism rather than investigating the implementation and effects for professional journalists, their workdays and their identity. Mobile technology and the role it plays in changing newsrooms are a key focus area of this research especially at this crucial point in mobile phone usage from 2018 onwards (Swearingen, 2018).

The decision to choose practice-based research was reinforced by the aforementioned views of Candy, Skains, Rust, Buchler and Biggs. Furthermore, I joined the academy as a practice-based educator and feel the contribution of an artefact from practice-based research aligns more to my videography and broadcast skillset, but also demonstrates the impact images can have in research with not just a sole reliance on text to present insights and findings.

Further to this, as a journalism practitioner the opportunity to demonstrate the expectations and challenges from the case study participants was more compelling on screen and through a media, they and I were comfortable with. This approach is also utilized in medical research where Henry and Fetters (2012) argue that video documentation allows for a greater understanding and quantification of data during research. Their study presented insights into the relationships, thoughts, beliefs and emotions from both patients and medical practitioners.

3.3 Ethnography, autoethnography and video ethnography

In undertaking a practice-based study, this research drew on journalism ethnography and some auto-ethnographical techniques, including personal reflections from the fieldwork and editing stages that are presented later in the thesis. The data provided in documentary video form as well as in this thesis is aligned to a new wave of research in the areas of Mojo ethnography (Murphy, 2020; Mabweazara, 2011).

Ethnographical research in journalism has previously provided insights into newsroom practice, newsgathering and the daily lives of journalists (Willig, 2012). Willig further argues that work by the Glasgow University Media Group can be defined as the first wave of ethnographical journalism research but he believes we are now approaching a second wave. In the second wave, Willig adds that economic and cultural influences impact more significantly on journalism. Perrault and Stanfield (2018) suggest that the limitations of their work lay in the surveying of mobile journalists that could have been complimented with ethnographic or long form interviews that would have provided a richer vein of data. Boyer (2013, p. 19) suggests that journalists are ‘constantly oscillating between praxiological and mediological reflections on their practice and on the news’ and therefore make excellent contributors to ethnographic research.

This study draws on ethnographic techniques and investigates the way technology influences mobile journalism practice in newsrooms across the world. Combined with participant observation and a review of current practice, this study contributes to knowledge in the second wave of journalism ethnography. Cramer and McDevitt (2004) believe that ethnography and journalism crossover when it comes to interviewing practice. They believe that feature reporting is similar to ethnography as it aims to

understand people and issues at a deeper level. While interviewing occurs in both ethnographical research and journalism practice, deadlines, objectivity, immersion and impartiality can all differ between both approaches. As Polsky (1998 [1967]) suggests, ‘successful field research depends on the investigator’s trained abilities to look at people, listen to them, think and feel with them, talk with them rather than at them. It does not depend fundamentally on some impersonal apparatus, such as a camera or tape-recorder’ (p. 119). Further to this, video ethnography enables the interviews to be presented beyond the limits of the textual and to give context to the space and the environments in which the field research is conducted (Garrett & Hawkins, 2014).

Adopting this approach reinforces some of the suggestions made by Peters (2012) who highlighted the important role space plays in journalism. With a decade of experience in journalistic interviewing, the transition to a researcher identity, performing the same task but from an ethnographic standpoint proved a natural transition. Further to this, during the field gathering process, diary notes were compiled, and observations noted based on the practice of the journalists being documented and reflection from the researcher’s own practice. Video documenting throughout the journey to and from each research site, throughout each day in the field and five hours of interviews were then transcribed, evaluated and edited to demonstrate ethnographic and autoethnographic techniques during this study. This approach aided the answering of the research questions and allowed the researcher to evaluate contrasting and complimentary views on Mojo implementation and the opportunities and threats it presented to the journalists.

Autoethnography also formed part of the methodological approach as I reflected on my own creative practice journey, documenting this through research field notes. These

insights form part of both the findings chapter 4 and the creative practice reflections in Chapter 6. As Ellis, Adam & Bochner (2010) suggest, ‘Autoethnography is an approach to research and writing that seeks to describe and systematically analyze (*graphy*) personal experience (*auto*) in order to understand cultural experience (*ethno*)’ (p. 1). Kelly (2016) incorporated autoethnographic methodological approaches into his practice-based doctoral study through videotaping his personal journey to abstain from social media for 80 days. His use of video and reflection upon the journey he took through his video recorded diary demonstrates that autoethnography with video has been utilised successfully in previous practice-based studies. Autoethnographical approaches are evidenced later on in this thesis when analysing my mobile journalism practice, analyzing the creative artefact and reviewing how the practice of others influenced my own mobile journalism as well as reflecting on my creative practice journey. Gans (1999) defines autoethnography as autobiography written by sociologists involving deeper reflection. However, autoethnography is also incorporated into journalism research. Hughes (2018) explores autoethnography when reflecting on journalism education as ‘a merging of the techniques, theories and practices found in ethnography with those of autobiography and memoir’ (p. 42). Niedderer and Stokes (2007), when evaluating the merits of practice-based qualitative and ethnographic research in the arts and humanities refer to the work of Miles and Huberman who explain that objectivity, reliability and validity need to be evidenced to demonstrate research vigour. Niedderer and Stokes (2007, p. 12) describe how ‘expertise’, ‘discriminatory judgement’ and ‘tacit’ knowledge can all be utilised to fulfil the aforementioned expectations of Miles and Huberman and therefore argue that there are significant ‘valid’ and ‘rigorous’ (Niedderer and Stokes (2007, p. 13) opportunities for practice-based research ethnography to provide a range of contributions to knowledge.

3.4 Ethnography and mobile journalism interviewing

This study is wholly qualitative in orientation. In bringing the ethnographical approach to life in this study, qualitative methods were suitable because ‘Qualitative research is interdisciplinary, interpretive, political and theoretical in nature. Using language to understand concepts based on people’s experience, it attempts to create a sense of the larger realm of human relationships’ (Brennan, 2013, p. 4). Brennan (2013), as an advocate for qualitative research in media studies, also stresses that the choice of method by a researcher comes from the questions they wish to ask. These include an evaluation of mobile journalism practice and a critical examination of its impact on journalistic identity drawing on the insights from the case site interviewees and three established media academics.

Interviews are one popular qualitative method that complement the ethnographic ethos of this research. Smith (2009) argues that the best interviews in qualitative research are ones that allow the ‘subjects to express themselves in their own way’ (p. 4). For this study an open-ended semi-structured approach was adopted within each of the four case study sites NDTV, Léman Bleu, WDEF News 12 and STV2, allowing interviewees to explain why and how they implemented content gathering techniques based on technological advances. At least three key interviews with employees from each of four international case studies were conducted on camera between January 2018 and May 2019. The producer and editor roles were sit-down interviews and were intermingled with the day-to-day fly-on-the-wall focus of the reporters. Critics of qualitative research and interviewing in journalism studies include Atton (2008) who suggested that not enough detail is provided on the style of interviewing and what questions are asked. Due to this

study having been recorded to video with audio included, these concerns did not arise, as tone and delivery are evidenced both in the interviewing style and the interviewee responses.

Baker (2012) questions how many qualitative interviews are enough. She outlines that when including expert interviews that 10 may be sufficient if it is a small field of specialism. This research included 30 interviews with media academics, reporters, anchors, producers and editors. Etherington (2017), explains that stories are reconstructions of people's experiences, which are told at a particular time and to a researcher at a certain point in their lives. In this study, the journalists recalled examples of when and how mobile technology impacted on their professional expectations, their identity and their newsrooms. These stories were often detailed and reflective with the journalists also talking about the news reports they were working on during the recording of the documentary film, in real time as a window into their current world and situations. Etherington (2017) suggests that through the recounting of stories to the researcher we gain 'memorable, interesting knowledge that brings together layers of understanding about a person, their culture and how they created change' (p. 6). In the example of this doctoral study, the change was in some situations influenced by economics, employment, societal shifts and technological advances.

27 interviews were conducted across the four case studies during a five-day field gathering process with each media outlet. The first 20 interviews were expert interviewees quoted directly in this thesis and in the practice element of this research in video form. Three further interviews were conducted via web video calls with academics based in the US, Romania and Kuwait. Tables 1 and 2 provide a summary. Interviews with the letter 'S' denotes an STV2 interview conducted in Scotland. 'A' represents an

American interview conducted in the US with WDEF News 12, ‘I’ for an Indian interview at NDTV and ‘G’ for Léman Bleu journalists in Geneva, Switzerland. ‘R’ represents researchers who were expert interviewees that were conducted remotely utilising screen-to-screen recordings.

Code	Name	Title	Employer	Experience
R-1	Professor Kristoffer Holt	Lecturer and media author	Gulf University, Kuwait	18 years in Media Education + Academic
R-2	Professor Georgeta Drula	Lecturer and media author	Bucharest University, Romania	17 years in Media Education + Academia
R-3	Professor Mary Bock	Professor and broadcaster	University of Texas, Austin	15 years in TV + Radio 18 years in Media Education

Table 1: Background and information pertaining to academic interviewees

All three media academics provided insights that helped shape the study with both the written aspects, the editing process and editorial decision making surrounding the creative output. Table 2, which follows, provides information about the interviews that were conducted during field work and provides the reader with an understanding of the roles each played within their organisation as well as their level of experience. All interviews are coded to aid the reader throughout the findings and discussions chapters while further information is provided in the appendices pertaining to the fieldwork interviews.

Code	Title	Employer	(Years) Experience at time of interview in 2018 (STV + WDEF 12 and 2019 (NDTV + Léman Bleu
S-1	Bruce McKenzie- Reporter	STV2 Scotland	14
S-2	Kirsty Feerick – Production Journalist	STV2 Scotland	2
S-3	Suzanne Lord- Output Editor	STV2 Scotland	17
A-1	Dutch Terry – News Director	WDEF12 USA	24
A-2	Bill Mitchell – Reporter/Assignment Manager	WDEF12 USA	59
A-3	Amber Worthy - Anchor/Reporter	WDEF12 USA	5
A-4	William Collins Parker - Web Producer	WDEF12 USA	35
I-1	Amitoj Singh - Anchor/Reporter	NDTV India	10
I-2	Neeta Sharma - Reporter	NDTV India	19
I-3	Shitij Kumar Gupta –	NDTV India	23

	Executive Producer		
I-4	Jatin Gupta – Deputy Production lead	NDTV India	25
I-5	Arun Singh - Anchor	NDTV Hop Live	10
I-6	Rheea Cheema – Reporter/Anchor	NDTV Hop Live	9
I-7	Amber Choudhary - Producer	NDTV Hop Live	4
G-1	Laurent Keller – Director of News	Léman Bleu	20
G-2	Odessa Blanc – Sports Reporter	Léman Bleu	9
G-3	Julie Zaugg – Reporter/Anchor	Léman Bleu	5
G-4	Celine Argento – Reporter/Anchor	Léman Bleu	5
G-5	Denis Palma - Reporter	Léman Bleu	26
G-6	Priscilla Chacon – Reporter	Léman Bleu	4
A-5	Ashley Henderson - Reporter	WDEF12 USA	24
A-6	Robyn Estabrook - Reporter	WDEF12 USA	4

I-8	Bunnat Grower - Technician	New Delhi	3
I-9	Adbul Qadir - Cameraman	NDTV Hop Live	5
I-10	Pabitra R. Jena – Inhouse Reporter	NDTV India	5
I-12	Richa Jain Kalra – Lead Anchor	NDTV India	18

Table 2: Background and information pertaining to the case study interviewees

More information regarding roles and areas of journalistic expertise for Table 2 interviewees is available in the appendices.

3.5 Participant observation

‘Participant observation is perhaps the easiest method in the world to use because it is ubiquitous and we can all already do it’ (Laurier, 2016, p. 2). Domingo (2003) suggests that participant observation of journalists has been documented by academics since the 1960s. He further outlines that his participant observational research conducted in newsrooms provided ‘Loads of raw, first-hand data’ (Domingo, 2003, p. 5). Gans (1999) contests that participant observation has been renamed as ethnography and this umbrella title covers multiple qualitative research methods. Part of the methodological approach for this research involved participant observation and video documenting of the weekly and daily requirements of news journalists in the case study sites. Gans (1999) argues that participant observation is an expensive, time consuming and laborious, research approach. However, during the fieldwork, the fusion of interviewing and participant observation

provided a focused in-depth look into current practices in mobile and broadcast journalism and demonstrated their similarities and differences. Laurier (2006) believes that vantage point and the correct tools are key to providing strong research outputs. In this study, as the researcher I was utilizing the same tools as those I was observing and due to the embedded focus of the fieldwork, I had full access to the participant's workday.

This study also allowed for investigation into content gathering techniques from contrasting newsrooms and provided scope, via the sit-down interviews with the producers, reporters and news editors to understand how live news and as live journalism is aided or restricted via mobile technology and the platformisation of media. Aside from the formal interviews, the aforementioned 'casual conversations' (Domingo 2003, p. 6) also formed part of the participant observation and qualitative research process. Three interviews were also conducted via internet video calls with media academics who helped form and shape this study. The academics reacted to the initial commercial edit of the practice-based output and following the viewing provided further insights and views related to the key debates and issues surrounding mobile journalism, technology in newsrooms and journalistic identity. The methodological approach deploying observation aligns more to that of Burd who sees journalists as similar to sociologists, observers, analysers and documenters of the world around them (Burd, 1983).

3.6 Case study selection

Figure 2: Four case studies in three continents were chosen for this research

A significant aspect of the research design was case site selection. Rather than a direct comparison approach, the choice was made to explore a variety of different sized news organizations at different stages of their mobile journalism implementation process including early adopters and innovators (Rogers, 2003). This method allowed for a wider range of data from each site rather than repetition, as well as providing a more extensive overview into mobile journalism developments in different geographical contexts. Burum's (2014) research also contained a similar international dimension with his site selection, but the study did not examine the influence of mobile technology on journalists. Perrault and Stanfield (2018) advise that mobile journalism research focusing on individual newsroom case studies would provide more impactful data to build on their earlier mobile journalism research. The four case sites selected for this study varied in size of broadcast output as well as location. STV2 in Scotland, NDTV in New Delhi, Léman Bleu in Geneva and WDEF News 12 in Tennessee. Through selection of newsrooms in different geographical, social and economic news, a wider range of insights could be garnered.

STV2 is headquartered in Glasgow but the bureau chosen for the primary field research covered Ayrshire, a more rural region. Field visits to both locations were undertaken

during the study. The small Ayrshire team comprised just two employees, employing a Mojo focus that allowed the employees autonomy and independence when covering their 300 square mile region. STV2 formed part of the STV group PLC and was funded through advertising revenues and broadcast rights, (Dorsey, 2020). WDEF News 12 is located in Chattanooga, Tennessee, but their mobile journalists cover an area of more than 600 square miles across four states, providing a diverse range of news output and they first implemented mobile journalism in late 2012. They are owned by Morris Multimedia and are commercial broadcasters, (Miller and Jessell, 2021). NDTV in New Delhi is an international broadcaster with more than 1400 employees and they switched to mobile journalism in summer 2017 while pioneering the world's first vertical live streaming news channel for mobile only devices. According to some Indian journalists the news outlet is aligned to the Congress political party and therefore do not show support to prime minister Modi and his BJP party, (Anand, 2015). Léman Bleu an independent TV news outlet in Geneva is considered a European pioneer in Mojo and delivers workshops and training for other news outlets since their Mojo implementation in summer 2015. The Swiss outlet is partially government funded and operates in an open media market where a 'below average amount of attention' is paid to political reporting (Imhoff, 2012). Perrault and Stanfield (2018) argue that particular research of newsroom case studies that are a blend of mobile and traditional broadcasting would provide an avenue for further and focused research, building on their survey based mobile journalism study.

STV2 News launched in April 2017 and began implementing mobile journalism practice amongst its reporting team. Their head of news output was pushing for this approach across her bureaus in Scotland due to staffing and budgetary restrictions. The Ayrshire reporter, who previously worked in commercial radio was their lead mobile journalist. He was also utilized by the news organization for mobile journalism staff upskilling and

training. My field study there took place in January and February of 2018. The local news focus of STV provided a varied news patch for mobile journalism demonstration with both journalists covering sports, news and weather on a daily basis. The alienation and isolation of a one-man band reporter was an issue I was able to observe, investigate and demonstrate throughout my time with STV2. The idealism of TV journalism versus the reality are themes that have rarely been explored and analyzed in journalism research. Bock (2012) is one of a small number of scholars who outline that the transition to mobile journalism is often at the 'price of newsroom collaboration and camaraderie' (p. 33). The lead reporter was often all alone daily in a small car with just two smartphones, a laptop and a camera kit, driving from one remote location to another gathering content and pinging it back. His colleagues became his phones based on my observations, they helped him do his job, communicate his news agenda and share his content quickly.

WDEF News 12 was the focus of the second case study, with fieldwork conducted in late spring 2018. This stage built on and further developed the key themes which emerged from the STV2 case surrounding journalistic identity and mobile journalism practice. A Fox affiliate for Charlotte, North Carolina, spearheaded by Geoffrey Roth had launched as a mobile journalism only outfit in 2015 (Scott, 2016) and represented a valid and compelling data site. Pedersen (2017) outlined how the station employed eight remote video journalists with an IP only system. However, WDEF News 12 had created a similar newsroom three years prior without receiving the same national publicity. The station's chief engineer along with the news director had taken the mobile journalism route blended with camera technology. Their live streaming output has been provided by Dejero since 2012, this was also the same mobile broadcasting platform utilized by STV2, however the American outlet had far more experience with live mobile broadcasting. Their journalists were regularly sent to hostile crime scenes with multiple gang fatalities

and were expected to cover severe weather conditions, including tornadoes. The primary rationale behind the second case study lay in their experience within the mobile journalism sphere, six years more than STV and NDTV and three years more than Léman Bleu. The WDEF 12 case study provided more in-depth insights into the changeability and platformisation within broadcast journalism. The key interviewees provided deeper analysis and more rounded reflections, with three of the expert interviews having a combined 100 years' experience in American TV news and witnessed a significant amount of technological change. The expert interviewees included an Emmy-nominated producer, a web and social media producer, a first-generation mobile journalist and an experienced assignment manager who is also one of the longest serving active broadcasters in American history having begun his career in radio in the 1950s and transitioned into TV in 1960.

As pioneers in global mobile journalism practice NDTV were crucial to this research. The addition of a pivotal election season enhanced the rich vein of data and provided compelling examples of rigorous news coverage illuminating concerns over journalistic identity, platformisation and alienation. The uniqueness of Hop Live, a vertical only live streaming channel for younger audiences, designed for social media, was innovative as an example of the digitalization of news. The Indian TV station had been cited in *India Resists* in April 2018 regarding a debate on mobile journalism usage. The article highlighted the positives of utilizing mobile journalism technology but queried if reporters who do the jobs of two employees are being paid two salaries. It also raises the question surrounding the privatization of Indian news in the early 1990s and how advertising revenue affects technological choice and audience engagement.

The fourth case site, Léman Bleu in Switzerland, is a centralized independent news hub

that receives governmental funding as a public service broadcaster. The station deploys reporters to urban and rural locations and is recognized within the media world and academic spheres as a pioneer in mobile journalism implementation. Goujard (2016) profiled the station as a global leader in Mojo for the International Journalists Network. She highlighted increased activity, proximity and reactivity from their reporters due to mobile journalism adoption. The 2018 book, *Cases on Smart Learning Environments* refers to Léman Bleu as experimenting with technology in newsrooms and explains how their Mojo transition also influenced the BBC. Their newsgathering approach aimed to future proof TV news despite dwindling advertising revenues. They planned to do this by training their audiences and local community to become content gathers therefore ensuring their audiences are both participants/producers as well as observers/consumers, akin to what Bruns (2008) refers to. The news outlet went fully Mojo in 2015 for the summer and then decided that each reporter could pick their own recording and editing devices depending on their comforts and skills, creating autonomy and independence for their news team.

Building upon the research design and case study rationale, these four contrasting regions were chosen due to each having English-speaking journalists with mobile journalism training to varying levels, with contrasting audience sizes and engagement levels. The four outlets had different audience demographics but all who consume mobile journalism output on a daily basis. Each case study provided interviews and ethnographic opportunities including participant observation. The practice element of the research was facilitated by the openness of the organizations to allow me to be embedded in their newsrooms for a working week. This valuable opportunity facilitated avenues to garner compelling data, engaging insights and to make a unique contribution to practice-based journalism research.

	<u>WDEF News 12</u>	<u>STV2</u>	<u>Léman Bleu</u>	<u>NDTV</u>
Audience DMA	341,190	100,000	250,000	60 Million Households in India + 20 Million outside India
No. Of Newsroom Employees	20	15	15	300
Hours of Daily Live TV news	5	2.5	1.5	18-20 Hours
Actively Practising Mobile Journalists	14	15	15	75
Newsroom Budget	\$1.2 Million	£300,000	1 Million CHF	24 Million INR

Table 3: Audience, Staffing, Broadcasting and budget information for each case site

	<u>WDEF News 12</u> <u>Mojo</u>	<u>STV Mojo (S-1)</u>	<u>Léman Blue Mojo</u>	<u>NDTV Mojo (I-2)</u>
Video News Shoots (Over 5 days)	10	5	5	11
Camera used 100%	8	2	0	0
Mojo Used 100%	1	2	5	11 (100%)
Blend Mojo + Camera	1	1	0	0
Live Shots (5 days)	4	3	4	18
Camera used 100%	0	3	2	0
Mojo Used 100%	100	0	2	18 (100%)

Table 4: Information provided by Mojos on their broadcast expectations each week

3.7 Case study site access and power dynamics

Access to each case study was secured in accordance with the ethics process of the (then) School of Media, Culture and Society at the University of the West of Scotland. Each newsroom was initially approached via email, with follow up calls or in person video meetings and issuing of participant information documentation outlining the research focus and expectations. This paperwork is presented in the appendices.

While some mobile ethnographic research draws on the independence of being physically removed from fieldwork, in this study the case site organizations were supportive of me being geographically immersed in their work environments. Gray (2011, p. 2) explains the importance of the ‘access ladder’ for fieldwork when drawing on the work of Homans (1958) and details how researchers and participants benefit from each other in a remuneration type exchange. Gray (2011) discusses how both parties are motivated to continue the exchange during the fieldwork stages based on an immediate or at times future reward. STV2 were willing to partake in the research due to my standing in the mobile journalism and broadcasting communities and this same pattern repeated itself for each of the case locations. The editors were more open to me as a journalist coming into their newsroom and rather than a traditional researcher or ethnographer, despite making it clear that I was present to undertake doctoral research. Lierop (2015) explores ethical challenges including interference during fieldwork, suggesting that ‘the presence of a researcher can be quite alien and affects respondents and context - in the past’ (p. 24). The interviewees did not raise any concerns and often saw me as a colleague and fellow journalist in their presence. The participants willingly contributed and saw the video practice element as an area they could relate to. Lierop (2015) refers to Bryman (2008) when considering the merits of covert research and informed consent in qualitative

research. All participants spoke openly about their news values, roles and shared opinions regarding mobile journalism. Gray (2011) highlights the opportunity for resentment and hostility during fieldwork and a feeling of being exploited by participants; this was not the case during this study. The participants were briefed weeks ahead of my fieldwork and did not decline to participate. Further to this, all participants were comfortable to have their names, faces, voices and quotes/soundbites presented in this research and viewed it as a professional broadcast output, no participant requested anonymity or expressed confidentiality issues or concerns despite it being made available to them. Concerns surrounding a power dynamic, with news managers bringing the researcher into the space did not create conflict, as the participants were aware of my practice-based background and career in TV journalism. This was how it felt based on my observations and their rapport with me during this time. Most of the newsroom had researched and watched my reporting on YouTube prior to coming to their stations. Borneman and Hammoudi (2009) explain the importance of trust between an ethnographer and the participants but caution against developing sustained relationships as this can create contradictory results from fieldwork. This concern did not arise, but professional communication channels have been maintained since the fieldwork pertaining to other subject material not aligned to the study.

3.8 Documentary as journalism practice

Figure 3: Overview of the complementary aspects to both the written and practice elements

Documentary film was first defined a century ago by a Scottish filmmaker from Stirling called John Grierson who explained that it is ‘a creative treatment of actuality’ (Hardy 1979, p. 298). The moving picture era has since evolved, providing a non-fictional view of the world we live in, from travelogues of the 1920s through to cinema verité and the emergence of documentary journalism in the 1950s which some critics argue was both bland and statistic heavy (Cross, 2018). Lancaster (2013) suggests that documentary journalism has since evolved with content producers spending less time delivering voiceover and facts and now ‘give time to let their characters speak’ (p. 3). There are significant differences between documentary journalism and news journalism, which are evidenced in the practice-based outputs from this study. These include a focus on emphasizing the character’s voices, the researcher being off camera, less frenetic edits

and audio consciously designed to set the tone (Lancaster, 2013). Both news reporting and documentary journalism align, however, in having similar pace and simplicity when conveying their stories. Lancaster (2013) refers to this as a broadcast news style which works for both forms. Documentary making has also been impacted by the digitalization of journalism, with the proliferation of smartphones, harnessing of UGC from audiences, which is referenced in the middle part of the PhD documentary. This facilitates the ability to collaborate through social media platforms, changing how video content is created, as mentioned by news managers at *Léman Bleu* two thirds of the way through the PhD documentary runtime and within the literature (Nash et al, 2014).

The interview-focused talking heads style utilized during this study is more suited to a non-biased journalistic approach where the reporter does not significantly influence the behavior of on-screen interviewees. Bruzzi (2006), discussing new documentary style, states that this form of filmmaking has ‘not been rendered obsolete by the advent of more interactive forms of film and TV’ (p. 33) but has evolved. Rhodes (2014) suggests that the interview-led documentary, where the talking heads are not facing directly into the camera produces a more polished look but also explains that if the talking heads look directly into the camera, it is often easier to edit and also puts the interviewees more at ease. The ‘Spray and Pray approach’ to shooting content to augment the interviewees discussed by Lancaster (2013, p. 15) was not utilized during the filming process due to concerted efforts regarding planning and strategic shooting of cutaways relevant to the interviewee insights. Cross (2018) highlights that while documentary allows the filmmaker to blur the lines between professional and personal experiences as part of the creative process, documentary journalism does not. While both Louis Theroux and Stacey Dooley align to the journalistic documentary form, their use of themselves as vehicles to carry on screen personal messages conflicts with Lancaster’s arguments on what makes

documentary journalism impactful, the space and time afforded to interviewees in front of the camera, not the journalist or researcher.

Schultz (2007) refers to an ethnographic approach to journalism research drawing on examples from a wealth of qualitative data presented from field research within newsrooms. She refers to Bourdieu (1993) when explaining that journalists create cultural goods and do so often without thinking about what they are doing, performing tasks with almost a gut feeling and based on instinct (Schultz, 2007). This aligned with the role I performed when recording and interviewing throughout the fieldwork in this study, as much of my practice was based on journalistic instinct and experience of remaining detached, ethical and impartial. During the content gathering process, the role of ethnographer and journalist began to blur. An ethnographer without journalistic experience may have struggled with what Schultz refers to as ‘routinizing the unexpected’ (p. 195) but due to my prior broadcast media experience dealing with erratic news cycles and newsroom environments I was able to adapt quickly to the time constraints and logistical video demands placed upon the reporters I was observing and interviewing.

3.9 Interview transcription and thematic analysis

Transcription of video interviews and use of transcription by ethnographers is discussed by both Murthy (2008) and Oliver (2005). Murthy explains the benefits of video usage with some interviewees recording their own thoughts and sharing the video to the researcher. Within this study, the researcher was present and compiled the content himself taking the task of content gathering away from the interviewee. Murthy also highlights the risk of some interviewees who may play up to the camera (Murthy, 2008). Almost all of the interviewees that partook in this research had extensive on-camera experience and the novelty of playing to a camera was not a concern. Oliver (2005) details two approaches to

take when transcribing qualitative interviewees, including naturalism and denaturalism - the latter includes the removal of stutters, pauses and coughs. The approach taken to transcribing the interviews in this research was denaturalism, with a focus on the topics and issues detailed by each interviewee at the four case studies. With nearly all participants being experienced broadcast journalists accomplished in oration and on camera delivery, the concerns presented by Oliver (2005) were minimized. I reviewed all of the interviews before selecting those most aligned to answering the research questions surrounding mobile journalism and its impact. Following this, transcriptions were grouped together based on themes that emerged after listening and watching the on-camera interviews and analyzing the transcriptions in textual form. This approach to transcribing and then analyzing interviews is common in medical research. Bolderston (2012) explains how transcription allows the researcher to become more familiar with the voices of the interviewees before grouping them into comparable categories using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis has been used effectively in previous qualitative research including psychiatry studies when reviewing interview transcriptions. Galvin (2015) et al explain that the most important aspect of thematic analysis is becoming as familiar as possible with the transcriptions including reading and rereading and making notes before coding and grouping the issues and finally naming them. For Galvin et al (2015), the challenge of having multiple researchers evaluate the same transcriptions and then decide separately and together what the themes were for their psychiatric study took significant time. However, as this was a solo research project this issue did not present itself and I had also conducted and transcribed the interviews myself without using a third-party transcriber or videographer. This methodological approach of augmenting the interview transcriptions with field notes using thematic analysis is considered 'good practice' (Bolderston, 2012, p. 74).

3.10 Ethical considerations

Practice-based journalism research and the academy can ideologically clash, with industry journalists now working in universities struggling to adhere to university ethical guidelines (Vine, Batty, Muir, 2014). The previously mentioned journalistic principle of holding interviewees and the powerful to account has to be suppressed in a more reflective academic sphere (Vine, et al, 2014). It is for these reasons that in some regions, including Australia, there has been a decline in practice-based journalism research over the last decade as industry-facing academics struggle to reshape content gathering approaches to that of university guidelines. In some instances, early career researchers are being encouraged to abandon their practice until they have secured doctorates or senior university positions, (Vine, et al, 2014).

Further to this is a hesitancy from newsrooms to allow former colleagues turned researchers back into their media environments. Thomsen (2014) is one of the few ethnographers and broadcast journalists to have spent extensive time in newsrooms in the UK and Denmark, her work points to the challenges that non-journalists turned researchers face in addressing the erratic schedules and work environments of reporters and videographers. Thomsen (2014, p. 6) also highlights the importance of her previous decade in broadcasting as allowing her to 'be accepted by the group'. Thomsen explains that ethical issues could have arisen were it not for the journalists seeing her actively working during her time in their newsrooms rather than just observing. She explains that she was seen as a 'companion and colleague' (Thomsen, 2014, p. 10) but highlights that others may not have been treated in the same manner during similar doctoral fieldwork. The experiences and reflections that Thomsen refers to in 2014 were akin to those that I had in newsrooms in 2018 and 2019.

Previous ethnographic research conducted by Murthy, Oliver and Arber all conducted in medical facilities highlight the importance of in-person interviewing and respect through participant observation. The same studies highlight the importance of ethical access to case sites. The moral dilemmas referenced earlier in this study pertaining to ethnographic researchers when interviewing patients, doctors and caregivers present ethical standards for this study and encouraged ethnographic detachment and disconnection. The participants within this research were willing, experienced and confident professional broadcast communicators and were not in as vulnerable or ethically exposed positions as hospital patients or primary caregivers.

3.11 Conclusion

The research methodology guiding this study was qualitatively focused, incorporating interviewing, participant observation and documentary production. The decision to create a creative practice artefact allowed for a more visually compelling medium to present the critiques, insights and reflections generated from this research. Previous Mojo research output, while also in video form, has rarely examined the impact of technological-influenced changes on newsrooms. Burum's video documentaries shone a light on indigenous communities using Mojo kits and Perrault and Stanfield's (2018) work outlines that the shortcomings of their study are due to not conducting ethnographic interviews and not focusing on individual newsrooms case sites. Gans (1999), Bourdieu (1993), Gray (2011) and Lierop (2015) all raise crucial ethical debates surrounding the practice element of this type of research all of which were addressed due to the willingness and openness of all participants to appear on camera and share their views on mobile journalism.

Burd (1983) explains how 'most people who do journalism have little time to think about

it' (p. 10). This study presented an opportunity for the participants as well as the researcher to do this for the first time in their careers. Having observed, interviewed and documented journalists from across the four international case studies, stronger analysis, discourse and reflection on mobile journalism and its impact on journalistic identity and workflows can be garnered due to the merits of adopting a practice-based qualitative research methodology.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I present insights drawn from interviews, research diary entries and reflections from the fieldwork across all four case sites. The findings are presented thematically and informed by the research themes discussed throughout the literature review, including alienation, platformisation and the changing identity of reporters. In the first instance, each case study setting is presented in turn with findings from each grouped under the aforementioned thematic headings. All interviewees have been assigned identifiers detailed in Table 1 and Table 2. In order to clarify terms used by interviewees, Table 5 provides a glossary of broadcast terms.

Term	Explanation
To Package/PKG	To compile a video or radio report
OBs	Outside broadcasts
Stream	Compressed Video sent via the internet
Bonded Cellular Live Shots	Combining mobile phone broadcast feeds
Live Hits	Live on location reporting, usually brief
Two Way	Interview between Anchor and Reporter

Table 5: Glossary of broadcast terms

4.2 STV2: Scottish mobile journalism in action

STV2 launched in April 2017 with the aim of bringing local news to local audiences, (Gulyas and Baines, 2020). Their newsgathering approach was to have small teams in bureaus in Ayr, Dundee and Aberdeen, all generating local news, which in turn could feed into the national output. A number of their reporters were mobile journalists, including their team in Ayr. The smallest team for the STV2 output involved just two people - S2, a production journalist with a Mojo focus and a one-man band mobile reporter and content gatherer coded as S1, whose background was in radio reporting. Their manager and head of news output was an experienced national broadcaster who had worked for both the BBC and commercial organisations, coded as S3. All three provided expert interviews during fieldwork in early 2018, with participant observation conducted during the five days with S1 while he focused on newsgathering, editing and presenting. When analysing the interview transcripts and field notes, a number of key themes emerged. These include alienation for the journalists, convergence of media platforms, a loss of identity for the small bureau team and a reliance on mobile technology.

4.2.1 Alienation: The one-man newsroom

The solitary and solo aspect of mobile journalism is referred to on numerous occasions by Karhunen (2017), with the Finnish news editor even referring to the safety risks surrounding the profession. The STV2 mobile journalist rarely travelled to the Ayr based newsroom because he could leave his home in Dumfries, drive across Ayrshire to each video shoot filing content and sharing it via his smartphone and then return home. The challenge of spending a week with him was mostly logistical as he traversed a ‘huge patch, 300 square miles, it’s bigger than Luxemburg’ (S1, 2018). Operating as a Mojo provided him with the freedom and autonomy to shoot, edit, file and share content

remotely and yet there were intimations that he was alienated from a newsroom and a news team. Having a production journalist (S2) based in Ayr was a link, but both were removed from the main Glasgow newsroom and from each other for extended periods of time. The production journalist added that when she has shot solo as a Mojo 'there is room for mistakes', adding that 'there's more ways you can spot a mistake, if there is a whole team, one person can catch something' (S2, 2018). Her concern is supported by the literature, with Ryan (2014) outlining that the efficiency of a two-person team outweighs that of a one-man band reporter. Bock's (2012) work and research by Deuze (2019) also details how news managers place unrealistic expectations on reporters who have to self-shoot and edit. This was evidenced by the workload of S1 who at times would gather content for up to five different news, weather and sports stories per day.

With a reporter, a camera person, field producer and possibly even a light or sound technician, all crew members are able to specialise on their own craft skills throughout the content gathering process and individually contribute to the finalised news package and coverage. With only one person to fulfil all of these roles, a reliance on an assignment manager or senior editor to bounce ideas back off in the newsroom becomes more important. However, the physical and editorial disconnect from this newsroom-based employee and their Mojo counterparts produced changes to workflows, for example, the Mojo reporter made his own final editorial calls without having a colleague present. This added to the pressure of leaving one journalist on their own gathering, editing, producing, sharing content and making their own decisions on the spot which can also present more opportunities for poor ethical and legal decision making where a reporter is dealing with more sensitive subject material without support. Dickinson and Bigi (2009) highlighted these types of concerns when observing the expectations on one-man reporters prior to Mojo implementation. In the STV2 case, the Mojo reporter touched base with the

Glasgow newsroom less than twice a day, once in the morning for an editorial meeting via telephone call and after that sometimes only once more to confirm a story deadline. While he did not refer directly either in interview or during my time to the isolation surrounding the role, he did explain how vast an area he covered ‘it’s the size of Luxembourg’ and explained it was ‘just him’, (S1, 2018). The terrain the Mojo reporter traversed was remote and rural with poor roads and limited mobile and internet infrastructure which also impacted on his ability to share his news content due to restricted 4G coverage. The Mojo reporter was very much isolated, being his own troubleshooter, without a support network or a news team while still being placed with significant newsgathering demands.

4.2.2 Convergence culture: content production

Chakavah and Bogen (2007) define media convergence as the point where all mass media becomes one medium due to the impact of technological evolution. They also argue that media convergence often happens for economic reasons, and both views were reflected in the experience of observing journalistic practice at STV2. The shift to mobile journalism for the new STV2 channel was an attempt to produce local news efficiently, using smartphones with fewer staff required. STV2 maximised user-generated content, highlighted by the TV editor, ‘we can use our audience a lot more, they can be in constant touch with us’ (S3, 2018).

The TV editor also suggested that content convergence, ‘changes the way we gather our news, we put out calls, for case studies, people stuck in cars give us video diaries, it brought our audience closer to us’ (S3, 2018). Convergence of this sort was only possible due to the tools of a reporter existing in the hands of a member of the public, because ‘anyone can be a journalist now, you can do it from a bog-standard smartphone’ (S1, 2018). However, the Mojo reporter drew an important distinction between the content that

he produces and that of a viewer, suggesting that ‘you can see quite quickly the difference between what’s shot by the public and the camera men using them, simple things, framing shots nicely, not a wiggly shot, getting the sound right’ (S1, 2018).

The converging role of consumer and creator of news can have both positive and negative influences (Holt & Karlsson, 2013; Thurman, 2008; Thurman 2018). S2, the production journalist, echoed Drula’s (2014) views regarding convergence, suggesting, ‘it would be impossible to say iPhone technology hasn’t impacted the way we receive news, it’s definitely changed the way to share stories and get stories out’. Further to this, both STV journalists expressed concern over their extensive workloads, accentuated due to the convergence of the roles of reporter, social media producer, editor, writer and TV presenter into one role. This reinforces the arguments Rottwilm (2014) puts across that too much is expected of mobile journalists in the digital age. Convergence of newsroom roles due to the rise of mobile journalism, coupled with audience input, leaves the reporters vulnerable.

4.2.3 Shifting professional identities

‘It’s completely transformed what we do and how we do it’ (S3, 2018)

I witnessed the loss of the professional reporter identity during my observations of STV2. For example, in many cases the Mojo reporter was a content gatherer, a human hoover of video clips, interviews and still images without being able to take full ownership of any of the content. The lack of a daily video package expectation meant his voice, face and journalistic style was not being leant to a finalised piece of produced video reporting content on a regular basis. As S1 explained, ‘you’re splitting yourself from being a journalist and the person filming’. Through the convergence of the roles of editor,

shooter, producer, reporter and social media manager into one Mojo, there is some evidence of a change in identity, which is in contrast to the role of the traditional TV reporter owning the entire story each day. S1 admitted that through mobile journalism the quality of the material can be affected negatively because, ‘a craft cameraman can see the shots a reporter might not see’. He went on to state that an emphasis on speed and newsgathering demands outweigh that of other expectations, ‘I think mobile journalists can cover a patch easier and quickly, not to the same standard as a craft camera person’ (S1, 2018). To reinforce that the speed of newsgathering has become increasingly important, the production journalist explained her primary job functions:

My job is creating a 4-to-6-minute bulletin, we need lots of content, it’s good if (S1) can do that as quick as possible with the highest quality, the easiest way to do that is with mobile journalism (S2, 2018).

She reiterated this point during her field study interview by suggesting that ‘If there is breaking news, a car crash, that’s instant, you can film it and send it back to HQ in Glasgow’ (S2, 2018). The lack of specialism expected by the Mojo can undermine the identity of the reporter. I witnessed a trained journalist performing many roles but concerned that none of them was being delivered to a high standard. Yet, the journalist had little time to dwell on those workflow concerns and implement significant change due to the constant rolling newsgathering expectations that took precedence. This led to him having to develop workarounds to ensure the content was to a reasonable standard, ‘If you can get the sound right and then lit right, you can get away with a lot’, (S1, 2018). Burd (1983) identified journalistic workflow concerns 30 years prior to Mojo, stating that reporters have little time to dwell on the how and why of what it is they do.

S1 reiterated during field interviewing that one area where he still remains true to his own identity as a journalist and reporter is taking the time when interviewing, ‘there’s a lot of listening in journalism’. Pavlik (2015) emphasises these views by outlining how a reporter on the ground can ‘can make observations, ask questions and conduct interviews that might yield critical information’ (p. 18). The shift in professional identity aligns to the convergence of multiple journalistic roles. From my observations and the field study interviews the identity of the reporter in the STV2 case study was being changed due to the expectation of newsgathering which is driven in part by the flexibility and empowerment provided by mobile journalism.

4.2.4 Technological convergence in Scottish Mojo

During field research with STV2 it became evident that advances in mobile technology are enabling a transition from traditional camera videography to mobile phone video journalism. This necessitates the development of journalists with flexible skillsets as S1 suggests, ‘willingness to learn things, the techniques I have come up with I haven’t had official training for’. Salzmann et al (2020) emphasised this during research conducted between 2017 and 2019, which explained that mobile journalists feel compelled to keep up with technological developments but are often expected to do so in their own time and without formal upskilling from employers. To practice in this Mojo space, the TV editor confirmed the importance of being, ‘aware of technological developments...keep abreast, be adapt, be fast moving’ (S3, 2018). Furthermore, the Mojo reporter explained that there was a new creative dimension to this new Mojo role involving technology, ‘tinkering about with bits of kit, experimentation...formal training may not work, what works for me may not work for another journalist’ (S1, 2018). Technologically, it is not about

understanding the hardware of the mobile smartphone, but also the multiple apps now available. S1 highlighted that when stating:

‘We have a constant WhatsApp group for our newsroom in Glasgow...you can constantly feed information in, for example use the second answer from this clip, here are the in-words, caption details, quick snap of a press release and everyone in the newsroom can see it’ (S1, 2018).

The STV2 reporters did not use tailored journalistic app services but instead made use of everyday mobile software already utilised by media consumers. S1 explained, ‘when you’re liaising with a crew, drop a pin in Google Maps. The STV2 journalists also made use of WhatsApp, the iPhone notes app and voice recording memo features on their mobile phones. This use of free common technological applications enhanced both the generation and circulation of local mobile news content. As S3 suggested, it is not just for video gathering and app usage but also for live streaming options, where ‘you can get the person and a phone to the location, you might not be able to get a huge truck. STV2 had chosen Dejero as their live streaming partner but also had to adjust to prioritising Facebook Live, utilizing mobile journalism for both audiences.

It also became evident that mobile technology takes social media away from a desktop or laptop computer and puts it in the palm of the reporters hand, which impacts on news planning, ‘mobile journalism affects how quickly I can get my news agenda, a lot of the time I am on the train, I have my mobile with me, I can look at other outlets, radio, people putting things on Twitter’ (S2, 2018). The production journalist explained that accessing social media through her phone not only acted as a way to gather news but also represented a key tool in sharing it to her audience, ‘through hashtags, trends, news accounts they trust’ (S2, 2018). The STV2 focus of blended mobile journalism with

awareness of traditional camera journalism techniques coupled with the use of freely available smartphone software increased the delivery of news and mobile content. The station used the smallest number of journalists to generate the largest volume of broadcast and social media material from what was an extensive news patch.

Despite severe weather and logistical issues, the field study provided a range of insights and an introduction to Mojo in its most stripped back form.

4.3 WDEF News 12: One of America's Oldest mojo newsrooms

WDEF News 12 was one of Tennessee's first TV stations signing on air in 1954 and employing the longest serving broadcaster in world history, Luther Masingill, the only journalist to be live on air (Radio) during the Pearl Harbour attack and also the 9/11 terrorism atrocity (TV) (Hull, 2012). It was also one of America's first local Mojo TV newsrooms implementing mobile journalism at the beginning of 2012.

Their experienced news team covered four states with 20 employees, 14 of which were practising mobile journalists. The Emmy-nominated news director (A1) introduced Mojo to his reporters and his station was one of the first American news outlets to switch completely to Dejero live streaming under the guidance of their chief engineer. Some of the key observations from my time with WDEF News 12 were that reporters had more ownership of their Mojo content in contrast with the STV staff who did not appear on TV more than 2/3 times per week, yet their content was used by other colleagues on a daily basis. Each WDEF 12 News reporter was broadcasting live at noon via their smartphones and often at 6pm in studio daily with a full Mojo made video package airing in that same bulletin or in the 7pm newscast. The technological aspects of this case study revolved much more around journalism-tailored apps, not the free software that comes on your

mobile smartphone that STV was maximising. There was also a bigger push for live broadcasting and social media content and a more focused awareness and engagement surrounding digital and social media output. There was a more pronounced emphasis on the changeability within journalism in this case study. The expert interviewees spoke at length about competition from other outlets, impartiality and bias within a changing news media landscape and explained how mobile journalism was aiding these changes but also proving to be disruptive (Heckman and Wihbey, 2019).

4.3.1 Ownership and audience: WDEF News 12

Unlike its British equivalent, American TV News is dominated by on-air personalities and sustained demand from audiences for constant live content. As WDEF News 12's Assignment Manager suggested, 'these folks need to know we have a quite a bit of power in TV, not so much in radio anymore, printed media is still having its problems' (A2, 2018). The link between the on-air journalistic talent and the audience is far more important in US markets. Meltzer (2010) refers to rapport and connection between what are termed news personalities and their viewers as being crucial to an American TV station's success. Smartphone technology is enhancing the development of these relationships according to WDEF newsroom leaders:

Well, it makes you accessible to the viewer, the reporters, whether it's a DM on Facebook, or tweet... whether it's even as simple as email, it makes the viewer feel they have direct access to a newsroom' (A1, 2018)

This rapport between viewer and journalist creates a significant amount of accountability, with the news reporters and station staff projecting a shared identity and news agenda but

journalists still retaining individuality surrounding the content they produce. The engagement from mobile and digital audiences manifest themselves in comments, shares and likes on content created and consumed on mobile devices, however the Web and Social Media producer explained during the fieldwork that non-TV news consumers create challenges, 'it's difficult, it's getting harder to figure out who the digital audience is' (A4, 2018). The same interviewee reiterated that there are now fewer journalists involved with content production, leaving the mobile journalist with more power but also more responsibility:

In the old way there used to be funnels, of going through the assignment desk, keeper of paper files... now we are finding the person who is reporting on the story, has much more control of the information they have... They are not as dependent on other, older people back at the station... they can do it all themselves (A4, 2018).

The autonomy and independence provided to reporters through Mojo can also be seen as isolating with the offloading of responsibility on to one journalist expected to already perform three roles in one. The web producer's colleague who works as an assignment manager acknowledged this concern, stating that, 'the pressure on people in our business to be precise, we will make mistakes' (A2, 2018). The web producer also suggested that the pace of audience consumption is increasing through direct to social media publishing of mobile news content by the reporters, 'it is much quicker, it can be done from the person in the field... quicker is not always better. The consumer is quicker in digesting it also' (A4, 2018).

While the news content belongs to the station the reporter is more invested in the individual stories they are assigned to daily as their face and voice are aligned to that package for their shift. This encourages specialism of news content and also an

understanding between the audience and certain Mojo's as to what type of stories they consistently cover and how the audience can support that specific newsbeat.

While the reporter has more ownership of this content and greater rapport and engagement with the mobile and digital audience the expectations placed on the Mojo reporter can be concerning. Through observations and interviews, I found that audiences were dictating and having more influence in the news agenda, this was due to more UGC being utilised and open dialogue between the content producer/consumer and journalist. It became apparent that American news audiences were less passive than in the Scottish field study, this is evidenced during the interview with the news director at WDEF news at the beginning and also in the latter parts of the PhD documentary who explains how audiences will dictate when and where they engage with content and how.

4.3.2 Mobile technology and social media impact

WDEF News 12 relied heavily on mobile journalism software and hardware, including the use of an ENPS scripting app for each reporter and Social News Desk, Hootsuite and Tweetdeck software to share social media content, Facebook and Periscope for live streaming and the Dejero app for content curating and live broadcasting. As A4 suggested, 'we have gone from technology getting bigger, larger satellite trucks, larger things, to getting smaller, with everything that you need in your hand'. The station sold their three satellite trucks between 2012 and 2014, as they transitioned all of their reporters to mobile journalism broadcasting. This was a cost-saving exercise too:

Satellite truck costs \$400,000, 450, you have to have CDL to drive it, it's huge, won't go through a tunnel, or that street because there are trees, you can do the same thing in a small hatchback and a thing the size of a laptop computer (A1, 2018)

WDEF News 12 were an early adopter of the aforementioned Dejero technology, which uses an app on a smartphone or mobile tablet similar to Facetime to provide a live video and audio feed directly back to the station. The TV station had six mobile devices and could funnel all of their broadcast feeds in at one time to their control room, then pull up these individual feeds from across their viewing area depending on where their mobile journalists were based, 'the Dejero technology is fantastic, bonded cellular live shots, the way it changes the ability, basically one person perform the function of 3 at any given time in the field' (A1, 2018).

The news director explained that when they transitioned to this pioneering technology in 2012 most of their neighbouring stations had no idea what they were doing, 'it changed the equation completely, we were made fun of by our competition, when we made that first step...we were ridiculed on social media' (A1, 2018). Initially, mobile journalism live streaming was not utilised by bigger US markets and was seen as a cost saving solution for smaller TV outlets but Dejero has since been accepted as a useful tool for coverage of elections and sports events by larger networks including the 2012 and 2016 Olympic Games (Teves, 2016). From a software standpoint, WDEF News 12 reporters use ENPS script writing apps to file their copy and also to share video content internally through their Dejero apps back to the news outlet. Social media journalism is also a primary concern for content generation with all staff sharing content via the paid mobile app service, Social News Desk, 'when picking things for social media, you have to know what people will like... what will go really with our viewers' (A3, 2018).

The station has had a number of packages and clips go viral with the Mojo gathering the content via smartphone. The anchors produce Facebook Lives before each main TV broadcast to gain a closer understanding of their audience's interests and needs. This

approach of blending terrestrial TV and social media content using mobile journalism is discussed by Cameron and Geidner (2014) who explain that dual viewing and interactivity are crucial to retain audiences in American television news, ‘be you, be the person they don't get to see on TV, use a 15-minute Facebook live to get to know to the viewer and they get to know you’ (A3, 2018).

A3 added that this affinity with her social media audience through mobile technology has led to a rise in user-generated content, ‘battling social media, navigate it in crisis, learning how to get to whose there, we had to find out what was happening in the mall but from in your newsroom’. The news director highlighted that due to mobile journalism and social media, news managers can now keep abreast of how other stations are covering stories, ‘you monitor your competition more easily’ (A1, 2018). The Mojo (A3) stressed that their reliance on mobile phone technology is constant and mobile journalism has proven revolutionary in their newsroom, ‘don’t think this is little steps, our iPhone video is sometimes the only video that we have’ (A3, 2018).

Mobile technology and mobile journalism practice was the norm for WDEF during the field research in April 2018. Reporters worked consistently to push content to social media, delivering live feeds, packaging and gathering extra clips while the versatility of their mobile smartphones all played a role. The sheer volume of stories covered would not have been possible using a camera, SD card, a desktop editing system and a satellite truck as evidenced in Tables 3 and 4. Posetti (2018), in her UNESCO report, highlighted the extensive workload that mobile journalism has facilitated for each reporter and this was apparent through research observations at WDEF News12. However, despite the ages of their reporters being mostly under 30 and the management staff a generation or two older,

both grasped the technical and editorial value of mobile journalism and practised it daily despite increased expectations.

4.3.3 Instability in a mobile journalism age

‘We are on a precipice of major change’ (A4, 2018)

The WDEF News 12 web producer, news director and assignment manager raised a number of concerns about the pressures the mobile and digital media world is placing their newsroom under. As the news director suggested, ‘the internet and the rise of outlets like MSNBC, Fox News, all of that has led people to live in a bubble, where they only find that which agrees with what they already know, that’s not healthy, you have to hear different voices, hear all sides’ (A1, 2018). He further detailed that despite their efforts to satisfy the expectations of journalism standards and audience needs, they often go unappreciated and respected, ‘audiences don’t often differentiate between national and local news, the people in their own communities’ (A1, 2018). Further to this, he explained that all journalism whether mobile, print or digital will veer towards the needs of audiences in the coming decade:

On demand, we are spoilt, we want it when we want it, as we get further along with technology, streaming... you already login when you want, there is no longer appointment viewing at 6pm or 6.30 (A1, 2018).

The news director suggested that this transition was due to technological change, with news delivered to the palm of his audience’s hand. It was apparent from observations that his team chose the digital first approach, which marked a change from the newsgathering

philosophy of STV2. Both methods were about speed of content delivery but for the American outlet it weighed more heavily on their digital output despite being a TV news station and not a social media or web journalism outlet, 'compare numbers for late news, lifestyles have changed' (A1, 2018). The news director also warned that audience input will grow as the digitalisation of news progresses:

In the long term you are going to have to just produce content as a news organisation and put it out there, the viewer is going to say okay, this is the line-up of stories I want to see (A1, 2018).

His concerns are influenced by the transition to mobile journalism. The web producer affirmed that there has been a lot of change, often too quickly, 'there needs to be someone in the chain who asks not how something could be done, but whether something should be done' (A4, 2018). He suggests the removal of more assignment manager roles and chain of commands within newsrooms can have some ethical consequences, which have come about due to cost saving and mobile journalism:

There are a lot of things that are getting out that should not have been reported, names of victims, the reporter is not always the best person to do that, it's helpful to have someone back at the station asking the other questions, we may want to protect the family in this situation (A4, April 2018).

He suggested that while mobile journalism technical skills are important amongst their reporters, journalism values and morals remain still key, 'bottom line is we are more dependent on younger people to use this technology, they need to be taught the old stuff, but they often don't know it to begin with' (A4, 2018). It is not just the younger

journalists that the web producer highlighted concerns with, but also with the broadcast media landscape in North America:

Smaller stations are trying to retain their independence, what we are feeling now from the people who are consuming our news in the US is that they don't want the unbiased viewpoint of the news, they say they do but by their feedback they don't, they want news that is friendly to their take on the world, that's been coming for a while, it's become more severe with the Trump administration (A4, April 2018).

His worry is that mobile journalism, while empowering audiences and reporters to provide more content and quicker, could lead journalism back to the 1960s with biased reporting and less editorial consideration for journalism output, 'Newspapers were published with a political viewpoint, that's where we are going in local TV' (A4, 2018).

The field research week with WDEF News 12 provided significant insights into the positive and negative impacts mobile journalism implementation can have on a newsroom. The blended approach of traditional and mobile in Scotland coupled with a slower pace of social and live output did not present the same number of concerns and issues. These included pressured mobile journalists aiming to satisfy online and social media audiences while also having to fulfil TV broadcast demands. The over reliance of News 12 on their mobile journalists to deliver content with significant daily demands made me reflect on how little traditional TV reporters (who do not shoot or edit) did in contrast. WDEF are empowering their journalists with mobile technology, but they are also removing their ability to fully analyse the content they are creating.

Following this field work which highlighted some of the opportunities and threats that mobile journalism creates, the next case site in India was a late adopter but with innovation to the fore.

4.4 NDTV and Hop Live: India's mobile station

NDTV is one of India's first privately owned TV networks (Safi, 2017), with a viewer reach of 60 million people. The TV station was founded in 1988 by Dr. Prannoy Roy and his wife Radhika. Since 2017, they have altered their workflow, transitioning their 75 reporters to mobile journalism. I visited the organisation in April 2019 during one of their most demanding news cycles, the Indian general election. The rationale behind experiencing mobile journalism at NDTV lay in three key areas. Primarily, they are a major international news organisation who have chosen to adopt Mojo and have significant experience. Secondary to this is their pioneering use of vertical live streaming and shooting to create a millennial-only video news channel called Hop Live, the world's first. Finally, the demanding news agenda in late April and early May 2019 offered a window into one of the world's mobile journalism leaders during peak output, operating at full capacity. The key themes and insights that emerged from this field study include technological impact, role convergence and finally my reflections on the Mojo impact on journalistic identity.

4.4.1 Mobile journalism transition and implementation

Two years prior to my arrival at NDTV, Samsung released the S8+ smartphone. This was a pivotal moment for management at the station led by their executive producer, 'the S8+ were amazing phones we gave them out to all our reporters' (I3, 2019). However, transitioning from traditional broadcast journalism to mobile created a series of

challenges for producers and reporters, ‘it was very difficult initially, hard to get the footage to the station from a remote location’ (I3, 2019).

The executive producer tried to address this logistical and infrastructure-based problem by providing a range of phone network options with some of his reporters operating across the Asian sub-continent, ‘two sim cards from two different cell phone operators, a MiFi device with a third operator’ (I3, 2019). Once the content was created and the ability to share the mobile video supported via diverse phone networks, the files themselves became a problem when sent from the field-based Mojo reporters back to the TV station, ‘When mobiles came we were a little uncomfortable, the whole workflow changed...now the workflow was everything, we uploaded to cloud space, naming convention was a problem’ (I4, 2019).

The production lead also discovered that the names of the files and their formats created numerous difficulties for a station that had worked previously with satellite feeds since its inception, ‘the file format became a big issue, we had to import the files, there are a lot of apps which shoot in Pal 25FPS, most of the cameras have 30FPS, we were broadcasting in 25FPS... sync outs, dropped frames...the file formats were an issue, but there are more codecs now’ (I4, 2019). The executive producer tasked his engineers with the unique challenge of creating their own TV station content management cloud-based system for all of their Mojos to deliver consistent and accessible video files to newsroom staff:

They made a small utility on the web that provide logins to all the reporters, so now on location one can just login, select files on the phone, automatically transferred via the cloud to our NDTV servers. The moment the footage comes here, an automated email goes to the output department and producers concerned and it’s on air in no time (I3, 2019).

The revolutionary system acts as a journalistic Google Drive that enables all newsroom employees to share and access NDTV mobile video content. Having three phone networks equips the reporters to get the content off their devices with the NDTV Mojo app and broadcast their live feeds regardless of infrastructural restrictions. The production lead outlined that this system, which also archives the video content, is more flexible than satellite TV broadcasting, with ‘much more options to play around with the footage, as satellite feeds were limited with the cost...it was there in the cloud, if I want to use any other clip later, I could just pull it again’ (I4, 2019).

Both the station managers described how the 4k and HD video from Samsung camera phones which is then compressed down, enhances their viewers experience, ‘the quality of footage is amazing, we are shooting on 4k and HD... as a channel we are standard definition, so rich in colours and clarity’ (I3, 2019) and ‘the quality of the pictures looks way better’ (I4, 2019).

For their lead Mojo correspondent, along with other NDTV reporters, the focus is on gathering clips, interviews and providing live outside broadcasts (OBs). The Mojo reporters deliver the content to the production lead and his editors via the NDTV-created app cloud-based utility, those editors then trim the content, adjust any video or audio issues and turn them, in some cases into short TV news packages. This is an example based on observations during fieldwork of a Mojo altered workflow designed to facilitate mobile journalism production and distribution. The expectation on reporters is to gather the content and pass it over and remain available for live broadcasts and two-ways with the studio presenters. This dynamic differs from that of STV where reporters were expected to package or compile reports a few times a week but not consistently and where live reporting was not a regular occurrence. In America, live reporting and packaging

expectations were placed daily on all reporters but in India the packaging roles were passed off to a team of 12 separate in-house video editors as evidenced in Tables 3 and 4. This altered the Mojo workload, allowing the reporter to focus more on their live output and style of delivery.

During interview, the correspondent (I2) explained this autonomy leads to more freedom to solo broadcast live, empowering the reporter, 'there are some meetings that are taboo for camera but you can have your phone anywhere, I can do OBs from anywhere' (I2, 2019). However, both the production lead and executive producer also outlined the limitations of mobile journalism in great detail, having overseen its implementation and emergence. First, they detailed audio concerns, 'do the homework first, find out, audio is a major issue, the microphone that works on mobiles are not good enough, have the devices that convert audio acceptable' (I3, 2019). Second, they discussed shooting issues, 'there are limitations regarding framing, you have to be close to the subjects, for news it works, for features it's difficult' (I4, 2019). Finally, there are zooming problems, 'we have been using mobile phones for almost 2 years now, this technology is always developing, the cameras are better, the zoom is lacking to some extent... that's one field where I feel we are still waiting...for example, a panel discussion' (I3, 2019).

The constant expectations to keep developing, upskilling and moving with technological and audience demands are being addressed by NDTV, however this contrasts with both the views of Goggin (2015) and Erdal et al (2019) who highlight that budget cuts have led to less innovation, research and development by TV news organisations, (p. 173). As the production lead suggests, 'it's changing every day, much faster than I could ever have imagined' (I4, 2019).

Despite the technical drawbacks, as part of this smartphone led technological evolution,

the station created a vertical live streaming channel for millennials called Hop Live. The app and live output is shot and broadcast vertically with dedicated lifestyle and entertainment shows produced and presented by mobile journalists predominately under the age of 30. 'since we are shooting on phones for news, why can't we shoot for a vertical audience, the world's first lifestyle, digital channel in vertical' (I3, 2019).

This is not the only way the technology is being utilized in a more creative and pioneering way. NDTV have also removed a number of traditional mounted studio cameras and replaced them with Samsung Galaxy phones and connected their respective autocues beneath them. This has generated economic benefits and delivered a higher resolution live studio feed. The station have a business partnership with Samsung who cater and support mobile journalism output, in return, new devices are delivered consistently to the newsroom with their factory located within 50 miles of the station. Samsung receive on screen recognition for their mobile journalism relationship through advertising and marketing.

By creating their own file transfer system, the station bypasses the need to use Google Drive, Dejero or Dropbox or pay for extra storage space and can internally archive their own content. Their newsroom leaders explained that their push to Mojo was influenced by the rise in smartphone mobile usage in India coupled with the lack of TV, laptop and desktop computer purchases. Kaka (2019) reiterates this, stating that almost 1 in 4 Indians are smartphone users, which equates to almost 328 million people. Ericsson's June 2019 review on global phone usage found that Indians use more data per device than any other nation in the world at 9.8gb a month. Further to this, India is now a global leader in mobile app development and phone manufacturing (Mahoney, 2020). It seems this transition to mobile journalism is a journalistic shift and one influenced by societal,

economic and manufacturing developments. These same factors, societal and economic, were highlighted by Willig (2013) when he explained what a second wave of journalism ethnographic research would be influenced by. The NDTV newsroom recognized that audiences were empowered through mobile phone use and therefore while often unable to afford a computer or TV could own a simple inexpensive android smartphone.

4.4.2 Convergence of roles and mojo uses

The convergence of reporter and cameraman due to mobile journalism is for the following reasons 'economic, competition, technology, experimentation' (I1, 2019). The mobile journalist explained that these are the four key drivers that have influenced convergence in their New Delhi newsroom. Jamil (2019) writing about mobile journalism influence in Asian TV stations cites similar motives for Mojo adoption. Zafra (2014) refers to American studies of media convergence and highlights that quality of journalism can be affected when newsrooms are merged with roles and duties changed. However, Zafra (2014) also details that the Tampa Media General merger in 2000 between online, print and TV reporters enhanced pooling of resources and newsroom employees welcomed the transition.

The combining of roles through mobile journalism is supported by NDTV, 'they feel so enabled, they are out on their own, they have a phone a selfie stick, don't even need a tripod, they are shooting HD 4K' (I3, 2019). For the production management the convergence happened quickly, 'We took a phone, that's an end to the camera' (I4, 2019). Their on-air staff further detailed how mobile journalism also enhances social media content, 'People come to online first, then they reach out for TV...you can scan what's trending online, twitter, connect with your sources' (I2, 2019).

However, it is not just news outlets that are seeing the value of mobile journalism in India, during the election coverage their Mojo staff also witnessed political parties embracing the technology for social media gain and becoming their own content creators, ‘the BJP had mastered the art of social media to send out its narrative through new media’ (I1, 2019). He referred to political parties in India as having a war room of social media content and resources. At Hop Live a younger generation of mobile-only journalists believe non-political user generated content is also altering the dynamic between reporter and viewer, ‘now everyone has a screen with them, citizen reporting has gone up, people are concerned and now they have a way to share or show what happened to them’ (I6, 2019). She concluded that the impact of mobile journalism does not restrict their audience reach, ‘with digital the medium opens up to the world, it’s more fast paced’ (I6, 2019).

While smartphones are used to find, gather, create and share news at all four case studies it is only at NDTV they are used as studio cameras. This is, however, not the only way NDTV has explored how smartphone technology can be utilized innovatively despite being late adopters. Other departments within the TV station including HR are tapping into the phone’s potential. Each phone has a unique staff login built into it, which in turn can be utilized to record journalist expenses, travel time and data costs. The staff smartphones are also designed to deliver instant message requests for a specialist ride-sharing taxi app service to bring reporters to and from the scenes of breaking news. This unique and dedicated usage of mobile phones stretches far beyond the basic mobile journalism practices seen in other case sites, with NDTV devices providing monitoring, support and accountability functions. They deliver their mobile phone led studio output to 121 countries in two languages across nine channels, 24 hours a day.

While the shooter and reporter roles have converged at NDTV their workflow of having

dedicated editors, output editors, assignment managers and an array of producers and gatekeepers still demonstrates a more traditional structure, albeit utilizing mobile phone technology for live reporting and content gathering as part of their news cycle.

4.4.3 Identity, live on air

NDTV reporters are not expected to deliver their own edited video packages, this contrasts with both STV and WDEF News 12, the latter of which places this expectation on mobile journalists daily. NDTV reporters, however, have a larger news content gathering area because New Delhi has a population of 18 million and NDTV cover breaking stories both for the city, greater region and across other parts of India and Asia, ‘we don't restrict ourselves when shooting... we go all over India’ (I7, 2019). My observations highlight that the focus NDTV has on live reporting gives their mobile journalists more airtime and a greater chance of bringing their individualistic style and journalistic identity to the fore, enabled by Mojo. Their on-air staff primarily focus on content gathering and live reporting but not on editing, which further allows mobile journalists to finesse delivery and on camera presentation as well as social media output, ‘it's up to us regain trust and credibility with great coverage, great intellectual news, the facts, we have to work harder’ (I5, 2019).

This newsgathering approach allows journalist's space and time to conduct in depth reporting and political investigations, ‘they take time to spin whatever narrative, we need time to unspin them, that takes time, work harder, work faster, triple check our facts’ (I1, 2019). At Hop Live the news distribution approach is one that facilitates a younger more mobile engaged social media focused audience. The mobile news audience is growing in India and NDTV are capitalising on it, ‘our audience is millennials, we have recently over 10 million views, we launched in October, that is a fair number’ (I7, 2019). The

accessibility and style of presenting and reporting to engage youth audiences is summed up by a Hop Live anchor, ‘delivering the news but not in a newsy style’, (15, 2019).

The TV producers at Hop Live engage directly with social media audiences and broadcast to Instagram on a daily basis. They use smartphones to gather their content and broadcast it. The branding of the station, the identity and awareness of the journalistic staff and the consistency of content is focused around new media, bloggers, vloggers and social media stars. These interviewees are utilized as guests and for feature content. While Hop Live covered the 2019 election, it was done in a way that was more succinct, accessible and relatable to a younger audience of often first-time voters viewing their content on Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube demonstrating audience awareness and a digital media focus.

NDTV and Hop Live showed mobile journalism practice in a series of innovative ways. Their interviews provided technical insights coupled with access to both of their newsrooms and reporters in the field providing deeper insights into how this Asian news outlet functions. They adapted their use of existing technology to deliver to their audience needs and changing expectations in innovative ways despite not being early adopters.

4.5 Léman Bleu: the mobile-only newsroom

During the summer of 2015, Léman Bleu in Geneva made headlines for trialling a mobile only newsroom in the heart of Europe. What followed was a media and academic spotlight that has led to them becoming a hub for new media knowledge exchange and mobile journalism training, with reporters travelling from as far away as Japan and America to observe their newsroom in action. In May 2019, I spent a week with their team. A veteran Mojo on staff shared his views regarding mobile journalism and its

limitations as well as their director of news and his team of news and sports reporters. The themes that emerged from this case include technological challenges, autonomy and perfectionism.

4.5.1 Mobile technology: a double-edged sword

Léman Bleu did not remain a mobile journalism-only news organization after the summer of 2015 but instead gave their reporters the option to choose the device that worked best for them on an individual basis. However, a significant number of reporters not only used Mojo but some had never learned or used anything else due to the age and background of most of their staff, ‘I myself am a product of mobile journalism’ (G3, 2019). The initial rationale behind mobile journalism implementation was a simple one, weight, ‘they were not wanting to go in the field, very tired, enough weight of the material too heavy for them, I decided to put some lightness and quickness into this, let’s go iPhone, let’s go smartphone’ (G1, 2019).

Despite the freedom the smaller mobile equipment provided, Léman Bleu encountered a number of issues during the early stages of the 2015 mobile journalism transition, including, ‘technical problems, connectivity, 4G was not so good, in crowded places, bad connectivity, we had to find always solutions, it was quite challenging, we put energy in to finding solutions’ (G1, 2019). However, for their veteran Mojo this 2015 summer trial was a positive shift despite the technological limitations:

It was a very exciting period, for us we needed some software and hardware, cameras and all that, he decided to buy us like this [iPhone], the material you have, it was the summer, the summer is unbelievable, the light was nice, the weather was nice, we started to make some films, actuality (G5, 2019)

After this summer, some reporters remained as sole Mojo practitioners, but others did not. The newsroom management believed a fusion of the two newsgathering approaches worked best, ‘when we mix broadcast cameras and smartphones, we do both at the same time, we can get some power’ (G1, 2019). For other Léman Bleu reporters, mobile journalism enabled them to conduct challenging interviews, ‘interview in her place at home, someone who is not used to be filmed, you can go closer to them, they are not so shy’ (G6, 2019). The director of news believed that Mojo’s primary benefit is in relation to speed, ‘with breaking news, when it burns (fires), accidents, we can go very quick and be connected, we gained reactivity and quickness’ (G1, 2019). However, Mojo has also helped Léman Bleu expand their digital audience. The station now has TV viewers, social media followers and website readers, ‘we want to target younger people, we want to capture their attention, we try and do something catchy for social media, do a Facebook live, Instagram or on Twitter’ (G3, 2019) with ‘more focused people who will not watch long videos but only the talking points that matter to them’ (G2, 2019).

However, the Léman Bleu Mojo reporters also identify technical restrictions with iPhones that affect content gathering:

Any camera or iPhone with the materials, they have limits, with a camera you have limits, this is not light, the phone technology is not so good, you cannot do good things you cannot make beautiful image, beautiful pictures, two, three years the technology will be so nice for pictures at night, the zoom is not so good now, you cannot make great images, many times it’s night when I do things, this is not so well, there is no zoom’ (G5, 2019).

When you go in a place that is too dark, that you didn’t expect, then it’s dark, with smartphone you are not able to film (G6, 2019).

The NDTV management team highlighted similar issues, during their mobile journalism implementation phase. In contrast, however, Léman Bleu produced very little live news journalistic content, with deadlines less rigid and the ‘empty chairs’ in newsrooms that Deuze (2019) warned against not apparent compared to the other case studies. The station utilizes the streaming software LiveU when delivering outside broadcasts and produced social media broadcasts via Facebook live.

4.5.2 Autonomy and freedom in Swiss mojo

Each Léman Bleu Mojo outlined how their drive and self-motivation enabled them to work without interference from news managers, creating an atmosphere of newsroom autonomy, ‘they do all here, film, edit, put the material on social media, they put the stuff on websites, very challenging every day, they do all of the production chain’ (G1, 2019).

Some of their staff who are slightly older than the other reporters worked at night and often on their own creating long form video shows and magazine features, ‘I am not on stage (Studio), this is not my part, my part is to be in the field, so I like to be with people and where there’s some action’ (G5, 2019). The autonomy granted by the news director to his reporters to use any device they chose to record video was observed on multiple occasions during fieldwork. He stepped back and allowed the reporters the space to be creative with their subject material and their own use of smartphone technology. He explained that he is also attempting to impart his newsgathering philosophy to the Léman Bleu audience whom he is now training as mobile journalists through workshops and classes:

We see that video image is kind of democratizing, everyone shoots and edits, we have more experience, we can teach the people. We can give them new skills, we create

communities and these communities give us back what we give them (G1, 2019).

This two-way communication and support for UGC is explored by Bivens (2008) and Burum (2014) while cautioned against by Fuchs (2008, 2010, 2014) and Richardson (2020). The news director believes if he can transition his audience into citizen journalists and mobile content creators his newsroom in turn will benefit and not be left behind, ‘we have ONGs, sports clubs to shoot, edit, then they shoot, edit and then they bring it back, we are creating a modern network of user generated content’ (G1, 2019). He plans to provide autonomy to his viewership and remove the boundary between the reporter and the viewer, ‘we have expertise, we teach, they give us back, we have a position, we create centrality, we are now like Facebook, the people send us their content’ (G1, 2019). The expansion of Léman Bleu’s user generated network has proven fruitful for sports reporting and management believe the smartest way to sustain TV journalism is to devolve it and share the newsgathering responsibility:

We still have to be there to make some qualitative production, we have to invent the future, that's what we are doing, we make some technical changes, we try to reinvent our production, we have to capture the public where it is, we will take our audience with us, this is our main challenge (G1, 2019).

While other media organisations referenced both in this study and the literature review have explained they are influenced by audience needs, Léman Bleu are reversing this trend by accepting different audiences have different expectations but also getting those same audiences to make content for them. This in turn affects journalistic identity, with news outlets giving airtime and parity to citizen journalism content when needed to help address demands and expectations.

4.5.3 Perfectionism in reporting

Each of the interviewees spoke passionately about their desire to do their best for their employer and their audiences, ‘we try to adapt, it’s always moving, it’s hard to keep track of all the different changes, we try our best to satisfy our audience that is older on TV and younger on social media’ (G2, 2019). This mindset of constant improvement, efficiency and the desire to aim for perfection is visible in the output of the organization, which has a feature focus, providing in-depth, balanced reporting with high production values. ‘to keep our audience with us, we have to try and be good everywhere in this new world, in this content consumption’ (G1, 2019). Their Mojos suggested that news should be happy and uplifting where possible ‘show in Geneva more positive news, to some people Geneva is dead, it’s boring, to show [Them] that things exist’ (G6, 2019). The station did not operate seven days a week and there was no live Sunday broadcast output. It was apparent the pace and demands of the newsroom are significantly less and content is delivered at a slower pace than the other three case sites as visible in tables 3 and 4, while their newsroom is staffed by progressive multi-skilled primarily female reporters under the age of 30. Through this slower news agenda, the reporters aim for balance and impartiality. Léman Bleu encourages objectivity and fact checking for all their broadcast and social media content. This ethical journalism news flow is supported by the Poynter institute (Scanlan, 2003) and referred to by both Deuze (2005) and Kovach and Rosenstiel (2001).

The aesthetics of their output and the finessing within news production remain paramount. Due to only having 30 minutes of live TV news a day the mobile and broadcast journalists are given the autonomy, the time and the tools to create high value news content without the same pressures of other mobile journalists (Ornrebring, 2010).

4.6 Ethical journalism for mobile media practitioners

The ethics of practice-based journalism is affected by the rise of mobile technology (Burger and Fitzgerald, 2019). This is due to a Mojo-enabled shift whereby citizen journalists and politicians no longer require traditional broadcast outlets to share ‘ready-made-home-made’ content and can bypass traditional media and engage directly with smartphone enabled digital audiences without journalistic codes of conduct or standards. The ethical issues which mobile journalism creates were also evident during the fieldwork stage of this study. A number of journalists operating independently in the field had to make sensitive editorial and ethical decisions without support. The risk this creates was highlighted by the web producer at WDEF News 12, when mobile reporters are in the field and away from the newsroom and refer to ‘names of victims’. WDEF News 12 and NDTV staff cautioned against political impact in media production.

Deuze (2005) explains that journalists see themselves not as a profession but as an ideology. Vos and Hanitzsch (2017) referred to journalistic identity as a belief system that was previously influenced by colleagues and newsroom values. These values and beliefs were imparted in person with reporters surrounded by experienced colleagues prior to the digitalization of media and decentralisation of newsrooms. My fieldwork enquiries highlighted that each journalist had their own code of ethics that aligned to their broadcast style and storytelling skillset influenced in part by their employer, society and culture. These were formed primarily on their own drawing from past experiences, if they had them, the mobile journalists did not have a support system in place, a videographer or an experienced on-site producer to consult with. This self-policing and ethical decision-making was highlighted by Sjovaag (2011). The diverse social settings for each fieldwork site presented contrasting ethical approaches to newsgathering with fact checking to the

fore for the stations that engaged more with critical social media audiences and political coverage (Thurman, 2018).

4.7 Conclusion

All four case studies presented a range of rationales and insights into the implementation and impact of mobile journalism. The economic benefits of leaving satellite broadcasting behind influenced management in each case study. Audience expectations and demands also played a key role when influencing the adoption of Mojo and which mediums were given precedence. Findings from Léman Bleu and WDEF News 12, in particular, demonstrated that both organisations valued their digital audiences and sought to engage directly with them and harness their UGC potential.

The news managers from all four outlets heralded the live broadcasting options available to them because of developments in Mojo, especially how efficient and autonomous it made their staff. While News 12, STV2 and Léman Bleu all had similar staffing numbers the mobile content return from the main reporters for STV and Léman Bleu was much lower than that of the American TV station. The European mobile journalists delivered less news content, social media output and fewer live broadcasts than News 12 mobile journalists. The American outlet, with its challenging workflow trying to satisfy social and digital audiences as well as TV viewers, was also more reliant on Mojo with all live reports produced by smartphone devices.

Geographical distinctions were also evident. In India, despite having a comparable number of video shoots and live reports over a five-day working week, their reporters did not have to package video news content. These findings show that Mojo employees at NDTV and Léman Bleu were provided with more time and space to finesse and hone

their on-air deliveries. The findings also demonstrated that WDEF News 12 employees were working harder than the other outlets but in doing so were also more reliant on smartphones, since their Mojo transition in 2012. This smartphone reliance presented greater versatility, work volume and autonomy but put mobile journalists at risk with fewer gatekeepers of information and support networks.

In the forthcoming analysis chapter, I evaluate the primary findings from each case site in relation to the digital and mobile journalism landscape while building on the key debates brought through from relevant literature.

Chapter 5: Mobile Journalism Evaluated

This chapter explores how the findings generated from the practice-based study help generate new research insights in the field of mobile journalism. This study sought to investigate the extent to which mobile journalism has been a reactionary and disruptive force within journalism, influenced by technological, social and economic factors.

Through analysing the study findings, I evidence the nature, extent and effect of Mojo influence from each case study site and present similarities and differences in practice. Furthermore, I demonstrate that Mojo presents a range of opportunities but also threats to journalistic identity.

5.1 Nature, extent and effect of mobile journalism

We are living in a mobile-influenced world (Xu, 2016) and the extent to which technological developments have transformed our daily lives is apparent through communication, consumerism, transport, healthcare and media consumption. The OFCOM Digital News Report of 2018, reflecting on changes since 2008, suggested that a combination of the rise of social media apps, enhancement of WIFI and 4G technology and the evolution of smartphones have all influenced changes in how and where audiences access news. From 2008, through the Mojo emergence in 2012 and up until this study began in 2018, there has been an internet-first approach to news distribution (Meijer, 2014) and mobile journalism has enhanced and accelerated that process. Based on findings from this study these arguments can be supported.

Murphy (2020) and the Reuters Institute report *A Decade of Dependency* suggest that the economic crash of 2008 led to newsrooms having to cut back and adjust staffing numbers

and find a solution to keep broadcasting. Editors and news managers began to see the value of smartphones in aiding newsgathering in this more fiscally-restrictive decade. Evidence from this study suggests that the mobile journalism transition was ‘reactionary’ (R1, 2019) as journalism responded to these economic problems and changing audience needs only when it became apparent that as an industry it had to adapt (Wu, Tandoc, Salmon, 2019).

Upon reviewing both the literature and interviewee insights, the primary driver of Mojo adoption was economic, this argument is also supported from the academy (Perez and Cremadas, 2014; Albeanu, 2017). While social trends, influence of the ‘big five’ technology corporations and audience demands all played a role in the rise of Mojo, cost cutting forced the hand of news organisations to adapt or face being left behind. This study has shown that these social trends included the shift to a more mobile society (Westlund, 2013), with enhanced internet infrastructure both in Global North and in Global South nations (Couldry, 2019). Coupled to this were advances made in smartphone technology, with better cameras, live streaming capabilities, free and accessible apps and social media platforms influencing the rolling 24-hour news cycle accessible beyond the parameters of newspaper print rounds or TV schedules (Mohammedsalih 2017; Drula 2014).

All four case studies transitioned to what they viewed as cheaper alternatives to maintain their broadcast output. Mojo was a bandage that allowed broadcast journalism to continue during a period of dwindling advertising revenues, job cuts and economic instability. News organisations utilised already available personal smartphone technologies and repurposed them for industrial needs. During the decade before this study commenced, the rise in social media platforms and improvement in internet infrastructure equipped one

third of the world's population with smartphones (Silver, 2019) and this research has demonstrated that mobile journalism has become both an accepted form of media creation and a medium for content distribution in both developed and developing world newsrooms.

Each of the four case studies revealed, to different degrees, the effect of mobile journalism on news output. In Scotland, STV2 adopted a blended approach utilising traditional video journalism cameras and Mojo which was similar to WDEF News 12 in the US, who used a combination of both technologies but relied on Mojo for live broadcasting output. The Indian and Swiss case studies demonstrated greater Mojo reliance for all aspects of content gathering and distribution, albeit the Indian news operation had a much more significant live broadcasting focus. Each of the cases pointed to mobile-aware newsrooms with staff of all ages engaged in some form of Mojo practice. For example, Léman Bleu's management explained that the story being covered dictated the technology required. This unique approach also reduced pressures on staff to alter their workflow and upskill (Ornebring, 2010). However, this was not the case in other outlets with WDEF News 12 prioritising Mojo hires and STV2 adopting a Mojo first approach. WDEF News 12 were the first case study to move to Mojo in 2012, Léman Bleu in 2015 and STV and NDTV in 2017, signifying that the mobile adoption has accelerated over the last decade, triggered by the economic needs of the stations, societal influences, including enhanced internet infrastructure and technological trends and demands.

Evidence from this study also suggests that mobile journalism has proven to be a disruptive influence on journalism similar to the key arguments made by Heckman and Wihbey (2019). Further to this Mojo has been adopted without question or query by news

managers while it has in turn altered workflows and transformed newsroom dynamics and journalistic roles, evidenced across all four case studies. There are a number of common ways that smartphone technology is being utilised beneficially to expand content dissemination and reach a range of audiences, despite the cultural, economic and societal differences of each case site.

5.2 Mojo opportunities

A key benefit to switching to Mojo for all four case studies was the use of smartphones for live broadcasting. Dejero and Live U apps and social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and Periscope were utilised across each setting. Traditional broadcast cameras were unable to deliver the same volume of broadcasts or in as accessible a manner direct to digital and mobile audiences. WDEF News12 and NDTV had challenging live broadcasting agendas with demanding expectations placed on reporters. Léman Bleu and STV2 had fewer live reports working towards flexible deadlines and less strenuous remote broadcasting demands (Rottwilm, 2014). WDEF News 12 preceded TV broadcasts with social media live streams demonstrating a fusion of both approaches and NDTV pioneered a streaming only news service for younger mobile platform viewers. A1 referred to the live broadcasting transition due to ‘appointment viewing’ no longer taking precedence for US audiences.

Through transitioning to a form of Mojo, all four news outlets were also able to utilise UGC and engage with their audiences directly. STV mentioned this in relation to live weather coverage and NDTV explained that they experienced similar trends but with political reporting. Through wider participation from audiences, social media’s role for each news organisation provided their newsroom with a more open dialogue than with previously passive TV viewers.

Mobile journalism also provided more autonomy and independence for journalists as they were no longer reliant on teams of people and given more editorial freedom to make key decisions regarding content gathering, production and distribution (Bock, 2012).

Previously, rigid and restrictive work practices and larger staffed newsrooms left journalists performing only one function or task. While the initial solution Mojo presented became a more accepted norm from 2012 onwards, it also presented an array of challenges for news outlets.

5.3 Mobile journalism a disruptive solution

When analysing and reflecting on the case study insights it is important to recognise the influence of the social and cultural contexts affecting each case study and their adoption of Mojo. The frenetic chaos of India and the incessant news demands of American audiences were echoed in the respective ways in which Indian and US mobile journalism was created and distributed in their respective nations and markets. Swiss society, with high employment, low crime and a calm and slower pace of life influenced the thought provoking and balanced reporting of *Léman Bleu*. In Scotland, the desire to do more with less and be adaptable was more apparent. STV staff were overworked products as well as reporters of their news patch. In this case, mobile journalism reinforced Fuchs (2010, 2014) view that a digital society is creating cogs in a media machine that enriches the establishment and wealthy corporations. This view was one I would have dismissed prior to this study, as a product of Mojo I rarely questioned or queried practices or the impact it had on colleagues within the media sphere.

In each case, Mojo also facilitated a social media focus and encouraged audiences to participate in the news agenda. However, the risks of unverified citizen journalism content, political bias and lack of newsroom gatekeepers to authenticate content all

presented major threats to the core principles of journalism (Kovach and Rosenstiel, 2001; Mohammedsalih, 2017). The importance of objectivity and balance are diluted with mobile journalism facilitating avenues for fake news, including a greater risk in developing world media markets. The exploitation of citizen journalism and user generated content can also impact on impartiality for vulnerable poorer and rural audiences outside of Global North media markets reliant on private broadcasters (Couldry, 2019; Udupa, 2018).

Through having web, social media and TV audiences, all four case sites were coming under increasing pressure to satisfy growing and varied audiences with less staff. This, in turn, led to a lack of ownership of content in places. For example, journalistic identity and the role expectations at STV were getting lost due to excessive demands. Both American and Indian audiences expected breaking news content available on all platforms and mediums while *Léman Bleu* differed to the other stations with their attention to detail, focus on balance and perfectionism with slower and less intense news cycles. While some media academics have contested that mobile journalism and slow journalism conflict (Drok and Hermans, 2016), with the former facilitating speed of bite size news and the latter appealing to older audiences, *Léman Bleu*'s approach utilises smartphone technology in a more pronounced and considered way. Slow journalism is a more in depth and balanced approach to content production, which aims to improve journalistic quality while giving a reader or audience a more rounded picture and not prioritize advertising revenues, (Dowling, 2016). Dowling also refers to how slow journalism facilitates 'scrollytelling' where a reader is given a more immersive experience through text, images, graphics and video, all of which was utilised by *Léman Bleu* during fieldwork observations while their reporters relied on smartphone technology, (Dowling, 2016, p. 534).

This poses a question, what set of skills and practices are now required to be a journalist and if so, how are they similar or different? Ornebring (2010) discussed the challenges of reskilling, deskilling and multiskilling simultaneously for newsrooms and the subsequent pressure it puts on journalists to ‘not be left behind’. From field observations, there were similarities between Mojo practices with expectations placed on reporters to be more adaptable and open to change, despite the technical challenges they had to overcome. Mojos did not always feel supported in the transition to smartphone technology, with some feeling self-taught and others highlighting technical limitations and challenges. Research from Salzmann, et al (2020) reinforces the idea that journalists feel a ‘need to keep up’ (p. 12) to reinforce their professional identity and credibility despite most not receiving formal training to begin with as mentioned by the STV Mojo.

Technology corporations are also directly disrupting newsroom dynamics as they drive this Mojo transition. There is greater alignment between smartphone manufacturers and media producers, including the examples of NDTV and Samsung in this study and Reuters and Nokia referenced in the literature review. Karhunen (2017) demonstrates that journalism will continue to be affected by new and emerging technological drivers. Each of the case studies relied heavily on big technology corporations for apps, some free to use, including WhatsApp (Facebook owned), Skype (Microsoft owned), Facetime (Apple), Dropbox, Voice Memos (Apple) and Google Maps. The American case study differed from the others by paying for the AP scripting app service and Social News Desk software to help reporters write and share Mojo content. The expectation of being adaptable and a self-starter with free or available technology echoes arguments pertaining to DIY culture and media participation explored by Kafai and Peppler (2011). They suggest that the democratising impact of the internet and digital media has led to younger audiences, women and minority groups demonstrating their own media talents through

blogging and content creation, which in turn echoes the expectation placed on those entering journalism during the Mojo emergence in 2012. Research from O'Brien et al, (2020) suggests that the digitalisation of news is economically led and impacted by how much content consumers are willing to spend to get news. What can be deduced is that the economic impacts of utilising smartphones with free apps and live streaming services that are cheaper than satellite feeds are common to all four sites in this study and take precedence over traditional alternatives. *India Resists* queried if NDTV staff were doing the jobs of two employees then why were they not paid two salaries due to the Mojo transition. Ornebring (2010, p. 1) suggests that 'journalists ascribe great power and independent agency to technology' yet this same technology is alienating and breaking down what and who journalists are, as they are more removed from newsrooms and also from each other. From this study, it is clear that journalists have fewer guidelines, structures and clarity on what they are expected to do, coupled with less training and personal development as the incessant rolling 24/7 content demands continue, enabled by smartphones.

5.4 Mobile journalism threatening journalistic identity

The convergence of traditional newsroom roles due to Mojo was apparent in all four case studies. The lack of identity for content gatherers who became human journalistic hoovers was apparent at STV2 and also to a lesser extent at WDEF News 12. However, Léman Bleu and NDTV were able to push back against this practice with their news outputs reinforcing reporter identity and ownership of content through greater live broadcasts and social media platform distribution respectively.

Interestingly, the same mobile device affected convergence in both positive and negative ways. Journalists can be more alone and isolated due to the one-man newsroom enabled

by Mojo yet they can also be more connected to a social and digital audience. Online audiences were supportive, interacting with journalists when they produced content for their specific interests and to their platforms of choice. However, as both Thurman (2008, 2018) and Meltzer (2010) caution, a closer relationship between consumer and producer leads to greater expectations and more criticism. It was also evident that content consumers were creating more UGC, blurring the lines between citizen journalists using Mojo and broadcast journalists operating with a Mojo skillset. In some cases, despite the rise of UGC, ‘craftsmanship’ was still evident from mobile journalists compared to their citizen journalist counterparts. And yet, the removal of specialized skills like videography, editing, framing and sound production from broadcasting due to the introduction of smartphone devices contributed to shifts in identity and responsibility for broadcast journalists. It also presents opportunities for the potential polarization of content and dilution of quality as alluded to by news managers at WDEF News 12.

Some respondents in this study explained that they struggled to dedicate adequate time to interviewing when they were expected to be both a reporter and a videographer. This inability to specialize and deliver higher quality news content was, in turn, influenced by increased newsroom demands (Deuze, 2019). Mojo granted the journalists more editorial autonomy and freedom when reporting but also limited them with a greater volume of expectations each workday. This situation was replicated at WDEF News 12 but not at Léman Bleu as the mobile journalists had more time and space to evaluate and troubleshoot with reduced live broadcasting demands.

The convergence of roles also presented staff with an expectation to be their own IT support team, highlighted by Léman Bleu and NDTV production staff, in particular. Both organizations had issues with file formats, data and infrastructure limitations.

Smartphones presented zooming and framing challenges, audio concerns and lighting restrictions. Some respondents explained that these technical challenges can at times be addressed by younger reporters but can also lead to older newsroom staff feeling marginalised. This expectation to address technological problems adds pressure to journalists and creates new expectations of themselves and from their employers (Salzmann, et al, 2020). The assignment manager at WDEF News 12 was the oldest interviewee during this study and explained how the technical skills of younger journalists are an asset but they need to be taught more about government, ethics, objectivity and geography. These findings demonstrate two gulfs, one between older journalists resistant or struggling to change and younger journalists with the appropriate digital skillset but lacking in more fundamental and core knowledge for a role that has become more technology-focused but is still not considered a tech role. Hanitzsch and Vos (2017) describe how journalistic ideology and identity is being muddled and lost with reporters unsure of what is required or expected of them.

5.5 The early adopters and innovators

Despite Léman Bleu and NDTV facing technical challenges through their Mojo adoption, both contradict the views of Goggin (2015), Erdal et al (2019) and Nelson (2020) who claim that there has been a lack of research and innovation in broadcast journalism since the Mojo emergence. The democratization of journalism due to mobile technology has in most cases put journalists out of jobs, yet Léman Bleu are trying to readjust this shift and make their audiences and local businesses paid contributors in the formal newsgathering process, rather than see them as competition for free content creation. This innovative approach demonstrates that despite being early adopters (Rogers, 2003) similar to WDEF News 12, the Swiss outlet are pushing back against the pressures of audience demands.

Their audiences are now becoming a skilled semi-professional media arm of their newsgathering community. Jamil (2019) highlighted that while this may work in Global North news markets with watchdogs and public service broadcasters, it could be exploited in certain Global South economies due to political influence and private media ownership. This is echoed by Green (2002) when referring to technological determinism who explains that technological advances do not automatically equate to social progress, often there is economic success for corporations but not for poorer audiences or large communities.

NDTV, as late adopters, let smartphone technology influence their newsroom dynamic but were also trying to harness mobile hardware and software in a more tailored, innovative way. The pioneering method of creating their own cloud-based app system and file transfer service to suit their stations' needs could pave the way for mobile journalists who not only create content but can also have a greater input in coding, programming and software development. This also reduces reliance and dictation by the 'big five or other technology companies at NDTV (Whitaker, 2019). Further to this, utilising the same mobile device to log travel costs and provide ride-sharing opportunities to travel to and from video shoots was not evidenced in the other case sites. However this monitoring of employee data and movement can be viewed as a privacy concern with Davidow and Malone (2020) explaining how these services would need to be manually deactivated by the user . Adding to this, NDTV's creation of the world's first vertical live streaming channel (Sinha, 2018) and use of smartphones as studio cameras all demonstrate that while technology is driving changes in journalism and newsrooms, some innovation remains and it is a late adopter that is leading this charge. This is evidenced throughout the PhD documentary with news managers detailing the importance of adaptability while the media academics refer to MOJO implementation as reactive.

The creative response to news cycles and audience demands at NDTV were aided by the flexibility of Android OS systems versus the Apple reliance at the other case sites and the technological skillset of their staff, many of whom had engineering backgrounds prior to entering journalism. The open-source approach of the OS and, secondly, the strategic partnership with the phone developer Samsung also altered the Mojo implementation at NDTV. It can be argued that while technology and Mojo is driving change in the other case studies, NDTV and to a degree Léman Bleu are altering the power dynamic due to their unique position within this mobile journalism space. Green (2002) suggests that technological progress is achieved due to other changes including social, policy and economic factors and once the new approach is viewed as successful, it is difficult to return to previous technological norms. Unfortunately, based on the research findings WDEF News 12 despite being the earliest adopter in this research have not innovated due to having a smaller news team who are reliant on Apple technology, tighter budgets and with less versatile and skilled staffing, however they remain the only case study and one of the few explored throughout the literature who pay for software instead of using free personal apps preinstalled on iPhones.

Since Mojo implementation newsrooms have experienced constant change (Westlund, 2013), what this study has demonstrated is that very few journalists have had the opportunity to adapt this technology to their specific needs while the technology has facilitated greater demands and expectations (R1 2019; R2 2019). The specific skills of individual reporters can help define Mojo practice if economic constraints are not as prevalent.

5.6 A reliance on mobile journalism

This study provided significant opportunities to evaluate mobile journalism

implementation in newsrooms across the world. Some of the key successes to effective mobile journalism practice lay in its ability to aid stations to create more live content without significant additional costs and to satisfy audience expectations. It is clear that mobile journalism and the platformisation of society have significantly altered newsrooms in the last decade (Deuze, 2019; Murphy 2020; Goggin 2020). There are now fewer staff doing more work with less expensive technology. Newsroom management at each case site explained that increased output with reduced costs was the principal rationale for transitioning quickly to mobile journalism. The financial motivation of having less staff capable of delivering more for less has also been accelerated by the growth of consumer-produced content that mostly comes for free and can be augmented into news output (S3, 2018) (A1, 2018).

However, an overreliance on mobile technology has left many reporters removed from newsrooms for extensive periods of time, producing feelings of isolation, alienation, and disconnection from a support network of co-workers (Bock, 2012). When Mojo is fully adopted, newsroom workloads are no longer distributed amongst a news team but often put on the shoulders of an individual. In this sense, Mojo reflects the worst excesses of global capitalization (Zuboff, 2015) whereby new developments lead to job loss and greater alienation. When you factor in the infrastructural and technical problems that can arise for the individual Mojo reporter, it becomes a very isolated, underpaid and difficult profession, which is part journalist, social media producer, broadcaster, editor, and software engineer. A range of technical concerns can present themselves due to lack of connectivity and file types from just the sheer wear and tear put on technology that is not specifically created for demanding industrial workflows.

Evidence from this study suggests that opportunities for audiences to be more engaged

and involved with the news cycle have been enhanced through Mojo (Nelson 2020; Murphy 2020). However, there are a number of risks to this UGC approach especially in relation to ‘political coverage’ as seen in the Indian case where political parties had a ‘war room’ of social media output which created concerns over fake news. While Mojo can certainly contribute to the democratization of journalism, it is also opening up more pathways for biased or skewed content from UGC to be shown to a regional or national broadcasting audience (Udupa, 2018).

In Switzerland, the devolution of Mojo has helped their small newsroom become media trainers, utilising content from NGOs, private companies and sports clubs who now act as content creators and distributors for them. While this is effective for small public service newsrooms, it may undermine jobs in larger private media organizations and affect balance and objectivity. The risk associated with relying on UGC is that newsrooms shrink to just a few editors reviewing citizen and PR-produced content while repackaging the material for larger digital and broadcast audiences, dictating their editorial agenda.

NDTV’s switch to Mojo resulted in the loss of 70 jobs and this downward spiral of job loss has been seen in newsrooms globally (Lees, 2017; Flew, 2019). STV2 reporters referred to this loss as that of ‘craft’ professionals who are experts within their fields rather than one Mojo being adequate at a number of different roles. All four case studies evidenced extensive demands placed on their newsrooms due to audience expectations, which were all enabled and facilitated by Mojo. Fuchs (2014) and Nygren and Gidlund (2012) outline some concerns including the profiting of media corporations from UGC enabled by Mojo as well as the removing of a sense of self for journalists who become less social beings and more cogs in an ‘always on’ news machine. These constant news demands across social media, TV and online are leaving reporters stretched or out of

work. Journalists feel they have to fulfil all these Mojo needs in order to not be left behind (Salzmann et al, 2020). This research has demonstrated that mobile journalism is both a constructive and destructive force in newsrooms across the world, filling gaps where budgets for employees has vanished but also forcing staff to alter workflows, their identities and their news values due to dictation by new and evolving technology. In the coming chapter I reflect on the creative practice journey taken throughout this study and prior to drawing conclusions from this research.

Chapter 6: Creative Practice Reflections

This chapter comprises reflections from the creative practice experiences during both the fieldwork and editorial phases of this study from 2018 to 2020. Included within these reflections are insights into the review process, which surfaced throughout the final production of the creative artefact.

My background as a mobile journalist from 2011-2017 involved filing short daily TV news reports and some longer feature-length packages of up to five minutes in duration. Schultz (2007) refers to this workflow for journalists as like ‘a blackboard wiped clean each morning’ (p. 192). She further highlights that while this is the routine of the journalist it is not that of the ethnographer or researcher when studying a newsroom (Schultz, 2007). Within factual TV I had shot, presented and produced two thirty-minute TV episodes, but was not experienced in the role of a practice-based researcher compared to that of an active mobile and broadcast journalist. This dilemma, and the challenges it presented, are discussed within this section of the thesis. Guillaumier (2016) highlights that having an open mind and being curious are vital when reflecting on your own creative practice.

Prior to embarking on the study, I had to ask myself a few important questions including how many days of fieldwork are sufficient for fieldwork within each case site? How many interviews would be adequate to garner a broad range of views and insights? Would this immersion and exposure to newsrooms from a non-practitioner standpoint create internal conflict?

6.1 Reflecting on creative practice

Kolb (1984, p.24) believes experience plays a ‘central role’ in the learning process. In the context of this study, the documentary approach of creating a slow journalism version of the mobile journalism debate allowed space for insights both from the newsroom setting and the academic world. This ethnographic research contributes to the second wave of newsroom research first initiated by the Glasgow Media Group (Willig, 2013) due to greater societal and economic factors now at play (Schultz, 2007). Throughout the fieldwork, practitioner-observer tensions existed. During three of the four fieldwork visits, I had to suppress my desire to be involved in the newsgathering process to focus on the task in hand as an ethnographic researcher (Arber, 2006). This presented itself in varying forms, both from a desire to criticize, to a concern to explain a quicker or simpler way to carry out a newsgathering task, none of which I could vocalize. Further to this was the emotional difficulty of being in awe of the newsgathering operation on day one with NDTV, an issue that Guillaumier (2006) has identified. I present some reflections on a case-by-case basis, before reflecting on the editing process for each with click-through links provided for each of the individual solo case study creative outputs. Finally, I reflect and analyse the revised editing stages where the interviews and insights from across all four case sites were combined to create longer form documentary pieces, eventually leading to the finalised creative artefact for this submission referred to at the beginning of the thesis.

6.1.1 Fieldwork reflections

The erratic requirements of the Scottish mobile journalists coupled with severe weather during some of the fieldwork required the aforementioned flexibility Schultz (2007) refers to. I was concerned about having gathered sufficient video material as this was my first

field study. Garrett and Hawkins (2014, p. 158) refer to this worry when reflecting upon their own visual ethnographic study as ‘pics or it didn’t happen’. Due to this concern, I frequently archived daily video clips to multiple hard drive and cloud locations while reviewing the gathered video content and compiled reflective notes on my smartphone notes app. Upon completing these tasks at the end of each day across the four case study sites I became acutely aware of what content I had but also of what I was missing. By front ending the interviews with the STV news manager and production journalist while allowing the space to be with the lead Mojo (S1) and speak to him in a sit-down interview at the end of the week, I gave myself more opportunities to grasp who he was and what he did and delve deeper in the final focused interview. Borneman and Hammoudi (2009) cite the work of Zaman (2008) when describing how the ethnographer must strike a balance between gaining trust from study participants and also asking naïve questions.

The Mojo’s radio broadcasting background also impacted my mobile creative practice. He was acutely aware of noise and sound while undertaking his newsgathering tasks. I became influenced by this and began to include natural sound, alter audio levels and remove background interference when capturing his movements and duties. His mantra of ‘trust the technology, have good quality sound’ (S1, 2018) resonated with me during all four case study weeks. Thomsen (2014) explains how the influence of journalistic participants operating in the same media space and field as a researcher can impact on them. Furthermore, the production journalist described during field interview that poor audio had negatively affected her earlier in her TV career ‘with the phone it was harder to tell the levels, you were just taking a video’ (S2, 2018).

What also became apparent was the feeling of incapacity. I could not contribute or influence what the journalists were doing, even if I disagreed or felt there was an

alternative approach to performing their daily tasks. This detachment dilemma surfaced in a number of ways, including route choice to video shoots, where to stop, where to eat, what questions to ask their interviewees. I had to remain removed from the story content and news cycle that the Mojo was covering and be an impartial ethnographer not a colleague.

One of the most significant challenges during the week-long field study in America with WDEF News 12 was remaining disconnected from the news story content and the newsroom workflow. For example, these included not interfering to provide technical guidance to the journalists during newsgathering. Iphofen (2013) suggests that interference influences the important value of trust between researcher and human participant in ethnographic studies. Despite this, seeing less cumbersome and quicker avenues to achieve both content gathering and production, I could not impart my viewpoint as my primary duties were to observe and document, not interfere with the practice of others, echoing the views of Thomsen (2014) who also visited multiple field sites during her PhD studies. An example I encountered included a murder investigation press conference with a Sheriff, where a number of key questions were not asked by the mobile journalists. I was present as an ethical practice-based researcher providing a window into the worlds of these mobile reporters, and not a journalist. Similar difficulties have been recorded in medical ethnographic research (Arber, 2006) with researchers observing staff in a hospice environment but unable to contribute significantly.

The majority of the WDEF solo video piece was once again originally edited each evening and also on the return flight from America in April 2018. However, I found having a diverse and experienced range of journalistic voices to pick from, some with

particular insights into current practice, others into broadcasting as a whole provided greater analysis, debate and critique.

Throughout both of the 2018 field studies with STV2 and WDEF News 12, an array of urges to intervene or contribute surfaced, however with NDTV in April 2019 it was the opposite. I was taken aback and in some cases in awe of how the media organisation operated as a mobile journalism broadcast hub. I was caught off guard at first and corresponded with my supervisory team regarding this at the time. The election fever and push for breaking live news and energy of hundreds of broadcast and mobile media professionals in one building with the same goals was initially overwhelming. The sounds, sights, smells and socio- and cultural bombardment meant funnelling my attention solely towards my research goals was at times a struggle. Arber (2006) explains this as an identity ‘dilemma’ (p. 154). Mehta (2019) refers to the Indian street as a vibrant and bustling space for social encounters, contrasted with the sanitised public spaces of the Global North. Mehta (2019) further explains how the street acts as a ‘space for civic life and democratic practices’ (p. 310), while observing election reporting by NDTV journalists the majority of my time was spent in the chaotic Indian streets that Mehta refers to. The participants in this field site had conducted extensive levels of research into my background, my journalistic output and were both trusting and open to my presence facilitating the access ladder mentioned in the work of Gray (2011).

The slower news cycle, lack of live coverage and absence of breaking news presented a less hectic final fieldwork visit to Léman Bleu in 2019. This week required more endeavour and initiative on my behalf, observing multiple journalists on different shift patterns to gain the maximum range of insights from a more reserved group of journalists. It involved deploying similar approaches to that of Thomsen (2014) in actively partnering

up with participants each day after editorial meetings to help further insights and fieldwork observation and opportunities. The language barrier did in some instances create challenges to access (Gray, 2011), but the calmer news agenda coupled with a less demanding live broadcasting focus provided an avenue to observe more closely how a newsroom of mobile journalists who are given autonomy, can deliver rounded technically and editorially balanced broadcast material. Their slow journalism approach while utilising Mojo was both unique and refreshing to witness and demonstrated how journalistic identity can be influenced and forged through support and interaction in a newsroom environment between colleagues even during the digital and mobile age (Hanitzsch and Vos, 2017; Deuze, 2019).

STV2, WDEF News 12 and NDTV were all striving for a higher volume of content and news output, whereas Léman Bleu was more welcoming of compelling news stories, with which they could add an objective narrative with longer interviews augmented by deeper analysis on social and political issues.

6.1.2 Editing process reflections

Upon editing each segment of the documentary individually, on a case-by-case basis, the first long form edit took the shape of a news bulletin with me as the in-studio anchor. This was the beginning of what became an editing journey that lasted over a year, with opportunities to experiment with form and structure (Garrett and Hawkins, 2014). The second edit was more experimental and thematically focused. While the final edits provided opportunity for greater critical debate. A key conflict emerged during this time, which involved questioning when the editing process was finished. Slaughter (1998) suggests that this is when ‘common sense and restraint’ (p. 298) need to take precedence.

Content redacted due to photographed subject and a lack of consent for publication.
Please contact the author for further information.

STV mobile journalist in Ayrshire, February 2018.

Click-through hyperlinked image for digital readers

I partially edited the STV2 standalone segment each evening of the five days of shooting but also in its entirety a week after completing the field study. Through this approach, I was able to analyse what video material I had and through editing so soon after shooting, it led me to create the original self-contained piece in a style that was influenced but not defined by the field study itself. I included elements of natural sound with noise from winds and traffic and a phone ringing. I adopted a slower pace with the editing flow than that of a breaking news reporter working on a daily deadline. Garrett and Hawkins (2014, p. 156) describe the editing process of video as being ‘intimate’ when describing the connection between researcher, technology and video footage. While I did not experience this same level of emotional attachment, the dynamic between the material and myself as

the practice-researcher became fused through immersion and focus upon illuminating a visual ethnographic narrative.

The idealism surrounding interviewing those who interview others for a living also became apparent throughout the fieldwork. I observed how the participants were not apprehensive when I began recording, allaying the fears of Oliver (2005) and Murthy (2008) regarding playing up to the camera. The interviewees presented as journalists being interviewed by a journalist, they did not see me as a researcher but as a peer within their workspace based upon my observations.

The STV2 segment was utilised by the station for staff training and upskilling in the months after the fieldwork. However, due to the rise of social media, freely available smartphone and UGC video and changing audience trends the channel was eventually closed, with all three employees moving to different employers. S1 moved to ITV Borders, (S3) to BBC London, (S2) to the *Scottish Sun* newspaper. Scottish TV News viewing figures had been falling throughout the duration of this study (Walker, 2019). STV2 along with the BBC Scotland channel were late adopters of hyper-localised TV content. Dwindling audiences no longer engaged through traditional media but chose a digital platform (Learmouth, 2019). STV2 came off air after 434 days on July 1st 2018, (Keyden, 2018).

Content redacted due to photographed subject and a lack of consent for publication.
Please contact the author for further information.

Mojo reporter delivering a live broadcast in Georgia, April 2018

Click-through hyperlinked image for digital readers

The flow of the first finalised edit of the WDEF News 12 piece was faster than STV2 due to my editing style once again being influenced by societal and cultural factors, including the urgency of live news demands in the station. Inclusion of natural sound and the voices of an array of interviewees illuminated the piece, building on the STV2 experience. Some editorial elements helped define the immediacy and urgency of broadcasting evidenced throughout the fieldwork, including the producer countdown, drone video and impressing upon an audience the size of news market and experience of its contributors. Aligned to this, through opening and closing segments with a veteran broadcaster narrative flavour could be added, a storyteller telling a story about his world which we are about to see and experience. The editing process can either be conscious or subconscious (Garrett and Hawkins, 2004), they clarify that in some cases we are even editing subconsciously when we are recording the initial content. I experienced this subconscious editing during my fieldwork with WDEF News 12

Mojo reporter broadcasting live outside parliament in New Delhi, April 2019

Click-through hyperlinked image for digital readers

Each evening I reviewed the video content I had gathered with NDTV. By utilising an iPhone, an iPod and two rechargeable battery packs and laptop as an extra hard drive, I had the opportunity to archive and analyse material during my fieldwork visit on a daily basis. The challenges of remaining detached and focusing on the researcher requirements are referred to by Guillaumier (2006) who explains that the ethnographer can be caught up ‘being in your element’ (p. 357). This week presented the most significant number of challenges for a number of reasons including the sheer quantity of clips, interviews, cutaways, location shots and themes and issues discussed. Further to this, I experienced editor blocks when it came to structuring the solo video piece due to having excessive amounts of content.

The cultural and social influence of India and New Delhi in particular engulfed the editorial process with sounds, colours, extended sequences and activity in so many parts

of the narrative flow to the piece. The energy of an Asian city, fast paced, loud and manic trickled through into the formation of the video story echoing Mehta (2019). The challenge of striking a balance between these elements, ended up with my original edit straying too much towards the subject material the reporters were covering, an election, rather than addressing the research questions and exploration of key debates within the Mojo landscape.

Mojo reporter reporting on a construction project outside Geneva, May 2019

Click-through hyperlinked image for digital readers

The editing process for the *Léman Bleu* solo segment was the least difficult despite being the only station with English as a second language. During edit and shooting, you subconsciously weave the story together (Garrett and Hawkins, 2014). With *Léman Bleu*, I had already begun to form the structure and pace of the piece prior to full completion of the fieldwork. Upon reflection, this may have been due to the slower news cycle and greater space afforded to me as the ethnographic researcher to reflect upon the study as a whole over the previous 18 months. The future-proofing innovation of the news director,

in first adopting Mojo, developing and enhancing the news workflow and production values before imparting the acquired knowledge and skills to the active Swiss audience can be argued was selfless and charitable at an initial reflection, but also a strategic move to sustain and in some cases expand the reach of the news organization.

6.1.3 Revisiting the editing process

In total, five long form edits took place of the practice-based output for this research. They included commercial and critical edits as well as the final revised version available at the beginning of this submission.

The first full edit (commercial Output, PBS TV + PBS Passport USA, June 2019) incorporated the individual case study videos with an off-camera summary and on camera introduction. It was structured akin to a news bulletin with opening credits, cutting to an in-studio presenter similar to a newsreader who would then throw to each case study. The case studies acted as independent longform TV feature reports self-contained with in-studio links between each one providing a cue or line in, similar to a TV newscast. This structure became apparent with each news organisation being identified as a different part of the Mojo journey during the initial editing phase. STV2 acted as a grounding in Mojo or an introductory report/case study in the practice, WDEF12 a more focused revolutionary example, NDTV an evolutionary report and finally Léman Bleu a devolution, whereby journalists distribute their skills and knowledge to their audience. The edit was composed with audience expectations to the forefront, with simplicity in the structure and a recap of major themes and issues. Garret and Hawkins (2014, p. 158) describe this as respect to an audience.

The PBS initial edit proved successful for TV audiences and at English-speaking film

festivals due to its simplistic form and ease of access to the key debates and discussions. I was challenged to restructure the piece on focused thematic grounds rather than case study by case study. This created a number of concerns namely the lack of desire to move on from what I had previously created, and which had proven successful, but also a lack of confidence to reshape the creative research output in a different way. Riley and Christou (2012) explain that video editing is about interpretation of scenes and highlight the importance of seeing multiple ways to tell visual stories. After focused efforts at transcription, further evaluation of the content and thematic analysis, the second edit took shape examining strengths and weaknesses of Mojo implementation. This form allowed retention of a simple structure while blending the case studies insights and being guided by the research questions. Initial concerns surrounding the documentary moving from case study to case study and back leading to audience confusion was removed when the interviewees, despite their different locations and accents, had shared views on Mojo. Through intermingling academic critiques and quotes throughout the production and incorporating music, the pace of the film was maintained. Garrett and Hawkins (2014, p. 157) describe in detail the coming together of a final video edit as a combination of 'aesthetic choices and judgements with technical abilities and limitations for the footage'. Their observations encapsulate the creative journey that I experienced.

Upon completion of the second edit, I was encouraged to intermingle the views of the key authors from my literature. These academic references moved the focus of the creative artefact towards a video essay form and enhanced synergies between the practice and written outputs of this research. These new additions allowed for viewers to reflect and observe through the pace of the piece the key themes and issues surrounding Mojo implementation.

The academic video edit, completed in December 2019 was the product of further review from my supervisory team, encouraging the replacement of on-screen academic quotes with the faces and voices of the academics themselves. The Kuwait based media academic (R1) articulated clearly some of the primary debates within the Mojo and digital media sphere and connected them to this study, including his belief that the adoption of Mojo was reactionary. The Romanian professor (R2) provided insights into where she felt journalism was progressing and referred to concerns around big data and privacy. She suggested that journalists need to be more tech savvy and have a stronger grasp of the software behind their news output. The American expert (R3) delivered some strong critical soundbites, possibly due to her extensive broadcast background, these included views on visual literacy and also how she believed traditional TV viewers may be left behind by newer younger audiences who want to watch vertical news content on their phones. All three remote video interviewees contributed to what became the 4th edit and with it a revised longer duration of 48 minutes. This more critical production proved successful with international non-TV audiences, winning half a dozen film festivals in late 2019 and early 2020.

The final edit, produced in August 2020, is the basis of the PhD submission. Throughout the study, I have presented the creative artefacts to audiences in England, Scotland, America and France and received feedback at each juncture. One of the final test audiences was a class of 4th year BA journalism students at UWS in early 2020. Individuals raised concerns surrounding the flow of the fourth edit, the type of music used, erratic audio levels and an expectation of more engaging opening titles. The final test audience praised the voiceover, the breadth of content, the beginning of the documentary and the use of archive materials. Taking the feedback from all audiences on board and guidance from the supervisory time, the final ethnographic video edit moves

away from onscreen thematic signposting, and allows for more nuanced interpretation in what is a shorter and more critical piece of mobile video journalism, that strives to show progression and impact as well as act as an original contribution to knowledge. The final submission takes into account the guiding research questions surrounding journalistic identity and shows threats, opportunities and similarities amongst Mojo practice while demonstrating that socio and economic factors are at play in newsroom changes.

6.2 Concluding comments

Upon final reflection of the fieldwork and the creation of the finalised creative artefact, the doctoral process has altered my perspective on both ethnography and mobile journalism storytelling. Through this creative practice journey, I have learned to question, analyse and debate the merits of whether mobile technology, which is dictating and influencing news workflows and journalistic identity, is suitable and appropriate. Prior to this study, I did not query or criticise mobile and digital journalism but rather championed it. I was part of the Mojo wave not a critic or an analyst of it. Over the last three years I have changed and now support the point made by the web producer at WDEF News 12 during field interview that ‘there needs to be someone in the chain who asks not how something should be done, but whether something should be done’ (A4, 2018).

Mobile journalism is essential to 21st century newsrooms but how often it is used and for what purposes can create a range of risks and issues for a generation of journalists that know how to use the technology but do not always query when it is being used against them.

Chapter 7: Conclusions and

Recommendations for Further Research

7.1 Introduction

This research set out to show the extent and effect of mobile journalism while presenting the key opportunities and threats it poses. Building on this, it aimed to provide an answer as to whether newsrooms or technology are driving these changes. When reviewing both the literature and the findings presented throughout this study it can be attested that Mojo is both a reaction and a solution influenced by social and economic drivers in relation to the digitalisation of journalism. The thesis and the practice output intended to show similarities and differences to Mojo practice while presenting insights on journalistic identity and affirm that technology is in fact driving change, while some news outlets are altering and harnessing this transition in innovative and creative ways.

Through presenting understandings from a range of case sites in different continents, it is evident that adoption of this new practice can be both constructive and destructive.

Greater live broadcasting options, fewer employees and cost savings all contribute to the welcoming of new and innovative Mojo practices. Yet, it is the loss of jobs and the increased pressure put on those who remain in newsrooms that demonstrates the damaging aspects to mojo implementation, 70 NDTV employees were cut and STV2 has since shut down. While technology companies are influencing newsroom change, a small number of news outlets are innovatively altering this dynamic, including NDTV and Léman Bleu. Social trends in a smartphone society with enhanced internet infrastructures have also contributed to the rise and dominance of mobile journalism based on the

findings from this study. In addition, technology corporations are leading and altering societal and journalistic practices due to enhanced capabilities of personal technology that is now being utilised for industrial media needs. These shifts all effect broadcast journalists who are now more isolated and alienated in newsrooms with fewer colleagues, fulfilling increased expectations, while using cost effective equipment. The growing significance of UGC exerts further pressure on newsrooms to accept free or available social media and citizen mobile video content with the risk of undermining core journalistic principles of balance and objectivity.

7.2 Research contributions

Perrault and Stanfield (2018) explain that their study would have been enhanced had it utilised ethnographic interviews and focused on individual case studies. Burum (2014) highlighted the lack of exploration in his work surrounding technology when investigating mobile journalism. Willig (2013) discussed the lack of another wave of journalism ethnographic research since Philo et al in the 1970s. This research study is part of what Willig envisaged, drawing on Global North and Global South case sites to examine the impact of social, economic and technological drivers on journalism practice. It adds to the Mojo focus of Burum (2014) and newsroom ethnographic work of Thomsen (2014) while echoing the views of Deuze (2019), Nelson (2020) and Westlund (2015). Through creation of a creative artefact, it provides a visual means to illustrate findings that differs from the more traditional doctoral studies into new media and digital journalism. Finally, a study from Wu, Tandoc, Salmon (2019) into the technological changes in broadcasting interviewed a small sample of broadcasters. This research was more inclusive through engaging with a much larger sample of experienced interviewees from across the world in India, Romania, Switzerland, Scotland, America and Kuwait.

Furthermore, the distinctive approach of ethnographic research with a mobile creative practice artefact that aligns thematically and analytically with this thesis has not been conducted previously and presents a contribution to knowledge that will hopefully inform and guide newsrooms and journalism educators. The fused approach of theory and practice has been utilised throughout modules at undergraduate level in media studies in the UK, but is not used as extensively in postgraduate studies or in PhD research.

This study aimed to improve conceptual definitions of practice-based journalism research. This type of enquiry is waning in certain regions due to conflict between the academy and media practitioners who join higher education institutions (Vine, et al, 2014). It is hoped that this study will encourage future and similar media research from early career practitioners. The video outputs may also demonstrate an example of how practice-based journalists within the academy need not solely contribute through textual form and can harness their creative skillsets similar to those in the music and performing arts academic spaces. By utilising transcription and thematic analysis of the video work and reflection on the creative practice journey, insights have been presented surrounding the practitioner versus researcher dilemma. The body of work in this space is more aligned to other creative industries including film and music (Thompson-Bell, 2014) but also pertains to digital and mobile media research as this study has shown.

Previous research into mobile journalism has included small sample sizes. There are some exceptions to this, including the extensive work of Mabwezara (2017) in Africa. This study, drawing on qualitative methodologies, can encourage others within the academia not to limit their enquiries to just one country or one case study site. Earlier Mojo studies have also relied on surveying and while this approach could have been incorporated into

this study, immersion in the field sites provided a more rounded opportunity to focus on both socio and economic impacts on journalistic innovation and observe changes to journalistic identity. While there is a significant body of work that shines a positive light on Mojo, it is hoped this study will increase critical dialogue and discussion surrounding smartphone influence in relation to media creation and consumption. The technical limitations highlighted through the findings as well as the impact on journalistic identity that are evidenced in this study demonstrate the negative effect and ramifications from accelerated Mojo adoption.

The ethical concerns presented in this work pertaining to younger self-taught mobile journalists who are at risk of making unethical or illegal decisions as referred to by management at WDEF News 12 point to a need for greater training and staff support. Building on this are the views brought forward by both American and India based journalists during interview about the threat that UGC and political parties can play in news coverage with misinformation and disinformation affirming the need for fact checking, analysis and source confirmation.

7.3 Recommendations for further research

Building on this study there are a range of areas and paths for continued research. For example, more forensic analysis into the role producers (Bruns, 2008) play through a short more focused study involving interviewing and observing citizen journalists and reviewing mobile UGC workflows would build on some of the key debates presented in this study. Further to this, a more in-depth exploration of how Asian news markets have emerged or developed since the conclusion of fieldwork in May 2019 could enhance

some of the debates surrounding early adopters and late innovators presented during fieldwork (Rogers, 2003).

Prior to commencing and during his study I liaised with African news outlets in Kenya and Nigeria who were working towards a Mojo newsroom approach, but were not able to facilitate field work at the time, these news markets could present an avenue of research for others to further explore. Another option could be a revisiting of the three remaining active case sites and an analysis of the impact of the coronavirus pandemic on broadcast output and newsroom identity may demonstrate the acceleration of Mojo practices into the mainstream, but also a devolving of newsrooms with a more alienated and disconnected workforce.

Each of these further research recommendations benefit from being able to travel to each location, however due to current restrictions through a combination of Covid-19 and Brexit I have evaluated a more localised and domestic opportunity to expand this study. It involves immersion in a newsroom in the Scottish Borders with ITV for a period of 6 months in late 2021 to early 2022 and will include working alongside rather than observing S-1 Bruce McKenzie, formerly of STV2. This post-doctoral work will allow the researcher to become immersed in the journalistic space as a practitioner/researcher rather than a participant observer. This approach will allow the researcher to draw on personal experiences and provide greater insights into some of the key areas of concern through Mojo implementation including alienation, technological determinism and the platformisation of newsrooms post Covid-19. Further to this, the researcher will be focusing on the craft element of journalism in reporter's skillsets and the dual approach of a blended journalism practice utilising cameras and smartphones to gather content.

Insights and findings from this post-doctoral study can be incorporated into teaching techniques and curriculum development to better prepare graduates for post Covid-19 roles in broadcasting while feeding into staff development, work placement and mentorship within the ITV organisation both in Scotland and with staff and news trainees in Northern Ireland and the North of England

Finally, a key recommendation from this study is that of upskilling and recognition of technological skillsets within a field that has previously aligned more to the humanities. Educators need to associate more technical production courses with journalism studies to prepare students for the expectations of newsrooms where they may often have to troubleshoot their own technological issues. Further to this a recognition of the role those with varying backgrounds including science, engineering and maths can have within the journalism space should be built on from this study, with innovation coming at NDTV not from journalism graduates but media practitioners utilising knowledge from previous computer science studies.

Concluding thoughts

In conclusion, this study aimed to explore the extent to which mobile journalism acts as a disruption, a reaction, and a solution influenced by both economic and societal trends when affecting newsgathering and journalistic identity. This ambition has been achieved through highlighting how smartphone technology is influencing change in newsrooms, with a minority of news outlets harnessing this transition and utilising available technology in innovative ways. However, the findings of this study suggest that we need to be wary and question rapid technological change instead of allowing big technology corporations and audience demands to dictate what our news and media worlds are

becoming. Broadcast journalism has evolved for more than 70 years but in the last decade it has transformed more rapidly than ever before, including significant changes in the media landscape with a growing number of jobs being lost. The effects of the coronavirus pandemic have accelerated the normalisation of mobile journalism practice into everyday broadcasting to the extent that the moniker 'mobile' journalism could soon be replaced simply by the term journalism.

References

Abramson, J. (2020) *Merchants of truth: the business of news and the fight for facts*. New York: Simon and Schuster.

Adornato, A. (2018) *Mobile and social media journalism: a practical guide*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publishing.

Albeanu, C. (2017) *Mobile journalism is helping CBC focus on digital storytelling*. Available at: <https://www.journalism.co.uk/news/mobile-journalism-is-helping-cbc-focus-on-digital-storytelling/s2/a704359> (Accessed 2 December 2018).

Allen, S. (2019) *Pale, male and stale: challenging representations of Africa at independent journalism festival*. Available at: <http://www.sussex.ac.uk/broadcast/read/49299> (Accessed: 16 February 2021).

Angus, R. (2014) *Straight to camera versus interview*. Available at: <https://www.clipsthat sell.com.au/blog/straight-to-camera-versus-interview/> (Accessed: 31 October 2019).

Aradau, B. and Greenway, C. T. G. (2019) 'Acts of digital parasitism: hacking, humanitarian apps and platformisation', *New Media and Society*, 21(11), pp. 2548-2565.

Arber, A. (2006) *Reflexivity: A challenge for the researcher as practitioner*. Available at: http://epubs.surrey.ac.uk/2658/2/Microsoft_Word_-_NurseresearchArticlefinal.pdf (Accessed: 1 December 2019).

Arnold, P. (2018) *CrossCheck Nigeria launches to fight information disorder*. Available at: <https://firstdraftnews.org/crosscheck-nigeria-launches-to-fight-information-disorder/> (Accessed: 21 January 2019).

Anand, A. (2015) *Why the media seems to hate the Modi government*. Available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/blogs/et-commentary/why-the-media-seems-to-hate-the-modi-government/> (Accessed: 8 August 2021).

Atton, C. (2008) 'Alternative and citizen journalism', in Wahl-Jorgensen, K. and T. Hanitzsch T. (eds.) *The handbook of journalism studies*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh Napier University, Routledge, pp. 265-278.

Babcock, W. A. and Freivogel, W. H. (2015) *The Sage guide to key issues in mass media, Ethics and law*. Sherman Oaks, CA: Sage Publishing.

Baker, S. (2012) *How many qualitative interviews is enough?* NCDRM, University of Southampton.

Becquet, N. (2015) *Mobile reporting has great potential, but where are the journalists?* Available at: <https://www.journalism.co.uk/news/mobile-journalism-has-great-potential-but-where-are-the-journalists-/s2/a594525/> (Accessed: 6 December 2018).

Biesterfeld, P. (2015) *Six primary styles of documentary*. Available at:
<https://www.videomaker.com/article/c06/18423-six-primary-styles-of-documentary-production> (Accessed: 28 September 2018).

Biggs, M. and Buchler, D. (2008) 'Eight criteria for practice-based research in the creative and cultural industries', *Art Design and Communication in Higher Education*, 7(1), pp. 5-18.

Bijker, W. (2010) '*How is Technology made?-That is the Question!*', Available at:
<https://academic.oup.com/cje/article-abstract/34/1/63/1702334>, Accessed: 30 September 2021).

Billington, M. (2001) *One night stands: a critic's view of modern British theatre*. London, UK: Nick Hern Books.

Bimber, B. (1990) *Karl Marx and the three faces of technological determinism*. London, UK: Sage Publishing.

Bird, S.E. (2011) 'Are we all producers now? Convergence and media audience practices', *Cultural Studies*, 25(4-5), pp. 502-516.

Bivens, R. (2008) 'The internet, mobile phones and blogging', *Journalism Practice*, 2(1), pp. 113-129.

Blankenship, J. (2016) Losing their Mojo? *Journalism Practice*, 10(8), pp. 1055-1071.

Bolderston, A. (2012) 'Conducting a research interview', *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences*, 43, pp.66-76.

Borchart, A. (2018) *Making journalism great again*. Available at: <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/fake-news-challenges-journalism-industry-by-alexandra-borchardt-2018-01?barrier=accesspaylog> (Accessed: 16 September 2019).

Borneman, J. and Hammoudi, A. (2009) *Being there: the fieldwork encounter and the making of truth*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.

Boyer, D. (2013) *The life informatics: newsmaking in the digital era*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.

Brennan, B. (2013) *Qualitative Research Methods for Media Studies*. Philadelphia, USA: Available at: <https://urimediastudies.files.wordpress.com/2016/10/bonnie-brennen-qualitative-media-research.pdf> (Accessed: 7 December 2018).

Brook, S. (2012) 'Introduction. Part 2: The critiques of practice-led research', *Text*, Special issue. Available at: [http://www.textjournal.com.au/speciss/issue14/Brook%20\(Intro%202\).pdf](http://www.textjournal.com.au/speciss/issue14/Brook%20(Intro%202).pdf) (Accessed: December 8th 2018)

Bruns, A. (2008) 'The future is user led: the path towards widespread produsage', *Fibre Culture Journal*, 11, non-paginated. Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/27472557_The_Future_Is_User-Led_The_Path_towards_Widespread_Produsage (Accessed; 5 May 2020).

Bruzzi, S. (2006) *New documentary*. 2nd edn. London: Routledge.

Bui, M. N. and Moran, R. (2020) 'Making the 21st century mobile journalist: examining definitions and conceptualizations of mobility and mobile journalism within journalism education', *Digital Journalism*, 8(1), pp. 145-163.

Burd, G. (1983) 'Journalistic observation as a qualitative research method for sociology', *Annual Meeting of the-Southwestern Sociological. Association* (Houston, TX, March 16-19, 1983). <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED233940>

Burger, M. and Fitzgerald, R. (2019) 'Good professional reasons for bad journalism practice: inventing audience contributions in a live TV debate', *Journalism Practice*, 13(10), pp. 1185-1199.

Burnett, R. and Marshall, D. (2003) *Web theory, an introduction*. London: Routledge.

Burum, I. (2014) *How to Mojo: democratising journalism skills across spheres of communication*. PhD thesis. Deakin University. Available at:

<https://dro.deakin.edu.au/eserv/DU:30067352/burum-howto-2014A.pdf> (Accessed:

January 28th 2018)

Cabral, F. (2017) *Operação serenata de amor*. [Digital image] Available at: <https://medium.com/data-science-brigade/jarbas-apresenta-todas-as-suspeitas-da-robô-rosie-da-operação-serenata-de-amor-cd021e9be045>, (Accessed: 14th October 2018).

Cameron, J. and Geidner, N. (2014) ‘Something old, something new, something borrowed from something blue’, *Journal of Broadcasting and Electronic Media*, 58(3), pp. 400-419.

Candy, L. (2006) *Practice-based research: a guide, creativity & cognition studios*. Available at: <https://www.creativityandcognition.com/resources/PBR%20Guide-1.1-2006.pdf> (Accessed: March 19th 2019).

Chakaveh S. and Bogen M. (2007) ‘Media convergence, an introduction’, in: Jacko J.A. (ed.) *Human-Computer Interaction. HCI Intelligent Multimodal Interaction Environments. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 4552. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73110-8_88

Chang, H. (2008) *Autoethnography as Method*. London: Routledge.

Chang, H. (2016) ‘Autoethnography in health research: growing pains?’ *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(4), pp. 443-451. doi: 10.1177/1049732315627432

Clark, R. P. (2009) ‘Who is the fifth estate?’ *Poynter Institute Blog*. Available at: <https://www.poynter.org/news/who-fifth-estate-and-what-its-role-journalisms-future> (Accessed; 14 October 2018).

Communello, F. (2016) 'Women, youth and everything else: age-based and gendered stereotypes in relation to digital technology among elderly Italian mobile phone users', *Media Culture and Society*, 39(6), pp. 798-815.

Couldry, N., Ridriguez, C. and Bolin, G. (2019) 'Media communication and the struggle for social progress', *Global Media and Communication*, 14(2), pp. 173-191.

Cross, J. (2018) 'In defense of documentaries as journalism', *Columbia Journalism Review*, 3 December. https://www.cjr.org/first_person/documentary-film-journalism.php

Cramer, J. and McDevitt, M. (2004) 'Ethnographic journalism', in qualitative research' in Iorio, S.H. (ed.), *Journalism: Taking it to the Streets*. New York, NY: Routledge, pp. 127-144.

Crowley, J. (2018) *How are Journalists dealing with email overload*. Available at: <https://www.journalism.co.uk/news/how-are-journalists-dealing-with-email-overload-in-modern-newsrooms-/s2/a725128/> (Accessed: 8 January 8 2020).

Dans, E. (2019) 'Meet Bertie, Heliograf and Cyborg', *Forbes*, 6 February. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/enriquedans/2019/02/06/meet-bertie-heliograf-and-cyborg-the-new-journalists-on-the-block/#2a0efcae138d>

Davidow, W.H. and Malone, M.S. (2020) *The autonomous revolution*. San Francisco, CA: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

Deloitte (2017) *The future of the smartphone: the era of invisible innovation*. Available at: <http://www.deloitte.co.uk/tmtpredictions2018/assets/img/downloads/FY18->

Predictions-Future-of-the-Smartphone-Single-Prediction.pdf. (Accessed: 6 February 2019).

Deuze, M. (2005) 'What is journalism? Professional identity and ideology of journalists reconsidered', *Journalism*, 6(4), pp. 442-464.

Deuze, M. (2019) 'What journalism is (no)t', *Social Media + Society*, 5(3), pp. 1-4.

Dewey, J. (1934) *Art as experience*. New York, NY: G.P Putnam's Sons.

Dickinson, R. and Bigi, H. (2009) 'The Swiss video journalist', *Journalism*, 10(4), pp. 509-526.

Dimitrova, D.V. and Neznanski, M. (2006) 'Online journalism and the war in cyberspace: a comparison between U.S. and international newspapers', *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12(1), pp. 248-263.

Domingo, D. (2003) 'Ethnography for new media studies: a field report of its weaknesses and benefits', *Symposium: New Research for New Media: Innovative Research Methodologies September 2003*, Minnesota, USA: Institute for New Media Studies, University of Minnesota.

Dowd, C. (2020) *Digital journalism, drones and automation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Donald, S.H., Anderson, T.D. and Spry, D. (2010) *Youth, society and mobile media in Asia*. London: Routledge.

Dorsey, K. (2020) 'Advertising recovery gathers steam as STV posts record growth in viewers', *The Herald*, 5 November. Available at:

https://www.heraldscotland.com/business_hq/18847148.advertising-recovery-gathers-steam-stv-posts-record-growth-viewers/ (Accessed 8 August 2021).

Dowling, D. (2016) 'The business of slow journalism', *Digital Journalism*, 4(4), pp. 530-546.

Drok, N. and Hermans, L. (2016) 'Is there a future for slow journalism?' *Journalism Practice*, 10(4), pp. 539-554.

Drula, G. (2014) 'Media convergence and mobile technology', *Journal of Media Research* 3(20), pp. 47-71.

Duffy, A., Ling, R., Kim, N., Tandoc jr., E. and Westlund, O. (2020) 'News: mobiles, mobilities and their meeting points', *Digital Journalism*, 8(10), pp. 1-14.

Durham, F. (1998) *News frames as social narratives: TWA Flight 800, international*. Oxford: Oxford University Press: Communications Association.

Dutton, B. (2016) *Get ready to meet the fifth sstate: how networked individuals and institutions are reshaping academe*. [Online Presentation], University of Oxford, UK: Oxford Internet Institute.

Earnshaw, D, (2018) *Vox pops International*. Available at:
<https://www.voxpops.com/about-us/> (Accessed: January 8th, 2020).

Ellis, C., Adams, T.E. and Bochner, A.P. (2010) 'Autoethnography: an overview', *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 12(1), non-paginated. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-12.1.1589>

Erdal, J.E., Øie, K.V., Oppegaard, B. and Westlund, O. (2019) 'Invisible locative media: key considerations at the nexus of place and digital journalism', *Media and Communication*, 7(1), non-paginated. <https://doi.org/10.17645/mac.v7i1.1766>

Etherington, K. (2017) *Narrative approaches to case studies*. Bristol, UK: University of Bristol.

Etherington, K. (2017) 'Personal experience and critical reflexivity in counselling and psychotherapy research', *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*, 17(2), pp. 85-94.

Ferreira, R.B. (2021) 'Liquid disinformation tactics: overcoming social media counter measures through misleading content' *Journalism Practice*, 20 April.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2021.1914707>

Flew, T. (2019) 'Digital communication, the crisis of trust, and the post-global', *Communication Research and Practice*, 5(1), pp. 4-22.

Fortunati, L. and O'Sullivan, J. (2020) 'Understanding mobile news: looking beyond the lockscreen', London, UK: *Digital Journalism*, 8(1), pp. 164-169.

Fuchs, C. and Horak, E. (2008) 'Informational capitalism and the digital divide in Africa', *Masaryk University Journal of Law and Technology*, 1, pp.11-32.

<https://core.ac.uk/reader/230601750>

Fuchs, C. (2010) 'Labor in informational capitalism and on the Internet', *The Information Society*, 26(3), pp. 179-196.

Fuchs, C. (2014) *Digital labor and Karl Marx*. New York: Routledge.

Fuchs, C. (2020) 'Communication socialism/digital socialism', *Triple C, Communication, Capitalism and Critique*, 8(1), pp. 1-31. <https://doi.org/10.31269/triplec.v18i1.1144>

Galvin, J., Suominen, E., Morgan, C., O'Connell, E.J. and Smith, A.P. (2015) 'Mental health nursing students' experiences of stress during training: a thematic analysis of qualitative interviews', *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, 22(10), pp. 773-783.

Gans, H.J. (1999) 'Participant Observation in the era of "ethnography"', *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 28(5), pp. 540-548.

Garrett, B.L. and Hawkins, H. (2014) Creative video ethnographies, video methodologies of urban exploration, in Bates, C. (ed.) *Video methods: social science research in motion* London: Routledge, pp142-164.

Gitlin, T. (1980) *The whole world is watching*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.

Goggin, G. (2020) 'Digital journalism after mobility', *Digital Journalism*, 8(1), pp. 170-173.

Goujard, C. (2016) *Profiles in mobile journalism: Bringing #mojo into the newsroom*. Available at: <https://ijnet.org/en/story/profiles-mobile-journalism-bringing-mojo-newsroom>. (Accessed; 1 December, 2018).

Granger, J. (2019) *We need to use smartphones smartly, key takeaways from Asia's first mobile journalism conference*. Available at: <https://www.journalism.co.uk/video/-we-need-to-use-smartphones-smartly-/s400/a741079/> (Accessed; 29 October 2019).

Gray, P. (2011) 'Exchange and access in field work', in Atkinson, P. and Delamont, S. (eds.) *Sage qualitative research methods*. London: Sage, pp.310-331.

Green, D. (2019) *AI-powered journalism: a time-saver or an accident waiting to happen?* Available at: <https://www.journalism.co.uk/news/automatically-generated-journalism-risks-unintentional-bias-in-news-articles/s2/a747239/> (Accessed; 20 November 2020).

Green, L. (2002) *Communication, technology and society*. Perth, Australia: Sage Publications Ltd.

Grieco, E. (2018) *Newsroom employment dropped nearly a quarter in less than 10 years, with greatest decline at newspapers*. Available at: <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2020/04/20/u-s-newsroom-employment-has-dropped-by-a-quarter-since-2008> (Accessed; 6 February 2019).

Guerrero-Pico, M., Masanet, M.J. and Scolari, C.A. 'Toward a typology of young producers: teenagers, transmedia skills, media production and narrative and aesthetic appreciation', *New Media and Society*, 21(2), pp. 336-353.

Guillaumier, C. (2016), 'Reflection as creative process: perspectives, challenges and practice', *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education*, 15(3-4), pp. 353-363.

Gulyas, A. Baines, D. (2020) *The Routledge companion to local media and journalism*. London: Routledge.

Hadland, A., Borges R.E. and , Hadland, J. (2017) 'Mobile phones and the news', *Convergence*, 25(3), pp. 428-448. DOI:10.1177/1354856517703964

Hagan, S.M. and Barron, D. (2019) 'Reviewing practice-based design research—the pursuit of a disciplinary destination', *The Journal of Design Economics and Innovation*, 5(1), pp.55-73. DOI:10.1016/j.sheji.2018.12.001

Hanitzsch, T. and Vos, T.P. (2017), 'Journalistic roles and the struggle over institutional identity: the discursive constitution of journalism', *Communication Theory*, 27(2), pp. 115-135.

Harlow, S. Chadha, M. (2019) 'Indian entrepreneurial journalism', London, *Journalism Studies*, 20(6), pp. 891-910.

Hardy, F. (1979) *Grierson on documentary*. London: Faber and Faber.

Heckman, M. Wihbey, J. (2019) 'The local-mobile paradox: missed innovation opportunities at local newspapers', *Newspaper Research Journal* 2019, 40(3), pp. 317-328.

Henry, S.G. and Fetters, M.D. (2012) 'Video elicitation interviews: a qualitative research method for investigating physician-patient interactions,' *Annals of Family Medicine*, 10(2), non-paginated. doi:10.1370/afm.1339.

Hernandez, N. (2018) *New mobile journalist guide*. Available at: <https://ijnnet.org/en/story/new-mobile-journalism-guide-has-free-resources-reporters-newsrooms> (Accessed; 5 November 2019).

Herzog, W. (2016) *Lo and behold: reveries of the connected world*. Available at: <https://vimeo.com/198891818> (Accessed; 29 October 2019).

Higgins, Smith, A. M. (2014) *The language of journalism: A multi-genre perspective*. London: Bloomsbury.

Holt, K. and Karlsson, M. (2013) 'Random acts of journalism? How citizen journalists tell the news in Sweden', *New Media & Society*, 17(11), pp 1795-1810.

Homans, G.C. (1958) 'Social behaviour as exchange', *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), pp. 597-606.

Hughes, M. (2018) 'Auto ethnography a methodology, to integrate professional and academic learning in journalism education', *Journalism Education*, 7(1), pp. 39-49.

Hull, W. (2012) *Legendary Locals of Chattanooga*. Mount Pleasant, CA: Arcadia Publishing.

Imhoff, K. (2012) *The quality of the media*. Zurich, Switzerland: University of Zurich.

Iphofen, R. (2013) *Research ethics in ethnography/anthropology*. Brussels, Belgium: European Commission.

Ireton, C. Posetti, J. (2018) *Journalism, fake news and disinformation*. Paris, France: UNESCO.

Jamil, S. and Appiah-Adjei, G. (2019) 'Journalism in the era of mobile technology: the changing pattern of news production and the thriving culture of fake news

in Pakistan and Ghana', *World of Media: Journal of Russian Media and Journalism Studies*, 1(3), pp. 42-64. DOI: 10.30547/worldofmedia.3.2019.2

Jensen, J.L., Mortensen, M. and Ørmen, J. (2016) *News across media: production, distribution and consumption*. London: Routledge.

Karhunen, P. (2017) *Closer to the story? Accessibility and mobile journalism*. Oxford, UK: Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, University of Oxford.

Kafai, Y. and Pepler, K. (2011) Youth technology, and DIY: developing participatory competencies in creative media production.' in Gadsden, V.L., Wortham, S. and Lukose, R. *Youth Cultures, Language and Literacy: 35 (Review of Research in Education)*. Washington, DC: American Educational Research Association, pp. 89-119.

Kaka, N. (2019) *Digital India, technology to transform a connected nation*. San Francisco, CA: McKinsey Global Institute.

Kay, M. (2019) *Transforming the future of digital journalism*. Hampshire, UK: Wilton Publishing.

Kelly, P. (2016) 'Creativity and autoethnography: representing the self in documentary practice', *Screen Thought: A Journal of Image, Sonic, and Media humanities*, 1(1), pp. 1-9. https://55fe5255-a4d9-45fa-8d5c-c7dcac88eadf.filesusr.com/ugd/0d1f4b_540f66dae00e443b97b4ac3714225ef2.pdf

Keyden, N. (2018) 'STV2 to close as Scottish broadcaster axes 59 jobs', *Daily Record*, 16 May. Available at: <https://www.dailyrecord.co.uk/news/science-technology/stv2-close-scottish-broadcaster-axes-12543416>, (Accessed: 17 September 2019).

Khan, S. (2016) *Yusuf Omar joins Hindustan Times as mobile editor*. Available at: <https://www.exchange4media.com/digital-news/yusuf-omar-joins-hindustan-times-as-mobile-editor-65095.html> (Accessed 18 February 2021).

Kitamura, J. (2013) 'The relationship between use of the internet and traditional information sources: an empirical study in Japan', *Media and Society*, 3(2), pp. 1-9.

Kolb, D. (1984) *Experiential learning: experience as the source of learning and development*. Hoboken, NJ: Prentice-Hall Publishing.

Kormelink T.G. and Meijer, I.C. (2014) 'Tailor-made news: Meeting the demands of news users on mobile and social media', *Journalism Studies*, 14(5), pp. 632-641.

Koushik, K. (2018) *NDTV and MoJo: revolution in journalism or a coup by media business?* Available at <https://indiaresists.com/ndtv-and-mojo-revolution-in-journalism-or-a-coup-by-media-business/> (Accessed: 18 February 2019).

Kovach, B. and Rosenstiel, T. (2001) *The elements of journalism: what news people should know and the public should expect*. 4th edn. Reston, VA: American Press Institute.

Kumar, A. and Haneef, M.S.M. (2017) 'Is MOJO (En) de-skilling?' *Journalism Practice*, 12(10), pp. 1292-1310.

Lancaster, K. (2013) *Video journalism for the web: a practical introduction to documentary storytelling*. London, Routledge.

Laurier, E. (2016) 'Participant observation' in Clifford, N., Cope, M. and Gillespie, T.W. *Key Methods in Geography*, 3rd edn. London: Sage, pp 169-181.

Latour, B. (1987) 'Science in Action', Cambridge, MA: Harvard Press

Latour, B. (1996) *Aramis the love of technology*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Press.

Latour, B. (1999) 'Factures/Fractures: From the concept of the network to the concept of attachment. Available at:

<https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/RESv36n1ms20167474?journalCode=res> (Accessed: 11 August 2021).

Learmouth, A. (2019) 'Stars "Consider Quitting" BBC Scotland show as ratings plummet', *The National*, 13 May. Available at:

<https://www.thenational.scot/news/17634726.stars-consider-quitting-bbc-scotland-show-as-ratings-plummet/> (Accessed: 8 August 2019).

Lee, E., Edson, C. and Tandoc, C. (2017) 'When news meets the audience: how audience feedback online affects news production and consumption', *Communication Research*, 43(4), pp. 436-449.

Lees, C. (2017) *Attacks on the press-the impact of technology*. Available at: <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/risj-review/attacks-press-impact-technology>, (Accessed: 4 October 2018).

Legget, M. (2006), 'Interdisciplinary collaboration and practice-based research, *Convergence: the International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*', 12 (3), pp. 263-269.

Lichterman, J. (2017) 'Swipe to unlock: Steve Jobs introduced the iPhone 10 years ago today, changing journalism forever', Available at: <http://www.niemanlab.org/2017/01/swipe-to-unlock-steve-jobs-introduced-the-iphone-10-years-ago-today-changing-journalism-forever/> (Accessed: 5 December 2018).

Lierop, M. (2015) 'Categorizing the Problems of Difficult Field Research', master's Thesis. Radboud University. Available at: https://theses.uhn.ru.nl/bitstream/handle/123456789/3873/Lierop%2C_Michiel_van_1.pdf?sequence=1 (Accessed: December 16th 2018).

Lin, L. and Zhao, Y. (2018) 'Towards SoMoLo journalism and SoMoLo activism: case studies of Macau netizens digital practices', *Media International Australia*, 173(1), pp. 93-107.

Ling, R. and Horst, H.A. (2011) 'Mobile communication in the global south', *New Media and Society*, 13(3), pp. 363-374.

López-García, X., Rodríguez-Vázquez, A. and Pereira-Fariña, X. (2017) 'Technological skills and new professional profiles: present challenges for journalism', *Comunicar: Media Education Research Journal*, 25(53), pp. 81-90. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C53-2017-08>

Mabweazara, H.M. (2011) 'Between the newsroom and the pub: the mobile phone in the dynamics of everyday mainstream journalism practice in Zimbabwe', *Journalism*, 12(6), pp. 692-707.

Mabweazara, H.M., Mudhai, O.F. and Whittaker, J. (2014) *Online journalism in Africa: trends, practices and emerging cultures*. London: Routledge.

Maccise, D.L. and Marai, M. (2016) *Mobile Journalism*. Doha, Qatar: Al Jazeera Media Training and Development Centre.

Mahoney, L.M. and Tang, T. (2020) *The Rowman & Littlefield Handbook of Media Management and Business*. Lanham, MD: Rowman and Littlefield Publishers.

Mandaville, M. (2009) *Citizen-soldier handbook: 101 ways every American can fight terrorism*. Indianapolis: Dog Ear Publishing.

Marconi, F., Siegmund, A. and Machine Journalist – An amalgamation of various artificial intelligence systems (2017) *The future of augmented journalism: a guide for newsrooms in the age of smart machines*. New York, NY: Associated Press.

Marrouch, R. (2014) 'How mobile phones are changing journalism practice in the 21st Century', Available at: <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/risj-review/how-mobile-phones-are-changing-journalism-practice-21st-century> (Accessed: 6 February 2019).

Mehta, V. (2019) 'The street: a fluid place of social /cohesion', in Aelbrecht, P and Stevens, Q (eds.) *Public space design and social cohesion: an international comparison*. London: Routledge.

Meltzer, K. (2010) *TV news anchors and journalistic tradition: how journalists adapt to technology*. Bern, Switzerland: Peter Lang Publishing.

Miller, M, Jessell, H, (2021) *Nexstar still No.1; Gray, Scripps, Allen busy buyers*. Available at: <https://tvnewscheck.com/business/article/nexstar-still-no-1-gray-scripps-allen-busy-buyers/> (Accessed: 6 August 2021).

Mills, J., Pellanda, E. and Pase, A. (2017) 'New Interactions: the relationship between journalists and audiences mediated by Google Glass', *Journalism Practice*, 11(8), pp. 980-999.

Mohammedsalih, S. (2017) *Mobile Journalism, Using Smartphone in Journalistic Work*. Masters Thesis. University of Uppsala. Available at: <http://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1305490&dswid=1714> (Accessed: October 8th 2019).

Monteiro, A. (2017) *How media outlets and journalists can develop their audiences: advice for tracking and growing your metrics*. Available at:
<https://utw10693.utweb.utexas.edu/blog/00-18547-how-media-outlets-and-journalists-can-develop-their-audiences-advice-tracking-and-grow> (Accessed: 30 November 2018).

Murphy, C. (2020) *Changing by the click: the professional development of UK journalists*. Available at:
https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/77633603/education_09_00249.pdf
(Accessed: November 20th 2020).

Murphy, E. (2020) *A guide to remote mobile ethnography*. Available at:
<https://indeemo.com/blog/remote-mobile-ethnography> (Accessed: 7 May 2020).

Murthy, D. (2008) 'Digital ethnography: an examination of the use of new technologies for social research', *Sociology*, 42(5), pp. 837-855.

Myers, E. (2012) "'Blogs give regular people the chance to talk back": rethinking "professional" media hierarchies in new media', *New Media and Society*, 14(6), pp. 1022-1038.

Nash, K., Hight, C. and Summerhayes, C. (eds.) (2014) *New documentary ecologies: emerging platforms, practices and discourses*. New York, NY: Springer Publishing.

Nelson, J.L. (2020) 'The persistence of the popular in mobile news consumption', *Digital Journalism*, 8(1), pp. 87-102.

Nelson, J.L. Lei, R.F. (2017) 'The effect of digital platforms on news audience behaviour', *Digital Journalism*, 6(13), pp. 619-633.

Newman, N., Fletcher, R., Kalogeropoulos, A., Levy, D.A.L. and Nielsen, R.K. (2018) '*Reuters Institute digital news report 2018*', Oxford: Reuters Institute at the University of Oxford.

Niedderer, K. Roworth-Stokes, S. (2007) 'The Role and use of creative practice in research and its contribution to knowledge', from the conference *IASDR07*, Kowloon, Hong Kong: 15 November 2007. Available at: <http://niedderer.org/IASDR07SRS.pdf> (Accessed: August 4th 2020).

Noshir, K., Madgavkar, A., Kshirsagar, A., Gupta, R., Manyika, J., Bahl. and Gupta, S. (2019) *Digital India*. Bengaluru, India: McKinsey Global Institute. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/digital-india-technology-to-transform-a-connected-nation> (Accessed: July 25th 2020).

Nygren, K. and Gidlund, K.L. (2012) 'The pastoral power of technology. Rethinking alienation in digital culture', *Communication, Capitalism & Critique*, 10, pp. 509-517.

Ohme, J. (2020) 'Mobile but not mobilized? Differential gains from mobile news consumption for citizens political knowledge and campaign participation', *Digital Journalism*, 8(1), pp. 103-125.

Oliver, D.G., Serovich, J.M. and Mason, T.L. (2005) 'Constraints and opportunities with interview transcription: towards reflection in qualitative research, *Social Forces*, 84(2), pp. 1273-1289.

Olmsted, S.C., Rim, H. and Zerba, A. (2012) 'Mobile News Adoption among Young Adults: Examining the Roles of Perceptions, News Consumption, and Media Usage', *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 90(1), pp. 126-147.

O'Brien, D., Wellbrock, C. and Kleer, N. (2020) 'Content for free? Drivers of past payment, payment intent and willingness to pay for digital journalism: a systematic literature review', *Digital Journalism*, 8(5), pp. 643-672.

Örnebring, H. (2010) 'Technology and journalism-as-labour: historical perspectives', *Journalism*, 11(1), pp. 57-74.

Otufodunrin, K. (2017), 'Journalism in the 21st century', *The Nation*, Available at: <https://thenationonlineng.net/journalism-21st-century-opportunities-challenges/> (Accessed 25 January 2021).

Owen, T. and Bell, E. (2017) 'The platform press: how Silicon Valley reengineered journalism', *Columbia Journalism Review*, 29 March. Available at: https://www.cjr.org/tow_center_reports/platform-press-how-silicon-valley-reengineered-journalism.php (Accessed: 13 March 2020).

Palmeiri, C. (2016) 'The sixth estate will restore hope to news media', *LinkedIn*, 2 October Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/sixth-estate-restore-hope-news-media-chase-palmieri/> (Accessed: 14th October 2018).

Papacharissi, Z., Streeter, T. and Gillespie, T. (2013) 'Culture digitally: habitus of the new' *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 57(4), pp. 596-607. DOI: 10.1080/08838151.2013.846344

Paul, S. (2018) 'Between participation and autonomy', *Journalism Practice*, 12(5), pp. 526-542.

Pavlik, J. (2010) 'The impact of technology on journalism', *Journalism Studies*, Volume 1(2), pp. 229-237.

Pavlik, J.V. (2015) 'Transformation: examining the implications of emerging technology for journalism, media and society', *Athens Journal of Mass Media and Communications*, Volume 1(1), pp. 9-24.

Pedersen, S. (2017) *Mobile journalism: professional tips and gear*. Available at: <https://www.shure.com/en-US/performance-production/louder/mobile-journalism-professional-tips-and-gear-list> (Accessed: 16 July 2019).

Perebinossoff, P. (2012) *Real-world media ethics*. Waltham, MA: Focal Press.

Pereira, F., Coutinho, I., Maia, K. and Moura, D. (2013) 'Journalism and professional identity', SBPjor, *Brazilian Journalism Research*, 9(2), pp. 4-8.

DOI [10.25200/BJR.v9n2.2013.613](https://doi.org/10.25200/BJR.v9n2.2013.613)

Perez, S. and Cremadas, M. (2014) 'The multimedia journalist in large-market television newsrooms: can old dogs learn new tricks? Do they want to?' *Electronic News*, 8(3), pp. 159-176.

Perreault, G. Stanfield, K. (2018) 'Mobile journalism as lifestyle journalism?' *Journalism Practice*, 13(3), pp. 331-348.

Peters, C. (2012) 'Journalism to go: The changing spaces of news consumption', *Journalism Studies*, 13(5), pp. 695-705.

Podger, C. (2019) 'How to Mojo, integrating mobile learning in journalism education', Available at: <https://jeraa.org.au/how-to-mojo-integrating-mobile-learning-in-journalism-education/> (Accessed: 10 April 2021).

Polsky, N. (1998) [1967] *Hustlers, beats and others*. New York, NY: The Lyon Press.

Raum, O. (1980) *The Press Council in Norway: a buffer between the press and society*. Paris, France: The Vigilant Press published by UNESCO.

Rhodes, K. (2014) *Straight to camera, clips that sell*. Available at: <https://clipsthatsell.com.au/blog/straight-to-camera-versus-interview/>, (Accessed: 11 August 2019).

Richardson, A.V. (2020) 'The coming archival crisis: how ephemeral video disappears protest journalism and threatens newsreels of tomorrow', *Digital Journalism*, 8(10), pp. 1338-1346.

Riley, Christou, M, M. (2012) *The craft of the cut: the final cut Pro X editor's handbook*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley and Sons Publishers.

Rogers, E. (2003) *Diffusion of innovations*. 5th edn. New York, NY: Free Press.

Rottwilm, P. (2014) *Future of journalistic work*. Oxford: Reuters Institute at Oxford.

Russo, T.C. (1998) 'Organizational and professional identification: a case of newspaper journalists', *Management Communication Quarterly*, 12(1), pp. 72-111.

Rust, C., Mottram, J. and Till, J. (2007) *Review of practice-led research in art, design & architecture*. Sheffield, UK: Sheffield Hallam University. <http://shura.shu.ac.uk/7596/>

Ryan, K.M. (2014) 'Video journalism, beyond the one-man band'. Review of *Video journalism, beyond the one-man band*, by Mary Angela Bock. *Journalism*, 15(8), pp. 1129-1131.

Ryan, M. (2001) 'Journalistic ethics: objectivity, existential journalism, standpoint epistemology, and public journalism', *Journal of Mass Media Ethics*, 16(1), pp. 3-22.

Safi, M. (2017) *Guardian*, *Indian Investigators raid premises linked to NDTV founders*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2017/jun/05/indian-investigators-raid-premises-linked-to-ndtv-founders-prannoy-radhika-roy> (Accessed: 10 August 2019).

Sage, Dainty, Brookes, D, A, N, (2011) 'How actor-network theories can help in understanding project complexities', London, UK: Emerald Publishing, *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*

Skains, R.L. (2018) 'Creative practice as research: discourse on methodology', *Media Practice and Education*, 19(1), pp. 82-97.

Sage, D., Vitry, C. and Dainty, A. (2020) 'Exploring the organizational proliferation of new technologies: an affective actor-network theory', *Organisational Studies*, 41(3), pp. 345-363.

Salzmann, A., Guribye, F. and Gynnild, A. (2021) "'We in The Mojo Community'" - exploring a global network of mobile journalists', *Journalism Practice*, 15(5), pp. 620-637.

Scanlan, C. (2003) *Writing from the top down*. Available at: <https://www.poynter.org/reporting-editing/2003/writing-from-the-top-down-pros-and-cons-of-the-inverted-pyramid/> (Accessed: 15 October 2018).

Schmelzer, R. (2018) *Automated journalism creeps into newsrooms leaning on AI*. Available at: <https://searchenterpriseai.techtarget.com/feature/Automated-journalism-creeps-into-newsrooms-leaning-on-AI> (Accessed: 12 October 2018).

Schultz, I. (2007) 'The journalistic gut feeling: journalistic doxa, news habitus and orthodox news values', *Journalism Practice*, 1(2), pp. 190-207.

Schröder, K.C. (2014) 'New media old and new: fluctuating audiences, news repertoires and locations of consumption', *Journalism Studies*, 6(1), pp. 60-78.

Scott, C. (2016) *How mobile journalism is rising in popularity*. Available at: <https://www.journalism.co.uk/news/how-mobile-journalism-is-rising-in-popularity-around-the-world/s2/a633170/> (Accessed: 30 July 2019).

Scuttarti, A. (2019) *Cycling and motorcycling tourism: an analysis of physical, sensory, social, and emotional features of journey experiences*. New York: Springer International Publishing.

Shu, Wang, Lee, Liu, K, S, D, H. (2020) *Disinformation, misinformation and fake news in social media: emerging research challenges and opportunities*. New York: Springer International Publishing.

Silver, L. (2019) Smartphone ownership is growing rapidly around the world, but not always equally. Available at:

<https://www.pewresearch.org/global/2019/02/05/smartphone-ownership-is-growing-rapidly-around-the-world-but-not-always-equally/> (Accessed: 1 December 2019).

Singh, A.D., Raghunathan, S., Robeck, E. and Sharma, B. (2018) 'Cases on smart learning environments', Hershey, PA: IGI Global.

Sinha, A. (2018) 'NDTV launches Hop Live, mobile-only LIVE channel with vertical format videos', NextBigWhat, [Online] Available at <https://nextbigwhat.com/ndtv-launches-hop-live-mobile-only-live-channel-with-vertical-format-videos/> (Accessed; January 21st 2019)

Sjovaag, H. (2011) *Journalistic ideology: professional strategy, institutional authority and boundary maintenance in the digital news market*. PhD thesis. University of Bergen. Available at: <https://bora.uib.no/bora-xmlui/handle/1956/5434> (Accessed: January 21st 2019).

Slaughter, S. (1998) *Easy digital video*. London: Abacus Publishing.

Smith, H. (2009) *Practice-led research, research-led practice in the creative arts*. Edinburgh, UK: Edinburgh University Press.

Spyridou, L., Matsiola, M., Veglis, A., Kalliris, G. and Dimoulas, C. (2013) 'Journalism in a state of flux: journalists as agents of technology innovation and emerging news practices', *International Communication Gazette*, 75(1), pp. 76-98.

Stephens, M. (2014) *Beyond news*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.

Sundet, V. (2012) *Making sense of mobile media. Institutional working notions, strategies and actions in convergent media markets*. PhD Thesis. University of Oslo. Available at: DOI:[10.13140/RG.2.2.25337.88163](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25337.88163) (Accessed: February 18th 2019).

Swearingen, J. (2018) *We're no longer in smartphone plateau. We're in the smartphone decline*. Available at: <http://nymag.com/intelligencer/2018/12/global-u-s-growth-in-smartphone-growth-starts-to-decline.html/> (Accessed: 5 December 2018).

Teves, E.C. (2016) *Breaking television news: is social media coverage you can count on?* DBA thesis. University of the Incarnate Word. Available at: https://athenaeum.uiw.edu/uiw_etds/7/ (Accessed: February 20th 2020).

The University of Manchester, School of Journalism (2013) *What is mobile journalism?* Available at: <https://schoolofjournalism.co.uk/blog/what-is-mobile-journalism/>, (Accessed: 8 October 2018).

Thomsen, L.H. (2014) *Ethnographic fieldwork: studying journalists*. London: Sage.

Thompson-Bell, J. (2014) 'Deconstructed Narratives: A Composer's Perspective on Form, Process and Review'. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Deconstructed-narratives-%3A-a-composer%27s-perspective-Thompson-Bell/7ee3b592981aa1afa314229a6c1dd08d0df207cf> (Accessed: March 20th 2020).

Thurman, N. (2008) 'Forums for citizen journalists: adoption of user generated content initiatives by online news media', *New Media & Society*, 10(1), pp. 139-157.

Thurman, N. and Fletcher, R. (2018) 'Are newspapers heading toward post-print obscurity? A case study of *The Independent*'s transition to online-only', *Digital Journalism*, 6(8), pp. 1003-1017.

Topkins, A. (2017) *The 2018 drone journalism forecast*. Available at: <https://www.poynter.org/news/2018-drone-journalism-forecast> (Accessed: 14 October 2018).

Udupa, S. (2018) 'Enterprise Hindutva and social media in urban India', *Contemporary South Asia*, 26(4), pp. 453-467.

Väättäjä, H., Koponen, T. and Roto, V. (2009) *Developing practical tools for user experience evaluation: a case study from mobile news journalism*, Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220956257_Developing_practical_tools_for_user_experience_evaluation_a_case_from_mobile_news_journalism (Accessed: 27 July 2019).

Van Damme, K., Martens, M., Van Leuven, S., Abeele, M.V. and De Marez, L. (2020) 'Mapping the mobile DNA of news: understanding incidental and serendipitous mobile news consumption', *Digital Journalism*, 8(1), pp. 49-68.

Vine, J., Batty, C. and Muir, R. (2016) 'A question of ethics: the challenges for journalism practice as a mode of research', *Journal of Media Practice*, 17(2), pp. 232-249.

Walker, J. (2019) *BBC Scotland evening news bulletin among 21 programmes with no viewers*. Available at: <https://www.pressgazette.co.uk/bbc-scotland-evening-news-bulletin-among-21-programmes-with-no-viewers/> (Accessed: 6 July 2019).

Wall, S. (2008) 'Easier said than done: writing an autoethnography', London, UK: *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 7(1), pp. 38-53.

Wasserman, H. (2014) 'The ramifications of media globalisation in the global south for the study of media industries', *Media Industries*, 1(2), pp. 54-58.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3998/mij.15031809.0001.211>

Westlund, O. (2015) 'News consumption in an age of mobile media: patterns, people, place, and participation', *Mobile Media & Communication*, 3(2), pp. 151-159.

Whittaker, J. (2019) *Tech giants, artificial intelligence, and the future of journalism*. London: Routledge.

Willig, I. (2012) 'Newsroom ethnography in a field perspective', *Journalism*, 14(3), pp. 372-387.

Wu, S., Tandoc Jr, E.C. and Salmon, C.T. (2019) 'When journalism and automation intersect: assessing the influence of the technological field on contemporary newsrooms', *Journalism Practice*, Volume 13(10), pp. 1238-1254.

Xu, X. (2016) *Impacts of mobile use and experience on contemporary society*. Hershey, PA: IGI Global.

Zafra, N. (2014) *The digital reporter as a one-man band*. Masters thesis. Massey University Available at:
https://mro.massey.ac.nz/bitstream/handle/10179/6515/02_whole.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y (Accessed: September 20th 2020).

Zafra, N. (2018) 'Backpack reporting of Typhoon Haiyan in the Philippines, implications of convergent technologies on disaster reporting', *Pacific Journalism Review*, 24(1), pp. 102-122. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24135/pjr.v24i1.397>

Zangana, A. (2017) *The impact of new technology on the news production process in the newsroom*. PhD thesis. University of Liverpool, Available at:
<https://livrepository.liverpool.ac.uk/3008664/> (Accessed; 6 February 2020).

Zuboff, S. (2015) 'Big other: surveillance capitalism and the prospects of an information civilization', *Journal of Information Technology*, Volume 30(1), pp. 75-89.

Appendices

The following appendices provide more detailed information on the case site interviewees and the fieldwork approach during this study.

Appendix 1:

Participant Information Sheet

The Mojo Revolution

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to investigate how mobile video journalists and news producers and editors are delivering video news content at their respective stations in 5 different developed world northern hemisphere countries and how are they planning to maintain and evolve these output practices. This project builds on a practice-based career of the doctoral student and will be carried as a video documentary.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because as Broadcast Journalists, or person in a similar role, you will have knowledge about news and content gathering, techniques and services.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to undergo a short on camera interview if you are an editor or producer and if you are a reporter, you will be shadowed as the focus of one of 5 video arcs across 5 days. You may also wish to agree to a follow-up interview to find out more about your approach.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that this work will have a beneficial impact on how Mobile video journalism is delivered and supported in higher education by isolating best practice. Results will be shared with participants in order to inform their professional work.

Will I be debriefed after the study?

Yes, at the end of each day the researcher and participants if they require a debrief will assign a time slot to review the activity of that session. At the end of each 5 day arc a sit down debrief will take place where the participants can voice any concerns or raise any issues required.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998).

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Results of the research will be published in written form but also manifest themselves in a video documentary which will be available online. You will be identified in any report or publication. Your institution will be identified in any report or publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports or hard copy resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

Who has reviewed the study?

MCS Research Ethics Committee

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: *The Mojo Revolution*
:4638

Ethics Approval Number

Investigator(s): *James Mahon*

Researcher Email:

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

Initials

I agree to having my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)
capitals)

Name of researcher (block
James Mahon

Date

Signature:

Signature:

Questions MOJO Revolution

All interview questions will be distributed 7 days prior to arrival of researcher on site. Interviewees can stop interview at any time and can refuse to participate at any juncture. All interviews will be done on camera, edited, archived and shown to interviewees prior to final submission and or broadcast.

Final editorial judgement lies with researcher and supervisory team

Reporters x 5

- *When did you discover mobile video was an option over traditional cameras*
- *How have you found this technology has impacted content gathering*
- *Do you believe in mobile alone or a combination of broadcast camera kits also*
- *Give me an example of when mobile was more effective than traditional means*
- *Give me an example of when mobile failed to deliver as a content gathering tool*
- *Explain in what way mobile proves useful or not for content editing*
- *Does mobile effect how you disseminate content*
- *Has your audience reacted positively/negatively to your mobile journalism role*
- *What advice do you have for those breaking into the journalism world*
- *What should we as educators learn from you as practitioners and incorporate into our teaching.*

Editors x 5

- *How has mobile video journalism changed how you prepare news agendas*
- *Does mobile journalism content alter you live broadcasting capabilities*
- *How have younger and older news crews reacted to the implementation of this technology*
- *Where do you see the strengths and weakness of mobile technology lying for newsrooms*
- *Is there an economic benefit to your transition to these platforms*
- *How has staff training been implemented to adjust to these tech trends*
- *Where do you envisage your newsroom moving in the coming year, 2 years and 5 years from a technological standpoint.*
- *What do we as educators need to do to prepare students for this evolving industry*
- *Would you agree with the BBC's Nick Garnett that MOJO is dying or waning*
- *What advice do you have for aspiring reporters*

Producers x5

- *How has and does mobile journalism impact your role*
- *From the perspective of online content distribution what contribution has mobile made*
- *When it comes to story searching /news agenda setting, does mobile play a role*
- *From the perspective of off-site/in the field content delivery how has mobile been instrumental or not*
- *When it comes to SEO, tagging, social media output, has mobile journalism altered trends for your organisation.*
- *Do you envisage a newsroom where camera operators and traditional roles are obsolete*
- *Do you think there are dangers for one man band reporters in the field*
- *Give me an example of where mobile journalism failed to deliver a satisfactory outcome*
- *Give me an example of where mobile journalism exceeded expectations to aid news output*

Appendix 2:

Code	Title	Employer	(Years) Experience at time of interview in 2018 (STV + WDEF 12 and 2019 (NDTV + Léman Bleu
S-1	██████████, Reporter, one-man-band journalist covering Ayrshire	STV2 Scotland	14
S-2	██████████, Production Journalist, background in newspapers and social media	STV2 Scotland	2
S-3	██████████, Output Editor, focus on digital technology	STV2 Scotland	17
A-1	██████████, News Director, leads on staff training and newsroom management	WDEF12 USA	24
A-2	██████████ Reporter/Assignment Manager, supporting broadcast output and reporters in the field	WDEF12 USA	59
A-3	██████████, Reporter/Anchor, weekday	WDEF12 USA	5

	reporter and weekend anchor with live streaming specialism		
A-4	██████████, Web Producer, traditional broadcast news producer who transitioned into social media distribution	WDEF12 USA	35
I-1	██████████, Reporter/Anchor, political focus and data journalist background	NDTV India	10
I-2	██████████ Reporter/Correspondent, Strategic and Security Affairs Senior editor	NDTV India	19
I-3	██████████, Executive Producer, lead on technological innovation and created of NDTV Hop Live vertical channel	NDTV India	23
I-4	██████████ Deputy Production Lead, primary newsroom	NDTV India	25

	manager involved into Mojo implementation at NDTV		
I-5	██████████ Reporter/Anchor, social media journalist	NDTV Hop Live	10
I-6	██████████, Reporter/Anchor, celebrity and showbiz beat	NDTV Hop Live	9
I-7	██████████, Producer, lead newsroom organiser at NDTV Hop Live	NDTV Hop Live	4
G-1	██████████, Director, Head of newsroom and lead of Mojo transition in 2015	Léman Bleu	20
G-2	██████████, Sports Reporter, social media and digital journalist	Léman Bleu	9
G-3	██████████ Reporter/Anchor, first generation Mojo, trained and studied without cameras, breaking news beat	Léman Bleu	5
G-4	██████████ Reporter/Anchor, economic	Léman Bleu	5

	affairs specialist and lead news presenter		
G-5	██████████, Reporter, traditional broadcaster who transitioned to Mojo then back to blended approach, features producer	Léman Bleu	26
G-6	██████████, Reporter, Traditional TV journalist transitioning to Mojo	Léman Bleu	4
A-5	██████████, Reporter, Former cameraman turned one-man-band Mojo	WDEF12 USA	24
A-6	██████████, Reporter, - one-man-band camera and mobile journalist	WDEF12 USA	4
I-8	██████████ Technician, specialist with smartphone technology	New Delhi	3
I-9	██████████, Camera Person, Mojo videographer	NDTV Hop Live	5

I-10	██████████, In house reporter, production and web journalist	NDTV India	5
I-12	██████████ lead Anchor, principal presenter for NDTV bulletins and programmes	NDTV India	18